

**Information Disorder and Climate-Smart Agricultural Practice in
Oyo State, Nigeria**

By

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CERTIFICATION

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to the Glory of God, the Author and Finisher of our faith, for the grace to complete this programme.

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ABSTRACT

Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) has emerged as an important framework for improving resilience, productivity and sustainability in the face of worsening climate challenges. However, the effectiveness of CSA interventions is often threatened by information disorder, which includes misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation. In Nigeria, particularly in rural areas of Oyo State, farmers are increasingly exposed to inaccurate, inconsistent, or misleading agricultural information across formal and informal channels. Extant studies emphasis on information disorder has been on politics, health and foreign contexts, leaving a research gap on climate-smart agriculture information disorder among Nigerians. This study investigated understanding and knowledge, sources, the influence of information disorder on the adoption of Climate-Smart Agriculture practices and how farmers verify CSA-related information.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory, Inoculation Theory and Global Village Theory serves as the theoretical background to the study. An exploratory sequential mixed-method research design was adopted. A combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. Expert purposive sampling was employed to select four agricultural extension officers assigned to Eruwa, Akufo, Ijaye, and Ogbomosho farm settlements in Oyo State for interviews. Questionnaire was administered to 294 farmers drawn from a total population of 1,114 farmers in the selected settlements using criterion purposive sampling. In-depth interview was also conducted with 29 experienced farmers. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS (version 20), while qualitative data were thematically analyzed using NVivo.

72% of farmers have a general awareness of what CSA information disorder entails. This knowledge varies based on exposure and experience. Thematic analysis revealed that farmers associate information disorder with misleading weather forecasts, false input quality claims, inaccurate agricultural advice, and unfulfilled government promises. The study found that the major sources of CSA information disorder was government agencies (59.8%) and social media (59%). Information disorder among farmers has led to distrust (55%), financial losses (53%), and hesitation toward adopting CSA practices (36%), making about 20% of farmers revert to traditional methods. Farmers relied on extension officers, Agricultural institutions, personal experience, and farmer groups for fact-checking. Findings also show that the major challenges of fact-checking CSA information are conflicting information from trusted sources, misleading information from peers, poor network coverage, language barriers, and CSA technical jargons.

Information disorder weakens the adoption of CSA among farmers in Oyo State as result of loss of trust in CSA information received by farmers. It recommended that empowering trusted communication sources especially extension services and media literacy for farmers is important to counter its impact. There is need to improve CSA communication through fact-checked, culturally relevant content from trusted sources.

Keywords: Climate Change Communication, Misinformation, Extension Services, Media literacy, Social media

Word count: 415

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background to the Study

Agriculture constitutes a fundamental aspect of human development and sustenance, serving as a critical source of food and raw materials necessary for industrial advancement. Historically, agriculture has played an important role in supporting human civilisation, acting as the primary provider of food for both human and animal populations. Beyond sustenance, it also serves as a major employer globally and represents one of the earliest economic activities known to humanity, deeply embedded in human existence since antiquity.

Over time, agriculture has undergone significant transformation, evolving into a structured and increasingly mechanised sector. This transformation has necessitated the implementation of diverse strategies and interventions aimed at addressing the many challenges confronting the sector, including food insecurity, drought, flooding, disease outbreaks, conflict, and famine. Among these strategies, technological innovation has emerged as a major catalyst for agricultural development, contributing substantially to improved productivity and food security across various contexts (Rehman, Jingdong, Khatoon, Hussain & Iqbal, 2016). Globally, farmers have adopted cutting-edge technologies, such as robotics, GPS applications, biotechnology, genetic engineering, and advanced breeding techniques—to enhance productivity and operational efficiency. For instance, automation in planting, weeding, harvesting, and crop spraying has significantly reduced production costs while simultaneously improving precision and timeliness (Simonian & Chin, 2010). Likewise, genetic engineering has facilitated the development of pest-resistant and drought-tolerant crop varieties with enhanced yield potential (Ahirwar, Swarnkar,

Bhukya, & Namwade, 2019). This is not to say that all odds challenging agriculture are surmounted, being that the greenhouse gas emission, leading to climate change, is a major global concern, even despite technological advancements of the 21st century. To address this climate challenge, climate-smart agriculture has become imperative.

Climate-smart agriculture is a new paradigm in different human endeavours, especially agriculture, which is directly associated with climate change. Climate-smart agriculture is one of the many benefits that cannot be overemphasised. Climate-smart refers to practices and policies geared towards solving climate change generally. Climate-smart agriculture resonates around adaptation, mitigation, increased productivity and sustainability. It involves deploying practices like drought-resistant crops, efficient water management, and sustainable soil management to increase productivity and resilience to climate change. This has been seen to guarantee food security, which is one of the necessities of man, and climate change affects agricultural development and food security, attention must be properly focused; otherwise, the human crisis on a global scale becomes imminent. African farmers have been forced to embrace the climate-smart concept because of drought, flood and irregular rainfall. Climate-smart agriculture means adjusting to the changing climate, and such adjustments must focus on climate literacy. This aspect is crucial to this study because understanding climate change comes with vital information from a credible source. Technology-driven agriculture depends on knowledge-based exposure and opportunities, which vary from one place to another. In Africa, technology-driven agriculture is gradually gaining acceptance and usability. The narrative is different, especially in the rural areas where resources and knowledge in modern agriculture are low.

A major constraint to climate-smart agriculture in rural areas is misinformation (Ngigi and Muange, 2022; Okoronkwo, Ozioko, and Ugwoke, 2024; Ojo, Akangbe, Kolawole, and

Owolabi, 2024; Jellason, Conway, and Baines, 2021). Information disorder, otherwise known as misinformation or disinformation, poses a significant threat to climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices. This is because it can undermine farmers' understanding of climate change impacts, the benefits of CSA, and the accuracy of recommended practices. This can lead to reduced adoption of CSA, hindering efforts to improve food security, build resilience to climate change, and mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. How Information Disorder Impacts Climate-Smart Agriculture is very important for this study. The spread of false or misleading information about climate change can lead to complacency or scepticism among farmers, reducing their motivation to adopt CSA practices. Also, misleading Claims about CSA Practices. Misinformation about specific CSA techniques, such as the effectiveness of crop diversification or water management strategies, can lead to farmers making incorrect decisions, potentially harming their crops and resources.

At the fundamental level, accurate information is essential for basic human survival and well-being. From communicating potential dangers and threats to sharing knowledge about food, shelter, and health, the ability to convey and receive truthful information has been a cornerstone of human evolution and progress (Mercier & Sperber, 2017; Tomasello, 2019). Moving higher in social organisation levels, accurate information becomes even more important. In governance, law, and policymaking, accurate and factual information is crucial for informed decision-making, ensuring that policies and regulations are grounded in empirical evidence and serve the greater good of society (Cairney, 2016; Parkhurst, 2017). However, inaccurate or manipulated information in the aforementioned areas can have far-reaching consequences, undermining the principles of justice, transparency, and accountability (Jasanoff & Simmet, 2017; Oreskes & Conway, 2010).

Consequently, communication becomes imperative because the climate-smart concept is important to farmers, individuals, communities, and societies (Pearce, 1989; Trenholm & Jensen, 2008). For climate-smart agriculture to take root, communication must be established. This also means that information must be accurate and factual to ensure proper practice and the desired result. (Hanafiah, 2018; Fischhoff, 2018). Communications are diverse; they include personal and group communication. However, in the present dispensation, mass media, alternative media, and digital media make more impact. In shaping public opinion and awareness, the mass media and new media become powerful tools (Fadipe, 2018).

Succinctly, mass media serve as a primary channel for information on key issues and are widely used by individuals seeking to shape the opinions and actions of diverse audience (Apuke & Omar, 2021). More so, the role of mass media in facilitating development has been widely acknowledged (Ogundahunsi and Olaniyi, 2020; Khan, Atif and Ullah, 2018; Nwaolikpe, 2018; Muhammed, 2005). By disseminating accurate information, mass communication empowers individuals and societies to make informed decisions, promote positive change, and address pressing issues. Whether it is raising awareness about environmental concerns, advocating for sustainable practices, or educating the public on crucial developmental matters, the power of mass communication lies in its ability to reach a large, heterogeneous audience.

In Nigeria, research has addressed sources of climate change information and farmers' knowledge and attitudes towards climate-smart farming strategies (Oyedele, 2018; Adetayo *et al.*, 2023; Kasimu *et al.*, 2023). However, the specific issue of information disorder (misinformation, or disinformation) and fact-checking mechanisms related to climate change and climate-smart agricultural information has received limited attention. While some studies have

explored information disorder in the Nigerian context, they have primarily focused on politics and health (Apuke & Omar, 2021). Thus, there is a need for a proper understanding of the climate-smart concept of agriculture, which is relatively nascent in Nigeria, especially in Oyo State. Importantly, the climate of Oyo state is suitable for a variety of crops, at the same time, has experienced several climate efforts in terms of agricultural productivity. A state that is reliant on agriculture and contributes significantly to the GDP should be better equipped with information concerning climate-smart agriculture is essential.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Understanding climate-smart agriculture, in terms of approach, practice, and analysis, is a major concern attracting global scholarship. Scholars have discussed climate-smart agriculture, potential impacts, and implementation challenges, particularly regarding fairness, sustainability, and equity. This discourse is predicated on the climate change phenomenon. It is a complex and multidimensional issue that has significant implications for food sustainability and development in Nigeria and the rest of the world.

Furthermore, the focus of many studies on climate change communication has been mainly on media framing, which includes newspaper framing of climate change, mitigation and adaptation strategies, how climate change is portrayed in the media, framing of extreme weather events and related risk management (Ijeoma *et al.*, 2018; Balarabe & Hamza, 2020; Stecula & Merkley, 2019; Brito *et al.*, 2020). Efforts have also been made to understand audience perceptions and their impact on climate change adaptation decisions (Smith & Johnson, 2017; Okeke *et al.*, 2021).

Moreover, studies on the use of social media, climate change information dissemination, and the effectiveness of agricultural information disseminated through social media have also been carried out, with the majority of the findings pointing to a positive relationship between the increased flow of knowledge, information and agricultural development (Mavrodieva *et al.*, 2019; Pearce *et al.*, 2018; Sandeep *et al.*, 2022). More studies have found various issues that have emerged as a result of climate change in Nigeria. These include increased rainfall intensity, prolonged dry seasons, frequent floods, rising temperatures, severe windstorms, unpredictable rainfall pattern and distribution, late-onset rain, and early cessation of rain, drought and desertification, flood, sea level rise, changing rainfall patterns, deforestation, loss of biodiversity, energy challenges, urbanisation, health impact, conflict and migration, inadequate adaptation and mitigation (Onyeneke *et al.*, 2021; Ifeanyi-obi *et al.*, 2023; Ikumbur & Iornumbe, 2019; Odok *et al.*, 2018; Aroyehun, 2023; Olutumise, 2023).

Incidentally, there is an emerging issue in climate change communication. This is the spread of false information, which scholars have referred to as information disorder; an issue that encompasses misinformation, disinformation and malinformation. Studies have established that information disorder distorts public understanding and acceptance of scientific consensus and hinders the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices (Vosoughi *et al.*, 2018; Lewandowsky, 2020). Wardle and Derekshan (2017) examined information disorder from a broader perspective. This includes challenges, such as filter bubbles and echo chambers. Additionally, Ejaz, Ittefaq and Arif (2022) looked into the issue of misinformation in climate change communication by exploring how media reporters deal with misinformation on climate change and their perceptions of using fact-checking tools to combat it. Also, Vu, Baines and Nguyen (2022) emphasised the need for fact-checking in modern journalism, which is

instrumental in verifying claims and ensuring the accuracy of information presented to the public. Chowdhury, Abdulai, and Alam, (2023) focused on the review of misinformation in social and online media for agrifood sector while other studies have beamed their search light on fact-checking climate change, mitigating fake news with warning labels, partisanship in correcting misinformation, climate change misinformation on online platforms, prevalence and effects of misinformation and impact of fake news on media credibility. (Vu, Baines, and Nguyen, 2022; Koch, Frischlich, and Lermer, 2021; Jennings & Stroud, 2023; Treen, Williams, and O'Neill, 2020; Stubenvoll and Marquart, 2019; Hassan, Musa, Azmi, Abdullah, and Yusoff, 2023). A more recent study by Hassan, Musa, Latiff Azmi, Abdullah, Yusoff (2022) studied strategies employed by different stakeholders and media outlets to challenge or dismiss climate change. In 2023, they also analysed climate change disinformation across types, agents and media platforms in Malaysian newspapers.

Extensive scholarship on the issue of climate change information disorder exists in international contexts. However, there is a noticeable gap in research, specifically in the Nigerian context. Not many studies have examined the issues of information disorder (misinformation, disinformation, fake news) and fact-checking as regards the dissemination of climate change (climate-smart agriculture) information and its influence on farmers in Nigeria. One notable exception is the study by Edet (2024), which investigated the impact of information disorder on climate change adaptation practices of farmers in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study revealed that farmers receive misinformation from fellow farmers, which most of the time is circulated without the intention to deceive. Similarly, studies on climate-smart and sustainable agriculture have pointed to some key challenges, including limited access to reliable information among farmers, communication barriers such as high illiteracy rates and digital divides (Obidike, 2011; Olorunfemi *et al.*, 2020;

Adeagbo *et al.*, 2021; Oladeji *et al.*, 2016; Onyeneke *et al.*, 2020; Oladeji *et al.*, 2023). Meanwhile FactcheckAfrica (2024) found that that rural communities in Oyo State especially where farmer reside struggle to identify and combat misinformation due to low media literacy and limited digital access. More recently, the prevalence of misinformation affecting decisions on nutrition, fertiliser application, adoption of improved seedlings and organic farming (Chowdhury, Kabir, Abdulai, & Alam, 2023) all point to the fact that there is an urgent need for accurate, accessible, and well-structured agricultural information to support sustainable practices and food security. Therefore, this study examined the sources, nature, and extent of climate change information disorder affecting the dissemination of climate-smart agricultural information in Oyo State, Nigeria.

1.2 Aims and Objectives of the Study

The following are the aims and objectives of the study:

1. To determine Oyo State farmers' knowledge and understanding of climate-smart agriculture information disorder;
2. To identify the sources of climate-smart agriculture information disorder among farmers in Oyo State;
3. To examine how information disorder influences the practice of climate-smart agriculture among farmers in Oyo State;
4. To find out the mechanism through which Oyo state farmers fact-check climate-smart agricultural information;
5. To identify the challenges faced by farmers when fact-checking climate-smart agricultural information disorder.

1.3 Research Questions

1. How well do farmers in Oyo State know about climate-smart agriculture information disorder?
2. What are the sources of climate-smart agriculture information disorder among farmers in Oyo State?
3. How does information disorder influence the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practice among farmers in Oyo State?
4. What mechanisms do Oyo state farmers utilise in fact-checking climate-smart agricultural information disorder?
5. What challenges do farmers in Oyo State face when checking the accuracy of climate-smart agriculture information?

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study, through its investigation into the prevalence and implications of information disorder as it pertains to the adoption and practice of climate-smart agriculture (CSA) among farmers in Oyo State, Nigeria, contributes significantly to scholarship in the fields of communication, environmental studies, and agricultural development.

Firstly, the findings will enrich existing academic discourse on misinformation, extending beyond well-studied sectors such as politics and public health to encompass the relatively underexplored domain of climate-smart agriculture in Nigeria. The study offers fresh perspectives for communication scholars and researchers examining the dynamics of information disorder within the broader context of climate change communication, particularly in relation to the agri-food sector.

In addition, the significance of this study is not only limited to local issues, but it can be used to contribute to a more global understanding of information disorder and its effects on food security. This research is therefore consistent with the concepts of sustainable development particularly as advanced by the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) that climate-smart agriculture is one of the ways of dealing with the effects of climate change on agriculture. In essence, objective 2.4 of the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices by the year 2030 (FAO, 2019) further proves the justification and significance of this study.

Practically, this research will determine the sources of climate-smart agriculture information disorder among farmers in Oyo State. This will enable them to make informed decisions, avoid misleading information, and find accurate information about climate-smart agriculture. By addressing information disorder, the study will help to encourage sustainable farming practices, which will result in increased productivity and resource efficiency. Farmers with valid and accurate information can maximise the utilisation of their resources, leading to cost savings and higher yields.

In all, this timely study focused on an under-researched area and will add valuable knowledge regarding climate change communication and the real-world impacts of information disorder in the Nigerian communication sphere. It will encourage future scholarship, for communication researchers to conduct further studies on information disorder in the media of communication. It will also provide practical guidance to stakeholders seeking to improve climate literacy and sustainable farming practices.

1.5 Scope of the Study

This study is focused on investigating the influence of information disorder on the reception and practice of climate-smart agricultural information among farmers in Oyo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the research encompasses farmers engaged in diverse agricultural activities, including crop farming, livestock farming, and aquaculture.

The geographical scope of the study is limited to Oyo State, which has a prominent agricultural sector and is strategically positioned to benefit from climate-smart agricultural practices. According to Ashley-Dejo, Omoniyi, Olaoye, Fakoya, and Adelaja (2016), Oyo State is divided into four principal agricultural zones: Ibadan/Ibarapa, Ogbomoso, Oyo, and Saki. Each zone encompasses various farming settlements officially recognised by the Oyo State government. These include Ipapo, Ilora, Eruwa, Ogbomoso, Iresaadu, Fashola, Akufo, Lalupon, Iseyin, and Ijaiye. The population for this study comprises practicing farmers within these settlements. A purposive sampling method was used to choose the participants for the study, ensuring the inclusion of representative farming communities across the state.

1.6 Operational Definition of Terms

The following terms are used contextually and functionally in this study, reflecting how they apply to the research scope, participants, data collection, and interpretation in Oyo State, Nigeria:

1. Climate Change

As used in this study, climate change refers specifically to the shifts in weather patterns experienced by farmers in Oyo State over time, such as delayed rainfall, prolonged droughts, and

extreme temperature fluctuations, which are attributed to anthropogenic factors. These climatic alterations influence agricultural productivity and decision-making among local farmers.

2. Climate Change Communication

This denotes the process through which farmers in Oyo State receive, interpret, and act upon information related to climate change impacts and responses. It involves the use of various communication platforms (radio, television, community meetings, social media, agricultural extension services) to share messages aimed at improving awareness and responses to climate-related agricultural challenges.

3. Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA)

CSA in this study is understood as the specific set of farming practices that Oyo State farmers either adopt or are exposed to, which aim to increase agricultural yield, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and enhance resilience to local climate variability. These include techniques such as organic fertiliser application, drought-resistant crop varieties, crop rotation, and integrated water management.

4. Information Disorder

Operationally, this refers to instances where farmers in Oyo State encounter, believe, or act on false, misleading, inaccurate or distorted agricultural or climate-related information, regardless of whether such information was shared deliberately or inadvertently. This concept underpins the core of the study's investigation into how such content affects decision-making and behavioural patterns.

5. Fact-Checking

In the context of this study, fact-checking refers to the practical steps and informal strategies employed by farmers or information intermediaries (e.g., agricultural extension officers) to verify the validity of CSA information before adopting it. It encompasses checking with extension officers, peers, seeking expert advice, or comparing different sources before implementation.

6. Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies

These are contextually understood as the actual agricultural adjustments made by farmers in Oyo State in response to climate impacts. Mitigation refers to actions such as reducing burning practices or using renewable inputs, while adaptation includes practices like altering planting dates or selecting resilient crop varieties, as reported during interviews and surveys.

7. Fact-Checking Mechanism

This term refers to both formal (e.g., agricultural extension verification, NGO-led sensitisation) and informal (e.g., word-of-mouth corrections, mobile fact-checking apps) systems that farmers use in Oyo State to confirm the accuracy of climate-smart agriculture information. It is analysed in terms of accessibility, reliability and credibility.

8. Agri-Food Sector

For the purposes of this research, the agri-food sector encompasses the spectrum of activities in Oyo State from food production to consumption, with a focus on how smallholder farmers are influenced by, and contribute to, this value chain. The study evaluates how disruptions caused by misinformation affect agricultural output and local food security.

9. Knowledge

Knowledge refers to the demonstrable awareness and informed perspectives that farmers in Oyo State hold concerning climate-smart agricultural practices and information disorder. It is measured through their ability to correctly identify CSA techniques, differentiate between accurate and inaccurate information, and articulate relevant climate change impacts.

10. Understanding

In this study, understanding goes beyond basic awareness to signify the depth of insight that farmers display regarding the implications of information disorder on their agricultural practices. It is assessed by examining how well farmers are able to interpret and apply CSA concepts in response to real-world farming challenges.

11. Sources of Climate-Smart Agriculture Information Disorder

This refers to the specific channels—such as radio broadcasts, social media platforms (e.g., WhatsApp, Facebook), and informal farmers' community discussions, through which false or misleading agricultural information reaches farmers in Oyo State.

12. Influence on Practice

This operational term captures the observable or reported ways in which misinformation or disinformation affects the actual farming behaviours and decisions of respondents in Oyo State as regards information disorder on CSA adoption.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents two important aspects of the study; review of relevant literature and theoretical underpinning for this study. Looking into literature is essential because no research effort is totally new. This chapter reviews key variables of this study such as climate smart agriculture, information disorder, sources of information disorder, fact-checking and so on.

2.2 Conceptual Review

Different concepts in this study are discussed to establish a suitable background for the research. The review of the different concepts provides deep understanding of issues that may result in further academic investigation.

2.2.1 Climate-smart Agriculture (CSA)

Climate change presents a major threat to agricultural output and the security of food supplies all over the world. In response to these challenges, climate-smart agricultural (CSA) practices, which have gained prominence as a holistic approach, emerged as adaptive strategies to address climate change impacts and promote sustainable agricultural production. Several scholars have looked into the concept of climate-smart agriculture. First, as defined by the specialised agency of the United Nations (UN) that focuses on addressing global issues related to food and agriculture, the Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO), climate-smart agriculture is “agriculture that sustainably increases productivity, enhances resilience, reduces or removes

greenhouse gas emissions, and enhances achievement of national food security and development goals” (FAO, 2018).

Three key interconnected pillars of CSA are clear from the above definition; these include increased productivity, strengthened resilience, and mitigation of agriculture emissions. This indicates that climate-smart agriculture represents a holistic approach designed to simultaneously elevate agricultural productivity and address climate change concerns by reducing or eliminating greenhouse gas emissions, thereby fostering sustainable progress towards national food security and development goals.

Corroborating this definition are Oyewole *et al.* (2022:19), who say that “climate-smart agriculture focused on the strategic effort of integrating climate change and agriculture in development planning with a view to aggregating opportunities to link adaptation and mitigation efforts.” Moreover, other climate change scholars, Kombat, Sarfatti and Fatunbi (2021), assert that in reaction to the rising impact of climate change, scientists and researchers have innovated climate-smart agriculture (CSA) technologies, which include both traditional practices and entirely new approaches. These technologies, according to them, include drought-tolerant crop varieties, efficient irrigation systems like drip irrigation, techniques for improving soil fertility (e.g., intercropping, crop rotation, composting), improved weather forecasting and climate monitoring, solar-powered cold storage and drying facilities, greenhouses and hydroponics agroforestry techniques that incorporate trees into farmland, conservation agriculture techniques like reduced tillage integrated pest management strategies.

These technologies are essential for adapting to changing climatic conditions and must have characteristics such as drought tolerance, rapid growth and productivity, resilience against

various pests and diseases, effectiveness in low-fertility soils and the achievement of high crop yields, among other characteristics. Also, several studies have highlighted specific climate-smart agricultural practices that have been recognised in Nigeria. These practices include conservation agriculture, integrated soil fertility management, agroforestry, crop diversification, improved livestock feed and feeding practices, and the adoption of agricultural practices with climate-smart agriculture potentials (AP-CSAPs) at the farm level (Shiferaw, 2020; Oyawole *et al.*, 2020; Nkonya *et al.*, 2017).

In Nigeria, the National Agricultural Resilience Framework developed by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) outlines strategies for promoting climate-smart agriculture, including improved seeds, fertilisers, irrigation expansion, climate information services, and strengthening extension systems (FMARD, 2018). In 2022, the National Council on Climate Change (NCCC), which is the nationally designated authority to address the impacts of climate change in Nigeria, was established by President Muhammadu Buhari on September 28, 2022. This council was established by Section 3 of the Climate Change Act of 2021. The Nigerian climate change framework involves formulating green growth policies such as the NCCAP, implementing carbon trading and taxation mechanisms, administering a Climate Change Fund, ensuring emission reduction targets, fostering multi-sectoral partnerships, and supporting climate-smart agriculture through NiMet forecasts and research by institutes like IITA and IART.

One will ask if the activities of these agencies have yielded positive results in Nigeria. Certainly, as Abegunde, Sibanda, and Obi (2019) noted, the Uptake of climate-smart agricultural practices by small-scale farming households has been positively influenced by climate change-related education through improved extension contact and exposure to mass media, leading to integrated

farm activities that increased farm profit. This indicates that educational interventions and extension services from government and non-governmental agencies have played a crucial role in promoting the adoption of CSA practices in Nigeria.

2.2.2 Brief history of climate smart agriculture (CSA)

In the 1990s, concepts such as sustainable agriculture and "triple-win" approaches began to emerge in research, acknowledging synergies among increasing productivity, building climate resilience, and reducing agricultural emissions (Rockström, Steffen, Noone, Persson, Chapin III, Lambin, and Nykvist, 2007). Subsequently, in the early 2000s, climate change impacts on agriculture gained attention at major international summits on climate, food security, and development, giving birth to policy interest in sustainable approaches (Beddington, Asaduzzaman, Clark, Fernández Bremauntz, Guillou, Howlett, and Wakhungu, 2012).

By 2010, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) agreements in Cancun, Mexico, included agriculture, reflecting consensus on the vulnerability of farming and its potential role in mitigating climate change (FAO, 2019). These two areas of research and policy interest in the relationship between agriculture and climate change set the groundwork for the consolidation of climate-smart agriculture. The term climate-smart agriculture was introduced by the FAO at the 2010 Global Conference on Agriculture, Food Security, and Climate Change held in The Hague. Subsequently, this approach has been implemented by many international organisations and governments of nations worldwide (Neufeldt, Jahn, Campbell, Beddington, DeClerck, De Pinto, and Zougmore, 2013).

The formal definition and framework for climate-smart agriculture took shape in 2010 through collaborations such as the Consultative Group for International Agricultural Research (CGIAR)

programme on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security (CCAFS) (Lipper, Thornton, Campbell, Baedeker, Braimoh, Bwalya, and Torquebiau, 2014). This important moment paved the way for a seminal CCAFS paper by Lipper *et al.* in 2013, entitled Climate-smart agriculture for food security, which brought the concept to prominence. This paper synthesised key aspects into the three pillars of sustainably increasing productivity, strengthening resilience, and reducing emissions (Lipper *et al.* 2014).

Following the 2013 publication that solidified the concept and approach of climate-smart agriculture, there was a growing momentum to implement climate-smart agriculture approaches worldwide. One key initiative was the launch of the Global Alliance for Climate-Smart Agriculture (GACSA) at the 2014 UN Climate Summit (GACSA, n.d.). GACSA aims to share knowledge, tools and resources to empower widespread implementation of appropriate CSA strategies. Various region-specific programmes and partnerships formed after 2013 focused on enabling climate action in agriculture tailored to localized contexts and challenges. These include policy initiatives like the Africa Climate-Smart Agriculture Alliance, an organization that supports the coordination of investment plans in different African nations. Research projects such as CCAFS continue exploring innovations to refine practices and enhance participation by marginalized groups (Lipper and Zilberman, 2018).

Capacity-building efforts have specifically targeted scaling CSA among vulnerable smallholder farmers. For example, the Rockefeller Foundation has funded training networks like the Africa Climate Smart Agriculture Youth Network, which engages youth leaders to act as peer mentors and accelerators in their agricultural communities (Lipper and Zilberman, 2018). Similarly, the Global Alliance for the Future of Food supports CSA learning platforms across several African and Asian countries to educate extension agents and provide farmers with knowledge to make

decisions aligning production needs with climate realities. As part of the Africa Climate Smart Agriculture Alliance (ACSA) launched in 2014, Nigeria committed to developing an agricultural resilience framework and laying out key priorities for implementing CSA in the country.

Nigeria's National Agricultural Resilience Framework (NARF) is aligned with and upholds the nation's existing policy targets around further modernizing production systems set under the Agricultural Promotion Policy (APP) for 2016–2020. The APP was the guiding policy document for Nigeria's agriculture sector over these periods. (Vermeulen, Abubakar, Conway, Dziba, Hoevel, Ibe and Vervoort, 2014).

The following are the key CSA-related policy commitments under the APP enumerated in Nwozor and Olanrewaju (2020) that the resilience framework aims to support:

- Improving farmer access to technologies that enable sustainable natural resource use and regeneration
- Enhancing the capacity of agricultural systems to withstand climate change impacts through advice on adaptive practices and use of climate information services
- Promoting integration of nutrition objectives along with productivity growth through multi-cropping systems
- Increasing economies of scale through clustering of producers to support joint access to CSA solutions
- Developing risk mitigation financial instruments tailored to smallholder needs

2.2.3 Role of Information and Communication in CSA Adoption

The role of communication in the adoption of innovations such as climate-smart agriculture (CSA) is multifaceted and crucial for promoting the uptake of sustainable agricultural practices. Several studies have looked into this role, especially as it relates to climate-smart agriculture. Djido, Zougmoré, Houessionon, Ouédraogo, Ouédraogo, and Diouf (2021) conducted a study to find out the extent to which access to weather and climate information services promotes the uptake of climate-smart agriculture practices in Ghana. They found that in Ghana, access to weather and climate information services (WCIS) significantly enhances the adoption of water management and multiple cropping practices. Similarly, Anuga (2019) identified reliance on radio and television for weather information as a key factor in CSA adoption among smallholder farmers in the Techiman municipality, Ghana. In Nigeria, Tihamiyu, Ugalahi, Fabunmi, Sanusi, Fapojuwo, and Shittu (2018) averred that the possession of receivers such as radio has a positive effect on the uptake of climate-smart farming techniques. However, Senyolo (2020), in her investigation, highlighted the presence of barriers to the adoption of CSA technologies, including the characteristics of the technologies and the business models employed in the adoption of the innovation. These studies emphasised the importance of targeted information and communication strategies to address the barriers to promoting the uptake of climate-smart agricultural practices. Similarly, Long, Blok and Coninx (2016) identified some barriers to the adoption and diffusion of technological innovations for climate-smart agriculture (CSA) in Europe, which encompass socio-economic, organisational, and behavioural challenges.

These include a lack of management support and awareness, conflict with traditional methods, poor information, and market unattractiveness on the demand and supply sides. Additionally, organisational barriers such as lack of required competencies and behavioural barriers like

negative presumed assumptions and low trust of advisers contribute to the slow adoption of CSA innovations. Regulatory frameworks, overly scientific language, and market uncertainty further impede the uptake of technological innovations. Additionally, Aryal, Rahut, Maharjan, and Erenstein (2018) emphasised that the involvement of various stakeholders, such as farmers, agricultural institutions, service providers, and government departments, is imperative to promote widespread adoption of climate-smart agriculture (CSA). This brings to light the importance of employing inclusive and participatory communication strategies for the effective dissemination and uptake of CSA practices. Furthermore, Makate (2019) contends that the integration of local institutions and indigenous knowledge is a crucial component of these communication strategies, enhancing the adoption of innovations in climate-smart agriculture.

In summary, the above suggests that access to reliable agro-climate information enable farmers to make informed decisions in line with climate-resilient production systems. More so, providing smallholder farmers with relevant and accessible climate information services enhances the adoption of resilient practices. However, to overcome the prevalent challenges and involve more farmers in climate-smart agriculture, inclusive communication strategies facilitating participatory learning processes are crucial.

2.2.4 The Concept of Information disorder

In recent times, a challenge has arisen that has far-reaching consequences across various fields of study and consequently affects the reliability and accuracy of information available to individuals, communities and nations. This challenge is referred to as ‘information disorder. The emergence of information disorder, encompassing misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation, poses complex challenges for climate action. Within the climate-smart

agriculture (CSA) field, inaccurate or misleading information around weather, resilient practices, low-emissions techniques and related topics inhibits efforts to advance sustainable food production practices. This review looks into key literature documenting the manifestations, drivers, influences and responses to climate and agriculture information inaccuracies that prevent the adoption of climate-smart agriculture among nations.

Wardle and Dias (2017:1) define “information disorder as the spread of false or misleading information, often facilitated by the use of social media and online platforms.” This phenomenon, according to the authors, is influenced by various cognitive and social biases that affect individuals' perception and interpretation of information. The vulnerability of human memory to internal and external influences, as well as the bombardment of information through social networks and smartphones, contributes to the challenges in discerning the veracity of information. Furthermore, they added that individuals tend to engage in motivated reasoning, where their pre-existing beliefs influence the way they process new information.

The above assertion by Wardle and Dias has implications for this study on the uptake of climate-smart agriculture practices among farmers in Oyo State. The spread of information disorder, especially on social media, could be a major obstacle to getting farmers to embrace innovative adaptation techniques as included in climate-smart agriculture. With climate change being politically controversial in many quarters, motivated reasoning may lead farmers to reject the scientific consensus if it does not align with their pre-existing beliefs. More so, the constant bombardment of competing claims on social platforms could overwhelm farmers trying to discern the most effective practices. This strengthens the need for this study using various academic investigative tools in fields like communication and information science to understand the complex causes of information disorder.

Moreover, the term "social turn" was created as a result of the rise of social media, which brought about major changes in society. This is the belief of Frau-Meigs (2019), who also defined information disorder as the spread of false or misleading information, including disinformation, misinformation, and malinformation. This can include intentionally false information as well as content that is shared without proper verification or context, leading to confusion, distrust, and harm. He added that information disorder can have serious consequences for individuals, communities, and societies and can undermine the public's ability to make informed decisions.

Hamzat (2022), in his own view, believes the term "information disorder" has gained prominence in recent times and can be historically traced to the 2016 U.S. presidential campaign through the discourse of President Donald Trump. He explained that despite its contemporary association with "fake news," the concept is not entirely novel, as it has historical ties to the idea of propaganda, adding that information disorder is increasingly distorting economic and political space across the world. Steensen, Bélair-Gagnon, Graves, Kalsnes, and Westlund (2022) also agree with the assertion that this concept has gained prominence, especially in the context of modern democratic societies, where the dynamics of news and information have become dislocated from traditional journalism, leading to the dominance of information disorder. This emerging phenomenon demands urgent attention regarding how it may impact climate change communication and the uptake of adaptive farming innovations. Specifically, the spread of misleading claims surrounding climate change could present a major barrier to conveying scientifically backed information to farmers in Oyo State.

In the same vein, digital platforms have created a great crisis in the field of journalism and communication studies as a result of information disorder. As scholars have noted, the

unregulated spread of misinformation and disinformation has led to reduced public trust in the news media and create a gap between fact and fiction (Marwick, 2018; Tandoc *et al.*, 2018). This proliferation of false content damages the main tenets of professional journalism like objectivity, presentation of facts, and transparency. Furthermore, Steensen *et al.* (2022) noted that the crisis of information disorder has given room for new approaches to evaluating source credibility. Traditional methods of assessing information claims and producing knowledge must adapt to today's complex communication field. The implication here is that traditional methods (i.e., credibility of the author, publication source, editorial standards, and expert opinions) of evaluating information sources may no longer be entirely effective given the challenges posed by information disorder, especially with the rise of misinformation spreading rapidly through social media and other online platforms.

Wardle and Derekshan (2017) offered one of the first attempts to structure the information disorder ecosystem in a report issued by the Council of Europe in response to member states' growing worries about the repercussions of misinformation. They established a conceptual framework for investigating information disorder and identified three distinct groups of incorrect information categories. (See Figure 1.) They divided their groups according to how false the information was. The first is "misinformation," which occurs when false information is shared but no harm is intended; the second is "disinformation," which occurs when false information is shared with the intent to cause harm; and finally, "mal-information," which occurs when genuine information is shared to cause harm.

Figure 1. Information disorder hypergroups and types (Wardle and Derekshan, 2017:5)

Wardle and Derekshan (2017) also advocate for a focused examination of the individual components of information disorder. These are:

1. **Agents** - the source responsible for generating and disseminating information.
2. **Messages**- messages involves a close analysis of the content itself. This includes looking at the language used, the framing of information, and the presence of misinformation or disinformation.
3. **Interpreters** - The interpreters are the individuals or groups receiving and processing the information. Examining this element involves investigating how different audiences interpret and respond to information.

Figure 2. Elements of Information Disorder (Wardle and Derekshan, 2017:5)

For this study, a thoughtful analysis and critical look at the agents, messages, and interpreters involved in information disorder are important. As leading scholars like Wardle and Derekshan (2017) note, carefully examining each component of the information environment helps us better understand how information disorders emerge and spread. As regards the agents, this study will uncover who the key sources spreading agricultural misinformation are and look into their motivations. A look at the message of information disorder itself will help to see those rhetorics that influence farmers' decision-making with regard to climate-smart agriculture, while the investigation of the interpreter will focus on the individuals and groups receiving and processing information, i.e., extension agents and opinion leaders. It will look into the various interpretations of farmers in Oyo State, considering factors such as cultural background, education, and past farming experiences.

2.2.5 Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) and Information Disorder

Climate smart agriculture (CSA), as noted earlier, has generated growing attention as an integrative approach to strengthen productivity, adaptation, and emissions mitigation across agricultural systems to achieve sustainable food security amidst intensifying climate change (FAO, 2019). However, the acceleration of information disorder (mis, dis, and malinformation) poses risks of diminishing the credibility and reliability of the information and data that support and guide the adoption of CSA practices aimed at making agriculture more resilient and sustainable in the face of climate change. This review looks into key literature connecting CSA, information disorder dynamics, and climate-agriculture information inaccuracies preventing resilient practice adoption.

The review of literature on misinformation and disinformation about climate change reveals the impact of false or misleading information on public perceptions, attitudes, and policy responses. Studies have shown that exposure to misinformation can lead to increased polarisation, reduced support for mitigation policies, and hinder political action on climate change policies (Treen *et al.*, 2020; Lewandowsky *et al.*, 2013; Farrell, 2019). More so, experimental studies have shown that exposure to climate change misinformation can increase polarisation along ideological lines and reduce acceptance of scientific consensus like climate smart agriculture (Cook *et al.*, 2017; van der Linden *et al.*, 2017). For example, van der Linden *et al.* (2017) found that exposing participants to common climate myths reduced their perception of scientific agreement around anthropogenic climate change. This implies that misinformation about climate change may similarly hinder the adoption, perception, and effectiveness of climate-smart agricultural practices.

While discussing the challenges associated with public perception of climate change, particularly the polarisation of opinions despite a scientific consensus, Van der Linden, Leiserowitz, Rosenthal and Maibach (2017) noted that in the context of climate change discourse, the dissemination of information is vulnerable to various forms of misinformation and disinformation. Misleading narratives, often fueled by ideological or vested interests, contribute to what can be termed climate information disorder. This disorder encompasses the spread of inaccurate or deceptive information about climate science, contributing to the existing polarisation and hindering efforts to convey the scientific consensus. They, however, emphasised the importance of experts in guiding the public through the complexities and uncertainties of the issue.

One major contributor to the gap between actual and perceived consensus on anthropogenic-caused climate change is the deliberate deception of individuals presented as experts who actually lack relevant knowledge or expertise. According to Cook *et al.* (2017), politically and financially motivated lobby groups have organized petitions, like the discredited 1995 "Leipzig Declaration," meant to copy authoritative refutations of the scientific consensus, signed by dozens of scientists with unrelated or non-existent credentials. The document is known for expressing scepticism about the risks and advantages associated with genetically modified organisms in agriculture. It was purported to have been signed by a number of scientists who were presented as experts in relevant fields. However, the legitimacy of the signatories and the scientific rigour behind the declaration have been heavily questioned. Cook *et al.* (2017), however, submit that

Communications research has revealed that featuring such false experts expressing contrarian views measurably reduces the public's perception of scientific agreement on climate change,

and also diminishes acceptance of climate science and concern about the issue. Essentially, these fake expert voices amplify doubt and confusion, misleading the public about the level of consensus, hindering belief in anthropogenic climate change in service of political aims.

Furthermore, the semantic attributes of misinformation related to climate change on social media have been studied, showing its role in confusing the public, undermining the effect of science communication, and causing confirmation bias and polarisation (Chu *et al.*, 2023). Lewandowsky *et al.* (2013) also emphasised that the dissemination of misinformation on climate change has been identified as a barrier to political action and mitigation, emphasising the need to combat misinformation to address the challenges posed by climate change.

Stroud (2019) argues that misinformation in agriculture has a detrimental impact on farmers' ability to make informed decisions and undermines the role of science and decision-making in climate-smart agriculture. Stroud emphasises the need for accurate information exchange and suggests that creating a network that fosters such exchange is central to tackling the risk posed by misinformation to sustainable food production. She provides some examples of misinformation identified in her study:

1. Experts promoting solutions to address the loss of minerals from farmland soils and the damage to soil organisms like earthworms caused by chemicals.
2. Conspiracy theorists spreading false claims of secret ties between soil scientists and the pesticide industry in order to cast doubt on the scientists' credibility.
3. Analyses of publicly available data on earthworms in agricultural fields indicate that chemical farming practices at Rothamsted have harmed soil life and potentially led to soil deterioration.

4. The claim that farmers worldwide are transforming their land into underground deserts.

In a webinar; Misinformation Research, (2023) where Dr. Jeet Ramjattan, was interviewed on the examples of information disorder in agriculture, he enumerated the following:

1. Misleading advertisements and testimonials promoting unproven miracle products or crops, such as certain fertilizers, chemicals, or seeds that are claimed to boost yields well beyond realistic levels. These make unrealistic promises to farmers.
2. Pseudo-scientific claims and practices that are not backed by research, such as certain crop planting or livestock management techniques promoted as scientific even when evidence is lacking.
3. Downplaying or denial of climate change impacts regarding agriculture, which has the potential to discourage farmers from adopting appropriate climate smart practices.
4. Fake images and videos shared on social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube etc. portraying false information and claims about climate smart techniques.
5. Conspiracy theories and misinformation questioning well-established scientific research on topics like GMOs, sustainable agriculture, soil science etc. aimed at discouraging their adoption.
6. Biased interpretations of cherry-picked data to falsely claim certain practices are ineffective, dangerous etc.
7. Unverified anecdotes and personal testimonies used to make broad claims about agricultural technologies and practices.

8. Imposter content mimicking legitimate organizations or individuals to spread false agriculture information to farmers.
9. Intentionally misleading statistics, figures, maps etc. used out of context to make flawed arguments against climate smart techniques.

He emphasised that most of these types of information disorders are being extracted from social media because most farmers in the Caribbean region sometimes rely on social media, especially WhatsApp groups, as their primary source of agricultural information and advice. When asked which type of information disorder is most prevalent, he noted that misinformation seems to have the upper hand since a lot of false or misleading claims about climate-smart agriculture are unintentional—spread by individuals trying to promote themselves and gain popularity rather than intentionally inflict harm. However, he warned that even misinformation can have damaging effects by discouraging the uptake of climate-smart agriculture practices by farmers who are exposed to and believe false claims.

As social media proliferates as a source of agricultural advice for farmers, it has also become a conduit for various forms of misinformation that can undermine evidence-based practices like climate-smart agriculture. Given Nigeria's large population of smallholder farmers with increasing internet access (Sennuga, Baines, Conway and Naylor, 2020), there is an urgent need to assess the prevalence of climate-smart agriculture misinformation reaching them through various sources and how this may shape their perceptions and decisions.

In the same vein, Antoniou, Robinson, Castro and Hilbeck (2023), in their critical evaluation of the issue of misinformation in agriculture, discovered the presence of biased claims and misinformation in the agricultural sector, particularly in the context of genetically modified

organisms (GMOs) and pesticides. They pointed out that there is no demonstrated consensus on the safety of GMOs, as different researchers have produced diverse findings and interpretations concerning the safety and potential risks of GMOs.

In their review, Antoniou *et al.* (2023) identify several misleading claims made by advocates regarding genetically modified crops and the pesticides used with them. These include:

1. The claim that there is a scientific consensus on the safety of GMOs is misleading, failing to account for the uncertainties and incomplete understanding of their long-term impacts on health and the environment.
2. Overlooking evidence of GMO failure: the selective reporting of data by proponents of GMO, pointing out the reliance on outdated information to support claims of success in certain regions, such as India, while ignoring more recent evidence of widespread failure of GMO crops.
3. Misleading claims about retraction of studies: they argue that proponents of GMOs often misrepresent the retraction of studies critical of GMOs as evidence of scientific misconduct, ignoring the fact that retractions can occur for a variety of reasons and do not necessarily indicate scientific fraud.
4. Questionable and biased assertions regarding the effects and outcomes of GMOs in India: biased reporting of data on the impacts and performance of GMOs in India, pointing out the reliance on industry-linked studies and the omission of evidence of widespread failure and negative impacts on farmers.

5. Misleading portrayals of the history of GMOs in Africa: the development and adoption of GMOs on the continent is often misrepresented by proponents of GMOs, who ignore the complex social, economic, and political determinants affecting the uptake and impacts of agricultural technologies in the region.

Consequently, the above raises critical questions about the potential existence of similar biased narratives and misinformation surrounding climate-smart agricultural practices in Nigeria. We need to know the sources of these information and how they may have influenced the adoption of sustainable climate-resilient practices in Oyo State.

More so, it is evident, as stated in our problem statement, that many studies have been conducted in other climes as regards the issue of information disorder in climate change discourse, but a review of relevant literature further reveals that not much scholarly work has been carried out in this area in Nigeria. Information disorder became a topical issue in Nigeria, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. This time, the issue raises a lot of concerns because drivers of rumours, political distrust, inefficiencies in government institutions, and government misinformation were identified in studies as major contributors to information disorder leading to distrust in Nigeria (Ilo, Ezeibe, Oguonu, Nwankwo, Ajaero, and Ezeibe, 2020).

Furthermore, existing research has predominantly focused on health-related misinformation in Nigeria, investigating its impact and challenges, including studies on family planning and COVID-19 myths and misinformation (Ankomah, Anyanti, and Oladosu, 2011; Ali, Khalid, and Zahid, 2021). However, there is a noticeable gap in addressing information disorder within the agricultural sector. Recognising the vital role of agriculture in ensuring food security in Nigeria and globally, this study aims to address the gap by exploring the dynamics of information

disorder, specifically in the framework of climate-smart agriculture, and how the incidence of information disorder has influenced the reception of CSA techniques in Oyo State.

One recent study relevant to information disorder in Nigeria is by Okocha and Akpe (2022), who conducted a study on the impact of fake news and misinformation on COVID-19 attitudes in Nigeria. They averred that false information and misleading reports regarding COVID-19, which were prevalent in Nigeria during the pandemic, had a negative impact on public attitudes and behaviour towards the disease, and the spread of misinformation was shaped by factors like profession, education level, as well as the availability of information sources. Thankfully, the media was instrumental, according to them, in helping combat the spread of misinformation; however, their credibility was also affected by the widespread occurrence of false information. Okocha and Akpe (2022) recommended that there is a need for media literacy programmes, fact-checking initiatives, and collaboration between media organisations and health authorities to combat the spread of misinformation and promote credible sources of information. The relevance of the above study is revealed in that it highlights the negative impact of fake news and misinformation on public attitudes and behaviour and emphasises the need for credible sources of information to combat the spread of misinformation.

Looking deeper into the issue of information disorder in climate-smart agriculture, Chowdhury, Kabir, Abdulai and Alam (2023) reviewed the issue of information disorder on social media with the aim of developing an analytical framework to address misinformation in the agri-food sector. They assert that the agri-food sector has been facing growing controversies related to climate change, animal welfare, the environment, technological innovations in agriculture, as well as the challenges associated with digitising food chains. These issues, according to them, provide avenues for polarising views that may extend into online communities, where information

exchange is less regulated. Chowdhury *et al.* (2023:13) further noted that despite extensive research on health, politics, and media and communication, limited attention to misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation related to agriculture has left critical gaps in the literature. Consequently, they proposed a comprehensive framework for understanding and evaluating agricultural misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation within social and online media communities. This framework encompasses the characterization of mis-, dis-, and malinformation, identification of sources, mechanisms of diffusion, impacts on stakeholders, detection strategies, and approaches for mitigation and countermeasures

Figure 3. A holistic framework for research and understanding agricultural mis-dis-mal-information (Chowdhury *et.al* 2023:16)

Specifically, the framework breaks down mis-dis-mal-information into several key dimensions, including characterization, sources, diffusion patterns, impacts, detection and correction. As the

authors highlight, applying this framework to complex and contested agricultural issues like climate-smart agriculture can provide crucial insights into how false and misleading narratives originate and propagate, how they influence farmer decisions, and how to counter them effectively. This aligns accurately with our objectives of finding out the knowledge of information disorder among farmers, the source, the influence and how farmers fact-check climate-smart agricultural information in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Moreover, Abugri, Brandner, Atsu, Kabuya, Mvubu and Waleling (2022) reviewed various types of misinformation in agriculture, including false reports about climate change, pesticide usage, fertiliser use, food safety, and agro-processing. The authors note that fake news and misinformation can be deliberately created or the result of an error, mistake, or misinterpretation. The authors note that misinformation can lead to fear, anxiety, and panic among farmers and the general public, which can have negative impacts on the uptake of climate-smart agriculture techniques. Furthermore, Abugri *et al.* (2022) noted that the prevalence of misinformation is often fueled by factors such as a lack of deliberation, where individuals may not invest the time and mental effort to scrutinise the accuracy of the news they encounter.

They continued that individuals tend to be less inclined to trust false information when they have the opportunity to deliberate over the accuracy of different news headlines. Additionally, repeated exposure plays a significant role, as individuals tend to be more inclined to accept a false statement as true the more they encounter it, possibly due to the familiarity of the information. The novelty of false news, often more attention-grabbing and emotionally charged than true news, further contributes to its spread. False information, eliciting emotions like fear, disgust, and surprise, captures our attention, creating the impression of updating our knowledge

and fostering its dissemination (Johar & Roggeveen, 2007; Ahmed & Rasul, 2022; Bryanov & Vziatysheva, 2021; Pillai & Fazio, 2021; Fazio, 2020).

2.2.6 Sources of Climate Smart Agriculture Information Disorder

Agricultural information serves as a linchpin in the reception and application of climate-smart practices, particularly in the context of Nigeria's diverse agricultural landscape. The dissemination of climate-smart agricultural information is fundamental to ensuring farmers have the knowledge and strategies that foster resilience in the face of climate change impacts. The sources of agricultural information in Nigeria are diverse and encompass various channels. These sources play a crucial role in disseminating information to farmers, thereby contributing to the development of the agricultural sector in Nigeria. The study by Fidelugwuowo (2020) revealed that the Ministry of Agriculture, friends and neighbours, radio and television were identified as major sources of agricultural information for rural farmers in South-East Nigeria. Additionally, the study by Bashir, Adam, Abubakar, Faruk, Garuba, and Francis (2021) examined the role of the National Farmers Helpline in disseminating agricultural information among crop farmers in Nigeria. They noted that the National Farmers Help was established to enhance productivity and promote sustainable agricultural development throughout the six geo-political zones. This utilises information and communications technology (ICT) to support the delivery of timely and impactful agricultural extension services to farmer.

Studies have shown that a significant number of farmers get agricultural information through conventional media, especially the radio. For instance, a study by Mtega and Msungu (2013) conducted in Nigeria and Tanzania indicated that the dependence on radio is primarily due to the wide coverage of radio frequencies, the availability of numerous radio stations, and the portable

nature of most radios. Similarly, a study by Sule *et al.* (2021) highlighted that the use of radio as a source of agricultural information was one of the most popular among farmers in Nigeria. Furthermore, the study by Opara (2008) revealed that 63.2 percent of farmers indicated radio as their source of agricultural information in Imo State, Nigeria. Additionally, Ani and Baba (2010) found that radio was the most utilised electronic mass media by respondents in Northern Taraba State, Nigeria, for accessing agricultural information. Additionally, a study by Akwiwu and Patrick (2020) revealed that the majority of respondents accessed agricultural information through radio in Imo State, Nigeria.

One study on climate-smart agriculture that emphasised the importance of farmers getting information from trusted sources like fellow farmers, extension agents, and researchers is that of Alarima, Aromolaran, Fapojuwo, Ayinde, Masunaga, and Wakatsuki (2020). They averred that information channels and sources play a key role in the dissemination and adoption of agricultural technologies and practices among farmers. Their study found that interpersonal contacts were critical for spreading information and affecting the uptake of climate-smart farming practices techniques. Direct information sources like fellow farmers, extension agents, researchers and farmers' associations were utilised by over 75% of respondents and proved more influential than mass media. This study highlights that credibility and trust in information sources matter for adoption and suggests that if questionable sources spread misinformation, it may still influence farmers' perceptions or practices.

Social media platforms have enabled the rapid spread of misinformation and disinformation about a variety of topics, including agriculture and climate change (Vosoughi *et al.*, 2018). The spread of misinformation on social media has been shown to be more prominent than in traditional news outlets, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic (Barr, Cotter, O'Hear,

Gray, Chesser, Atchely, and Tenhundfeld, 2022). While there is a significant body of research on misinformation on social media, particularly against the backdrop of the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a scarcity of studies specifically addressing the convergence of social media platforms, information disorder, and climate-smart agriculture in Nigeria. During the COVID-19 pandemic, social media became a major vector for spreading false and misleading claims about the virus, public health measures, and vaccines (Brennen *et al.*, 2020; Ahmed and Rasul, 2022).

Consequently, studies have found that several factors make social media prone to spreading misinformation about agriculture and climate change. These include echo chambers, the proliferation of fake news and misinformation, lack of gatekeepers, social bots and coordinated disinformation campaigns. Social media algorithms can create echo chambers where users only see content that confirms their existing views (Vicario *et al.*, 2016). Farrell 2019, cited in Ejaz *et al.* (2022), noted that the situation concerning misinformation has been worsened. He added that the advent and widespread adoption of social media have introduced fake news and misinformation as significant challenges for media systems, particularly in developing countries, in their reporting on climate change. Also, the lack of gatekeepers on social media allows misinformation to proliferate rapidly without fact-checking or editorial oversight (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017). More so, social bots and coordinated disinformation campaigns can manipulate narratives on social platforms (Lazer *et al.*, 2018).

Specifically for climate change, social media has enabled the spread of conspiracy theories, denial of scientific consensus, and promotion of climate pseudoscience (Williams, McMurray, Kurz and Lambert 2015). Groups opposed to climate action have successfully used social platforms to cast doubt on climate science and delay policy responses (Faris, Roberts, Etling, Bourassa, Zuckerman, and Benkler, 2017). Similarly, social media has spread misinformation

about key agricultural issues like GMOs, pesticides, and organic farming. Anti-GMO activists have used social media to stoke fears about genetic engineering despite the scientific consensus on GMO safety. Pesticide and herbicide misinformation is common on social platforms, distorting risk perceptions (Egamberdieva and Adesemoye, 2016; Apri, Irham, Jamhari, and Suryantini, 2022; Rahman *et al.*, 2021).

Treen *et al.* (2020) conducted an extensive study into online misinformation of climate change. They noted that several features of social media networks contribute to the spread of climate change misinformation. These include

1. Homophily - the natural tendency for individuals to form relationships with like-minded people,
2. Echo chambers - environments in which individuals encounter only information that confirms their preexisting beliefs,
3. Polarization - where people become more extreme in their views over time.

Additionally, according to them, the tendency of social algorithms to favor popular content, which promotes content based on engagement rather than trustworthiness, can also contribute to the spread of misinformation. They opine that the ease of spreading misinformation on social media, combined with the rapid pace of information sharing, can make it difficult to correct false information once it has been disseminated.

Moreover, according to Treen *et al.* (2020), belief systems, social norms, and psychological heuristics such as confirmation bias contribute to the spread of misinformation about climate change in several ways. Users tend to consume information that aligns with their existing belief systems, which can lead to the reinforcement and spread of misinformation. Additionally, social

norms play a significant role in influencing the acceptance of misinformation, as people tend to trust information received from individuals within their social network. Confirmation bias further exacerbates this issue, as individuals tend to seek out and prioritise information that confirms their preexisting beliefs, leading to the perpetuation of misinformation within online social networks (Treen *et al.*, 2020).

Consequently, it can be safely inferred that the advent of social media introduces dual dynamic positions. While positively providing a platform for rapid information dissemination, it has also become a breeding ground for misinformation and disinformation, encompassing key agricultural issues like GMOs, organic agriculture, agrochemicals, water use and pesticides. This is one of the issues that this study intends to shed light on: to find out the sources of information disorder in climate-smart agriculture in Oyo State, Nigeria.

2.2.7 The rise of information disorder

"The world is flat" as described in the book by Thomas Friedman, where he emphasized the emergence of a globalized marketplace where individuals, companies, and nations can seamlessly collaborate, compete, and innovate across borders and time zones, enabled by the internet, digitization, and advancements in technologies that have made the transfer of information, capital, and labor more efficient and widespread. Consequently, the phenomenon of information disorder which encompasses misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation—has emerged as a force shaping communication and discourse in a different direction across various areas of our live. Wardle and Dais's (2017) definition of the phenomenon has been widely adopted and referenced in academic literature, government reports, and media coverage related to the study and understanding of information disorder. According to Wardle (2017),

misinformation is information that is false, but not intended to cause harm, disinformation is information that is false and deliberately created to cause harm. While malinformation refers to information that is based on reality, used to inflict harm on a person, organization or country.

Information disorder is spreading like wild fire, through the internet especially the social media platforms, and even traditional media outlets, propagating false or misleading information fueled by human susceptibility, technological amplification and actors with vested interests (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2017; Fallis, 2015; Lewandowsky *et al.*, 2020). The origin of information disorder can be traced back to the early development of the internet and the rapid dissemination of information through digital platforms. The proliferation of social media and online news sources has contributed to the spread of false or misleading information (Guarino, Pierri, Di Giovanni and Celestini, 2021).

Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic brought the issue of information disorder to the forefront. The pandemic came along with issues of information distortion termed “infodemic,” with social media often flooded with false or misleading information linking the medical crisis to widely circulated disinformation topics. This phenomenon, acknowledged by the World Health Organisation, was depicted as ‘a deluge of ambiguous, inconsistent, and sometimes inaccurate narratives flooding various media channels, leaving the public confused and overwhelmed’ (Olatunji, Ayandele, Ashirudeen and Olaniru, 2020). During the pandemic in Nigeria, there were claims from different quarters that most of which are unverified. This includes information that COVID-19 was a hoax or a biological weapon created by specific countries or organizations. There was also conspiracy theories suggesting that the virus was linked to 5G technology or was a ploy by pharmaceutical companies to make money. This proliferation of misinformation

contributed to widespread public confusion, skepticism toward health measures, and failure to comply with measures such as vaccination campaigns and mask-wearing protocols.

While information disorder has resonated across sectors like public health and politics, one area where its impact is particularly concerning is in the area of climate change communication. Despite the scientific consensus and urgency surrounding this existential threat, a lot of misinformation and disinformation about the science, causes, and potential solutions has undermined efforts to achieve accurate public understanding and informed decision-making (Cook *et al.*, 2018; Stroud, 2019).

2.2.8 Climate Change and Adoption of Climate-Smart Agriculture

The topic of climate change is not a new phenomenon. Since the discovery and warnings about the depletion of the ozone layer, our lives have been transformed as we struggle with its consequences. The realization that human activities were contributing to the depletion of the ozone layer, which protects us from harmful ultraviolet radiation, was a turning point in our understanding of how fragile our planet's ecosystem is. In the decades that followed, scientists, policymakers, and environmentalists have worked tirelessly to develop adaptation and mitigation strategies to address the looming threat of climate change. From international agreements to reduce greenhouse gas emissions to local initiatives promoting sustainable practices, the world has united in its efforts to mitigate the impact of human activities on the environment.

The official United Nations definition of climate change identified the phenomenon as a long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns. Such shifts can be natural, due to changes in the sun's activity or large volcanic eruptions (United Nations, n.d.). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) also defines climate change as “a change in the state of the climate that

can be identified by changes in the mean and the variability of its properties, and that persists for an extended period, typically decades or longer.” Kompas, Pham, and Che (2018) opine that short-term natural disasters like landslides, tidal waves, and storms, as well as long-term, more gradual environmental destruction, are two ways that climate change is having a negative impact on the world. Many areas of our lives, such as water resources, human health, human settlements and migratory patterns, agriculture and food security, biodiversity and ecosystems, energy, industry and transportation have been feeling the negative effects of these occurrences (Stanley *et al.* 2021).

Recent climate change events in Nigeria have been characterised by a series of extreme weather issues and changes in agricultural practices. Noticeable climate events include increased rainfall intensity, prolonged dry seasons, frequent floods, rising temperatures, severe windstorms, unpredictable rainfall patterns and distribution, late-onset rain, and early cessation of rain (Onyeneke, Amadi, Njoku and Osuji, 2021). These events had a significant impact on agricultural production and food security, particularly in rain-fed agricultural areas, exposing the public to climatic fluctuations. The effects of extreme events, including floods and droughts, caused by climate change on agriculture and food security have been a cause for concern, with implications for sustainable agricultural production and rural livelihoods (Durodola, 2019). Ifeanyi-obi, Etuk and Jike-Wai (2012) had opined that agriculture, a vital component of Nigeria's economy, is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change due to the country's reliance on rain-fed agriculture and other socioeconomic factors such as poverty, inequitable land distribution, and poor infrastructure.

Consequently, the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices emerged as a crucial approach to address the challenges posed by climate change, especially in the agricultural sector in Nigeria

(Tiamiyu *et al.*, 2018; Lipper *et al.*, 2014). These practices encompass a range of environmentally sensitive agricultural technologies aimed at enhancing sustainable and improved agricultural productivity (Bello *et al.*, 2012). The Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) of the United Nations pioneered CSA as an approach for strengthening food system sustainability by increasing productivity and incomes. FAO (2013) defines CSA as agriculture that sustainably increases productivity, enhances resilience, reduces greenhouse gases, and enhances the achievement of national food security and development goals. This includes the adoption and planting of stress-tolerant seed varieties, efficient water management, diversified cropping, integrated pest management, and conservation agriculture.

Climate-smart agriculture (CSA) has gained significant attention in Nigeria, particularly in the south-west and northern parts of the country (Oyawole, Dipeolu, Shittu, Obayelu and Fabunmi, 2020; Chukwuone and Amaechina, 2021). Studies have focused on the perception and uptake of climate-smart agriculture practices, the effect of these practices on food security, and the adoption level of climate-smart agricultural practices among smallholder farmers in Nigeria (Chukwuone and Amaechina, 2021; Oyawole *et al.*, 2020; Adeagbo, Ojo and Adetoro, 2021), and the findings have shown that the adoption rate is increasing.

Furthermore, the role of communication and education in stimulating public awareness and promoting climate change adaptation has been emphasised as a crucial aspect of addressing the challenges posed by climate change in Nigeria (Azu & Alakwe, 2023; Abdullahi, 2020). Goyol and Pathirage (2018) averred that taking action to embrace environmentally friendly activities starts with awareness and a higher understanding of the issues. Thus, it is clear that raising public education and awareness of climate change-related concerns is crucial to efforts to slow down and even reverse climate change.

However, while the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices holds promise for mitigating the impacts of climate change on the agricultural sector, it is imperative to recognise the challenges posed by the proliferation of fake news, misinformation and disinformation in climate change discourse, also known as information disorder.

2.2.9 Information disorder, climate change and Agriculture in Nigeria

The issue of information disorder is especially problematic in the context of agriculture, a sector deeply linked with climate change. As the world struggles with the effects of a changing climate in the agri-food sector (the recent heat-wave experienced in Nigeria is an example), the spread of misinformation and disinformation about agricultural practices, technologies, and adaptation strategies has become a pressing concern (Chowdhury *et al.*, 2024). Inaccurate information can negatively influence farmers' reasoning and decision-making processes, which will as a result prevent the adoption of sustainable and climate-smart agricultural practices (Stroud, 2019; Lewandowsky *et al.*, 2012). For instance, the introduction of genetically modified (GM) crops in Africa, including Nigeria, is a climate-smart agricultural initiative, but has been met with controversies fueled by misinformation. This Misinformation affects public perception and reception of policies on climate-smart agricultural practices. Some messages, news reports, and videos circulating recently have portrayed GM seeds as a new form of colonialism, asserting that these patented seeds cannot be replanted by farmers after the first harvest, except through the originators.

Despite the documented advantages of genetically modified organisms, including higher crop yields and lower pesticide requirements, various myths and misconceptions persist. Another common misconception is that GMO crops are inherently unsafe for human consumption and

harmful to the environment. However, extensive studies and regulatory reviews have consistently shown that approved GMOs are safe. For instance, major scientific organizations, including the World Health Organization (WHO), the American Medical Association (AMA), and the National Academy of Sciences (NAS), have found that genetically modified foods are safe for human consumption and do not pose unique health risks (WHO, 2020) currently on the market are no more risky to human health than conventional foods. More so, Nigeria's National Biosafety Management Agency ensures that all GMOs undergo rigorous safety assessments before approval. The agency has cleared GMO crops like insect-resistant cowpea and drought-tolerant TELA maize, which have been shown to improve yields and reduce the need for pesticides (Eludunni, 2021).

In Nigeria, where agriculture accounts for about 23% of the nation's GDP and is crucial for food security (Sasu, 2023), the implications of information disorder in this sector are particularly severe. The country is already grappling with the impacts of climate change on agricultural productivity, such as increased rainfall intensity, prolonged dry seasons, and unpredictable weather patterns (Onyeneke *et al.*, 2021). Access to accurate and reliable information is paramount for farmers to adapt and mitigate these effects. However, the erosion of institutional support and the proliferation of unverified online sources have left many farmers vulnerable to being misled by misinformation and disinformation (Stroud, 2019; Nwakpu *et al.*, 2020).

Despite the urgency of this issue, research specifically examining information disorder in the context of climate change communication and agriculture in Nigeria remains scarce (Lewandowsky *et al.*, 2020; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2023). Although, several studies have examined information disorder and misinformation in Nigeria, majority have focused on the political and public health sectors. In the political sector, researchers have investigated user motivations for

sharing fake news during the COVID-19 pandemic (Apuke & Omar, 2021), the interplay of social media, misinformation, and age inequalities in online political engagement (Ahmed, Madrid-Morales & Tully, 2023), strategies for combatting disinformation ahead of the 2023 general elections (Jamiu, Adesina, Odunlami & Bello, 2022), as well as the dissemination of disinformation more broadly on political and electoral processes in Nigeria (Hassan, 2023). Also, Samuel, (2021) looked into Fact-Checking as a Solution to Political Disinformation in Nigeria. In the health sector, researchers have looked at information literacy as a means to curtail COVID-19 misinformation among university students (Igbinovia, Okuonghae, & Adebayo, 2021). Others have also investigated fake news, misinformation, and health communication gaps surrounding the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria (Omosotomhe & Olley, 2023). Oloruntobi (2023) examines religion as channel of disinformation/misinformation in relation to hesitation in acceptance of COVID-19 vaccine Nigeria. It is apparent that the existence of information disorder in major sectors of our life has been identified in studies and cannot be overlooked. While this knowledge gap represents a significant obstacle to understanding and mitigating the detrimental effects of inaccurate or misleading information encountered by farmers, hindering efforts to facilitate agricultural progress and climate change adaptation it is more important and expedient to examine its influence especially looking into the role of communication in our society and how agriculture has served as a driving force for economic development and food security in Nigeria

From a communication and media studies perspective, understanding the dynamics of information disorder in this context is very important. Some questions begging for answers include: How are false or misleading messages about climate-smart agriculture being created, disseminated, and consumed through various communication channels? What roles do different

actors – from social media platforms to traditional media outlets, and from malicious actors to well-intentioned but misinformed individuals – play in propagating information disorder? How does this phenomenon shape public discourse, attitudes, and decision-making processes related to climate change adaptation in the agricultural sector?

A clear line should be drawn between information and communication in this context. A lot of information are being churned out from agricultural ministries, agricultural extension officer, mass media and digital media. Focus have so much been on dissemination of information but not much attention is dedicated to communication. (Akwiwu & Patrick, 2020; Choudhary & Khan, 2017). In this context, we refer to the fact that information is the art of disseminating messages to a target audience by getting feedback from the process. However, little attention is focused on the communication aspect; the feedback from the receiver which makes a communication process complete and this gives the opportunity to the sender to review, analyse the presence of noise from the feedback of the receiver and look into ways of repackaging the information so that it will generate the intended feedback. In the study of information disorder, it is crucial to differentiate between information and communication. Information refers to processed and structured data that conveys meaning, while communication involves the exchange of this information (Wang *et al.*, 2008). Information disorder, a significant challenge in today's digital age, goes beyond discerning truth from falsehood to also emphasize the importance of information quality (Omoregie, 2021). It is not enough for information to be factually correct; it must also be contextually relevant, comprehensive in its coverage, up-to-date, and devoid of bias or distortion. Poor information quality can lead to misinformation, where accurate information is presented in a misleading manner, or disinformation, where false information is deliberately spread to deceive.

Addressing these issues require a focused examination of information disorder as a communication phenomenon, drawing insights from theoretical frameworks such as the Shannon and Weaver model of communication (1948). This seminal model conceptualizes communication as a linear process involving a source, message, channel, receiver, and noise – a framework that can be applied to analyze how "information disorder" acts as noise, distorting the credibility of climate-smart agricultural messages transmitted through various media channels and decoded by farmers (the receivers). Through this lens, fact-checking mechanisms, investigations, and media literacy efforts can be understood as attempts to detect and reduce the noise interfering with accurate communication.

2.2.10 Influence of Information Disorder on Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

In recent years, research across the cognitive sciences has demonstrated that exposure to information disorder does not just lead to inaccuracies in an individual's knowledge but can also negatively impact subsequent memory, reasoning, and decision-making even after the information is corrected or retracted. The misinformation effect, a phenomenon explored by Loftus (2005), demonstrates how exposure to inaccurate information can impair and alter memory. In his seminal study, participants who were exposed to misinformation about an observed event later exhibited reduced memory accuracy for the original details, incorporating the false information into their recollections. In essence, participants who were exposed to misinformation about an observed event tend to incorporate the false information into their recollections, leading to reduced accuracy in remembering the original details of the event. Therefore, external information, even if it is incorrect, has the potential to shape and alter our memories. In agreement with Loftus's work, the study by Karanian, Rabb, Wulff, Torrance,

Thomas, and Race (2020:1) also maintained that exposure to subtle forms of misleading information can significantly alter memory for past events, leading to memory distortion due to misinformation.

Additionally, beyond the memory effect, reasoning and decision-making processes are also susceptible to being influenced by information disorder, even after it has been discredited. A meta-analysis by Ecker, Lewandowsky, Cheung, and Maybery (2015) found that retracting misinformation did not fully eliminate its distorting effects on reasoning, as participants still showed reliance on misinformation in inferential tasks. This implies that even when misinformation has been corrected, it still has a lingering impact on people's reasoning abilities. These impacts stem from the insufficient updating of mental models after a retraction (Ecker *et al.*, 2022). These mental models refer to cognitive representations or frameworks that individuals use to understand, interpret, and navigate the world around them. Furthermore, Brydges, Gordon and Ecker (2020) demonstrated a continued influence effect on decision-making, with participants remaining influenced by retracted misinformation when making complex judgments. This shows the lasting effects of information disorder on the recipient.

Moreover, emerging research has begun applying these cognitive science insights to agricultural practices. Fuhrmann, Wan, Blouzard, Veludo, Holtman, Chetty-Mhlanga, and Rother (2021) found that outdated information constituted misinformation that led to hazardous pesticide use among North Carolina farmworkers, revealing the long-lasting effect of information disorder. In Zambia, reliance on misinformed social networks for agricultural advice was linked to suboptimal adoption of drought-mitigating strategies, though access to extension services helped counteract this effect (Gupta, Ponticelli, and Tesei, 2019). Masambuka-Kanchewa, Rumble and Buck (2021) argue that the availability of conflicting agricultural information from various

sources puts consumers at risk of being misinformed, thereby shaping their perceptions and decisions around agricultural technologies.

As climate-smart agriculture (CSA) aims to sustainably increase agricultural productivity and incomes, adapt to climate change, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions (FAO, 2022), the spread of misinformation and disinformation threatens evidence-based decision-making in climate-smart agricultural practices and policies the world over. According to Cook *et al.* (2016), one of the primary influences of information disorder on CSA practices is that it undermines public understanding and trust in climate science, despite 97% of climate scientists agreeing on human-caused climate change (Cook *et al.*, 2016).

In their study on neutralizing misinformation through inoculation, Cook, Lewandowsky and Ecker (2017:1) noted the following as influences of misinformation on climate change:

1. Decreased acknowledgment of climate change as a real phenomenon.
2. Lower levels of support for climate change mitigation policies.
3. Polarizing impacts, whereby individuals favoring free-market ideologies become less likely to accept anthropogenic global warming (AGW), while those with less emphasis on free-market principles show increased acceptance.
4. Uncertainty regarding the scientific consensus on climate change.
5. Negative consequences for public understanding and perception of climate change issues.

Furthermore, climate science disinformation campaigns by fossil fuel corporations have contributed to this disconnect (Supran and Oreskes, 2021). When the public distrusts climate science, support for climate policies and CSA funding suffers (Campbell and Kay, 2014). For instance, U.S. farmers are less likely to adopt CSA practices if they believe natural climate

cycles rather than greenhouse gases cause climate change (Arbuckle *et al.*, 2013). Misinformation also breeds polarisation and tribalism, making evidence-based CSA policymaking challenging (Lewandowsky & Van der Linden, 2021).

Elucidating further on this, Stroud's (2019) work sheds light on the influence of information disorder and emphasises the importance of addressing misinformation in agricultural practices. Firstly, agreeing with Loftus (2005), Thomas and Race (2020), he noted that misinformation has been shown to impact memory, reasoning, and decision-making, even after correction. (Stroud, 2019: 18). Secondly, the erosion of confidence in agricultural research and farmers' capacity to make well-informed choices is a critical influence of misinformation. False claims of connections between research organizations and the pesticide industry serve as the basis for conspiracy theories. This erosion of trust jeopardises participatory soil science, which relies on a foundation of trust between scientist-farming communities (Stroud, 2019).

Furthermore, the spread of misinformation about biotechnologies can hinder important research and development in the agricultural field, ultimately impacting the ability of farmers to effectively adapt to and mitigate the effects of climate change. (Kwena *et al.*, 2018; Ojoko, Akinwunmi, Yusuf, and Oni, 2017). Studies have also found that the influence of information disorder on climate-smart agriculture is promoting unscientific views on agricultural biotechnologies. GMOs (genetically modified organisms) and gene editing have helped develop drought-resistant, higher-yielding crops and livestock for climate adaptation.

This has consequently led to increased food security and sustainability in agriculture, as well as a reduction in the use of harmful pesticides. However, misinformation about GMOs has led to a reluctance to adopt new and innovative technologies that could significantly improve agricultural

productivity and sustainability. As recorded in Nigeria, biotechnology misinformation has proliferated the agricultural sector information ecosystem, like claims linking GMOs to health issues or infertility. For example, cowpea is a drought-tolerant staple crop in northern Nigeria, but pest-resistant cowpeas have faced opposition from issues relating to misinformation despite the productivity benefits of this cowpea trait. Additionally, glyphosate is a broad-spectrum herbicide used by farmers to control weeds in various crops in Nigeria. However, its use has been a subject of debate and controversy due to concerns about its environmental impact and potential health risks, as there are unfounded claims about its links to cancer, which further compounds challenges in adopting sustainable practices in climate-smart agriculture. (Egamberdieva and Adesemoye, 2016; Kwena *et al.*, 2018; Liverpool-Tasie *et al.*, 2022; Ojoko *et al.*, 2017).

Misinformation about climate-smart agriculture (CSA) also leads to unfounded fears and slow adoption, such as the misconception that agroforestry increases pest risk in Africa. False claims linking CSA techniques to lower yields also hinder farmer adoption, especially among smallholder farmers with limited institutional access. (Giller, Andersson, Corbeels, Kirkegaard, Mortensen, Erenstein, and Vanlauwe, 2015).

2.2.11 Fact Checking: A Communication Tool for Combating Information Disorder

Fact-checking is a crucial process in journalism and media literacy aimed at verifying the accuracy and truthfulness of information, particularly in the context of news and public discourse. It involves the systematic examination of claims, statements, or information to determine their factual accuracy and correctness. Fact-checking has gained prominence in response to the proliferation of misinformation, disinformation, and fake news in the digital age,

where the veracity of information is often challenged. (Wasserman, 2018; Jiang, 2022; Ha *et al.*, 2019; Arrese and Pérez-Latre, 2017).

Misinformation and disinformation on climate change has become a significant issue, weakening scientific consensus and polarising climate change debates. The spread of climate falsehoods, conspiracy theories, and doctored narratives has been turbocharged by social media, and in many cases, used by vested interests to slow down action and regulation. This requires intensive fact-checking to confirm assertions, dispel misrepresentations, and contextualize the issues of climate science (Farooq *et al.*, 2022; Ofoegbu and New, 2022; Ojoko *et al.*, 2017).

Considering the journalistic approach to fact-checking, Nieminen and Sankari (2021) describe fact-checking as a procedure to assess the veracity of the statements made in the public domain with the aim of finding out and reporting whether a claim is true or false by relying on different sources of information. According to this, Ejaz *et al.* (2022) describe fact-checking as a procedure whereby journalists rely on various databases and automated tools to verify the accuracy of any news or claims. Despite the opposing opinions, Ejaz *et al.* (2022) reported that some journalists do not use fact-checking tools due to the feeling that fact-checkers are biased or funded by foreign NGOs, and the fact that fact-checking tools are often funded by various interest groups with their own interests.

The issue of fake news has been in the spotlight of the public discourse in the wake of the 2016 presidential election in the United States. Researchers have been focusing more and more on the study of the methods of reducing the spread of fake news and misinformation. The fast spread of misinformation, especially on controversial topics, has prompted journalists to use fact-checking as a tool to combat false narratives in many countries (Lyons, 2017; cited in Ejaz *et al.*, 2022).

Porter and Wood (2021) carried out a study in Argentina, Nigeria, South Africa, and the United Kingdom to examine how long the effects of fact-checking last in the reduction of belief in misinformation. Their study, which is applicable to the Nigerian setting, where the proliferation of misinformation, particularly via social media, has been a point of concern, concluded that fact-checking interventions resulted in a lasting decrease in the belief in misinformation in all four countries included in the study, including Nigeria. We agree with this statement because fact-checking false claims will be a significant approach to the fight against the proliferation of misinformation in Nigeria. Fact-checking of agricultural information, particularly climate change, by farmers has been reported as essential to informed decision-making and adaptation to the changing climate (Adeagbo *et al.*, 2021; Muema *et al.*, 2018; Akinwalere, 2021; Kumar & Reddy, 2021; Samuel *et al.*, 2018).

Access to climate information that is reliable and easy to understand is critical to effective adaptation to climate change by farmers (Muema *et al.*, 2018). Research has indicated that weather information access is essential in enhancing farmer's perception of climate change, which enhances the likelihood of adaptation strategy adoption (Adeagbo *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, better-informed adaptation decisions are made by farmers with improved access to climate change information (Kumar & Reddy, 2021). This highlights the significance of credible and trusted climate information to be used by farmers in adapting to climate change (Muema *et al.*, 2018). Also, sources of information play a vital role in providing smallholder farmers with knowledge on how to respond to climate change appropriately (Mwalukasa, 2013). It has also been shown that climate change information helps in climate change awareness and adaptation by farmers (Samuel *et al.*, 2018). In addition, access to information on climate change also

affects the adoption of different climate change adaptive strategies positively and significantly among farmers (Tshikororo *et al.*, 2020).

As mentioned above, research shows that farmers use various sources of climate and agricultural information, such as government, extension agents, radio, NGOs, social networks, and personal observation (Fidelugwuowo, 2020; Adam *et al.*, 2021; Alarima, 2020; Muema *et al.*, 2018). It is notable that the degree of trust in an information source determines the probability of farmers fact-checking the accuracy of the information, whereby, trusted sources are less checked. Nevertheless, the excessive use of trusted channels is associated with the danger of believing inaccurate information (Porter and Wood, 2021; Singer 2023).

To successfully adapt to climate change and make informed decisions, farmers should have access to reliable and accurate climate-smart information (Ayalew *et al.*, 2023). Cross-checking of information and recommendations across information sources is one of the primary methods identified in the studies through which farmers assess and validate climate-smart information (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). For instance, a farmer can be given planting tips by an agricultural extension officer which contradicts the information being used by a neighbour farmer. Or a radio forecast of rainfall in the season may not be in line with their rainfall records.

In these situations, the farmers tend to use a conscious approach of cross-checking information across sources to verify consistency and accuracy (Muema *et al.*, 2018). They can talk to a number of extension agents, consult many peer farmers and compare agricultural radio advice with indigenous knowledge. This triangulation of sources enables farmers to find out corroboration and contradiction between statements and climate data (Kiptot *et al.*, 2006). This implies that agricultural organisations can facilitate this mechanism by making sure that farmers

can access various credible sources of information instead of relying on few extensions. Further encouragement of discussion groups and sharing of experience will contribute to comparative fact-checking.

Besides the use of expert sources, farmers also use their local social networks and indigenous knowledge systems to collectively assess and verify climate-smart information. In the farmer groups, they exchange information about what is working in terms of agricultural practices or varieties in the local conditions. They talk about the observed climate effects and comment on the validity of seasonal forecasts (Adeagbo *et al.*, 2021). According to Chen (2015), peer-to-peer interactions and organisational collaborations are crucial in the process of sharing climate information with farmers. Nevertheless, the research conducted by Chen implies that the efficiency of such interactions can be constrained by the level of knowledge of the core user and the platform design. According to Ofoegbu (2021), the author points out that there is a necessity to share climate information with multiple stakeholders, such as local farmers, in order to promote the adoption of adaptation practices. He also added that the exchange of climate information with farmers is affected by the partnerships between governmental organisations and non-governmental organisations, which means that the organisational partnerships are important in this regard.

This peer-to-peer sharing enables questioning and measuring the consistency of information on the basis of the lived experience of peers. As an example, when several farmers report a crop variety to have failed even when extensions have recommended it, there are doubts cast on the claims. By means of such discussions in communities, climate information can be cross-checked with local realities. In addition, indigenous knowledge that was built over generations regarding land, rainfall indicators, planting practices, etc. offers another yardstick to evaluate the relevance

of climate-smart recommendations. Information that is highly against community experience and norms is strictly questioned. This combination of peer-to-peer exchange and indigenous evaluation systems gives farmers a social mechanism of participatory fact-checking based on local contexts (Muema *et al.*, 2018).

According to some studies, farmers are fact-checking climate data mainly based on personal observation, social networks, and community knowledge, as opposed to official fact-checking (Adeagbo *et al.*, 2021). This underlines the importance of ground-truthing data by experience. Adetayo, Abata-Ebire, and Oladipo (2023) conducted a recent study on climate change information sources and fact-checking behaviours among students at Adeleke University in Nigeria. The study sampled 688 students to find out their source of information on climate change and whether they fact-checked it. They discovered that students tended to check the correctness of climate change information they came across on social media, mainstream media, friends, and religious institutions. They concluded that fact-checking skills, particularly related to informal sources such as social media, should be encouraged to enhance climate change knowledge in students.

More recently, Aina (2023) has analyzed the fact-checking activities of three large Nigerian websites (Dubawa, Africa Check, and Fact Check Hub) in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. The purpose was to evaluate the frequency of the posts that disproved misinformation and offered misinformation literacy training published on these sites. The findings indicated that 76 percent of the posts included debunkings of false claims by labelling them as true or false and giving corrected information (Aina, 2023). This is in line with the previous studies that indicate that the primary goal of fact-checking is to confirm claims and refute misinformation (Ireton & Posetti, 2018). Nevertheless, Aina (2023) also discovered a very

high percentage (98.6%) had literacy elements that informed the readers on how to find credible sources, how to detect misleading claims, and how to enhance media literacy. Aina (2023) found that the significant Nigerian fact-checking organisations are not only trying to dispel false statements but also to increase the misinformation literacy of their readers. The paper recommends the extension of the literacy education of these organisations to counter misinformation in general by collaborating with education systems.

Studies have presented evidence that fact-checking can be effective in reducing misinformation belief. Porter and Wood (2021) asserted that fact-checks led to a 0.59-point increase in factual accuracy on a 5-point scale, whereas exposure to misinformation without a fact-check led to an increase in belief in that misinformation of less than 0.07 points on the same scale. This implies that fact-checking may be a useful weapon against misinformation. The study by Porter and Wood (2021) also observed that fact-checking could be especially useful in correcting easy issues but less useful in correcting more complex or strongly held beliefs.

Fact-checking has also been used with the term debunking. It is one of the significant elements of the fight against the dissemination of fake news, especially in the case of mass health emergencies like the COVID-19 pandemic. Some studies have shown the need to dispel misinformation and present the truth to curb the proliferation of false claims (Gabarron *et al.*, 2021; Berkowitz and Vann, 2023; Steffens *et al.*, 2021; Chan *et al.*, 2017). Health professionals and public health authorities have been said to be crucial in revealing misinformation and giving accurate information to the people (Gabarron *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, studies have shown that debunking can have major implications in the fight against misinformation, whereby large effects have been found in the presentation of misinformation, debunking, and the maintenance of misinformation despite debunking (Chan *et al.*, 2017). It should be mentioned, however, that

debunking might not be enough, and other methods besides debunking might be required to help deal with misinformation (Bavel *et al.*, 2020).

In their article, Evidence-based Automatic fact-checking for Climate Change Misinformation, Wang, Chillrud and McKeown (2021) discovered that, misinformation on climate change is rapidly and widely distributed on the internet, therefore, it is not easy to verify the accuracy of the information by human fact-checkers. They added that a number of fact-checking programmes have been created to manually verify climate change-related statements and mark them as wrong or misleading. Manual fact-checking, is time-consuming and unsuitable to combat the increasing amount of disinformation on the internet. Thus, automated fact-checking is used in addition to human-driven fact-checking. Wang *et al.* (2021) proposed some of the methods that may be helpful in the field of climate-smart agriculture in the verification of claims.

1. Manual Fact-Checking: - This is a process where human experts manually check the truthfulness of the claims by carrying out comprehensive research, analyzing evidence, and cross-checking information with other reputable sources.

2. Automated Fact-Checking: - Automatically checks the accuracy of claims by using algorithms and natural language processing to analyze textual information, detect misinformation trends, and compare claims with factual databases.

3. Semantic Analysis: - Concentrates on the meaning and context of statements to evaluate their correctness, commonly through natural language processing and semantic comprehension to evaluate the veracity of statements.

4. Source Verification: - This is a process of determining the credibility and reliability of sources used in claims, the competency and trustworthiness of the people or organizations that provide the information.

5. Evidence-Based Fact-Checking: - Uses evidence collection and analysis, including data, statistics, expert opinions, and documented sources, to prove or disprove a particular statement and claim.

6. Claim Comparison: - Compares the information in a claim with the existing information, known facts and authoritative sources to ascertain the correctness of the information and any inconsistency.

The backfire effect introduces a twist to the process of debunking. In the context of fact-checking and debunking, the backfire effect describes the tendency of people to become more convinced in the misinformation being debunked when corrected with the correct information. This counterintuitive finding has major implications on the usefulness of fact-checking and debunking operations in combating misinformation. This has been shown to be true in the case of the coronavirus (Walter *et al.*, 2019; Lewandowsky *et al.*, 2012; Pingree *et al.*, 2018; Nyhan, 2021).

A number of studies have examined the occurrence and possible moderators of the backfire effect when it comes to correcting misinformation. First of all, Swire-Thompson *et al.* (2020) note the phenomenon of the backfire effect when a person is given an evidence-based correction and believes even more in the very misconception that the correction is supposed to eliminate. This reflects the backfiring effect of the backfire effect when it comes to misinformation correction. In addition, Lewandowsky *et al.* (2012) explain the backfire effect by the fact that people engage in counterarguing against information that is inconsistent with their worldview.

Also, Pennycook *et al.* (2020) discuss the consequences of the backfire effect, especially when it comes to religious people, highlighting the possibility of strengthening beliefs in the context of debunking. In the future, Ecker *et al.* (2023) will provide evidence on the backfire effect in relation to fact-checking, the way it is manifested by the participants, and the interaction between the type of evidence, its veracity, and the agreement with the news. Moreover, Schmid & Betsch (2022) address the possibility of a failure of fact-checking and debunking efforts, the difficulties of combating misinformation, and the unintended effects of corrective actions.

Krause, Freiling, Beets, and Brossard citing Scheufele and Krause (2019) put it succinctly thus

At first glance, fighting falsehoods with facts may seem like a straightforward strategy to mitigate misinformation. Unfortunately, while fact-checking can sometimes correct individual misperceptions, there is ample evidence from political communication and social psychology showing that fact-checking can be of limited utility—or worse, it can backfire—in contexts where audiences are motivated to defend their pre-existing beliefs.

In the work by Hassan (2022) that examined deception in the age of digital technologies and the distortion of reality and facts: an X-ray of Nigerian peculiarities, the focus was made on the problems of distinguishing between truth and lies because of the emergence of digital deception, fake news, and misinformation. The research underlines the necessity of collective responsibility and increased measures, such as proficiency in media practices, regulatory frameworks, cooperative efforts, media literacy, professional standards, editorial control, and self-monitoring, and detection, to fight the impact of digital deceptions and fake news. These actions coincide with the principles of fact-checking and accuracy of information in the digital environment.

The success of fact-checking remains controversial, with some researchers arguing that corrections do not work. Nieminen and Rapeli (2018) experimentally studied the effectiveness of

correcting misinformation in news articles about immigration and concluded that the correction did not have much of an effect on the perceptions of participants, even after they were made aware of the factual inaccuracies.

The authors observed that there are a number of reasons why fact-checking failed in this instance:

1. Emotional appeal of misinformation causes individuals to reject or reject corrections.
2. The misinformation-congruent worldview results in the counter-arguing of factual corrections.
3. Corrections are less effective in changing perceptions after misinformation has occurred.

On the contrary, the studies by Ecker *et al.* (2022), Porter and Wood (2020) did not agree with the notion that corrections are ineffective most of the time. They noted that fact-checking reduced the belief in misinformation in general. This contradicting evidence indicates that fact-checking may be effective in some cases and not in other cases. Further studies are needed to understand when and how corrections of misinformation are best applied to various groups of people. Nevertheless, it is evident based on the review above that fact-checking remains a significant strategy, but it must be used with caution to avoid possible adverse consequences or ineffectiveness.

2.2.12 Challenges of Fact Checking

Due to the effects of climate change on agriculture, smallholder farmers need to access the correct climate-smart information to cope with the changes. Nevertheless, the development of misinformation and disinformation about climate adaptation methods poses challenges. To make

decisions, farmers should be able to effectively assess and confirm the accuracy of climate-smart agriculture information, which is called fact-checking and is discussed in the previous paragraphs. There are several problems that farmers encounter when it comes to thoroughly vetting the increasing number of climate adaptation data, assertions, and recommendations they encounter.

Research has found limitations such as low climate literacy and insufficient transparency of climate models to be some of the limitations that hinder the ability to critically verify climate change information.

Fact-checking can prove challenging to implement due to differences between what farmers and researchers observe. Asten, (2009) pointed out that the approaches employed in capturing the knowledge of farmers are faulty and therefore incomplete or inaccurate information is obtained. This has the potential of creating and propagating unsustainable, unprofitable or socially unacceptable technologies.

In journalism, the challenge of fact-checking is made worse by the fact that there are no resources to conduct investigative journalism and thus many harmful claims go unchecked, especially at the local levels (Hassan, 2015). Also, he says fact-checking has also become an overwhelming task due to the time consuming process of fact-checking claims. The average article takes one day to research and write, so there can be a long time between the message and the article.

In other research that specifically investigated the issues of fact-checking in the agricultural sector, certain issues have been found to be causing the difficulty of fact-checking claims by smallholder farmers, particularly as it pertains to climate-smart agriculture. These barriers

comprise the lack of access to reliable sources of information, poor infrastructure, and the lack of support of governmental and non-governmental organisations (Kamara *et al.*, 2019; Phiri *et al.*, 2018; Azam and Shaheen, 2019; Baur *et al.*, 2017; Denkyirah *et al.*, 2016). These difficulties may have wide-ranging consequences on the lives of individuals, their farmers, and communities, such as the inability to access their basic needs, make informed decisions, and enhance their quality of life. It is also able to reinforce inequalities and constrain development and progress opportunities.

Moreover, technological resources and digital literacy are also lacking, which increases the challenges of farmers in verifying information (Juneja and Mitra, 2022). Moreover, the effects of armed conflicts and poor government support in some of the areas may add to the burden of smallholder farmers, especially in the post-conflict regions (Maass *et al.*, 2012).

Additionally, farmers have been found to lack climate literacy and critical evaluation skills that can be used to effectively analyse and validate climate data (George, 2007). This is especially alarming considering the effects that climate change will have on agriculture (Sarkar, 2015). It has been found that farmers do not necessarily perceive climate change in accordance with the data and that their awareness and knowledge levels regarding climate change are usually low (Ricart, 2022; Sarkar, 2016). Specific education and training programmes have been identified to be very effective in enhancing the competency of farmers in dealing with climate risk (George, 2007).

Similarly, Agwu, Bakayoko, Jimoh and Poremski, (2018) discovered that the educational level of farmers is a good predictor related to their perception of the impacts of climate change, which include changes in rainfall patterns, drought, flood, temperature, and winds in Nigeria. This

indicates that farmers who are better educated might understand better the phenomenon of climate change. In addition to this, Hein *et al.* (2019) found that correct perceptions of climate trends among farmers are critical to the successful adoption of adaptation measures whereas Ayinde *et al.*, (2018) found that small-scale farmers in Nigeria are highly vulnerable to climate change especially those with limited resources.

Another factor that inhibits fact checking of climate smart agricultural information is access to credible and accurate sources of information. This is essential to remote farmers so that they can cross-check against misinformation and make informed decisions. Due to this effect, many have resorted to the traditional farming practices that in turn result to poor productivity. The factors that motivate farmers to be exposed to information sources have been identified in several studies (Maqbool *et al.*, 2021; Yaseen, Xu, Yao, and Hassan, 2016; Lwoga *et al.*, 2010). These determinants are accessibility, usefulness, and credibility, which have a significant influence on the rate of exposure to information sources (Maqbool *et al.*, 2021).

Information communication technology has been found to be a breakthrough in accessing information in the agricultural sector. Nevertheless, there are certain aspects that restrict the application of ICTs in agricultural practices such as the inability to utilize ICT, technological infrastructure, cost, fear, time, value, and trustworthiness (Awojide, 2018). ICTs can enhance access to valuable agricultural data by farmers, yet adoption is hindered by a number of factors. One of the problems is the absence of technological literacy and skills of smallholder farmers to effectively utilize new ICT platforms (Awojide, 2018). Older generations of farmers are not used to working with smartphones, computers, or internet-based applications that may help them obtain climate and market information. The complicated interfaces and English-only content make it even more difficult. Besides individual capacities, lack of proper technological

infrastructure, including limited access to broadband internet in rural settings, limits the ability of farmers to access information using ICTs. In addition, the prices of acquiring ICT equipment and services discourage resource-poor smallholder farmers. Although the farmers acknowledge the utility of the emerging technologies such as SMS services, they find the costs of accessing information to be too high and not worth their money. The second reason is that 50 percent of the respondents stated that they had to wait more than 10 days to receive the money they had deposited (Aleke *et al.*, 2011; Harris and Achora, 2018; Wyche & Steinfield, 2015; Wawire *et al.*, 2017; Kante *et al.*, 2017). These issues, such as technology illiteracy, lack of infrastructure and affordability, are among the issues that farmers face when it comes to fact checking climate change information.

The spread of misinformation is a major problem in the digital era, especially when it comes to climate change. One of the most common issues with misinformation is that it can spread very quickly via social networks, blurring the line between truth and falsehood in the process, and fact-checkers may not be able to keep up with the speed of spreading (Lamprou, Antonopoulos, Anomeritou and Apostolou, 2021). This is compounded further when the topic of misinformation is a risk as in the case of COVID-19 since it becomes a multi-layered risk communication issue (Krause *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, debunking can decrease the belief at the moment, but corrective messages are forgotten within a short period of time, which makes it difficult to overcome the long-term consequences of misinformation (Brashier, Pennycook, Berinsky, and Rand, 2021).

Climate science information and forecast models are complex procedures, statistics, and computational analysis that may be hard to understand by non-expert groups such as smallholder farmers (Lemos *et al.*, 2012). As an example, the global circulation models include complicated and non-transparent algorithms that produce regional climate projections. The lack of climate

literacy is an important obstacle to farmers trying to critically interpret and fact-check raw data, analytical assumptions, and limitations behind climate projections and advisories. Lack of proper training in the fundamentals of climate science will make farmers unable to verify the authenticity of complex climate data sets, analytics and visualisations they are exposed to through different information channels.

This technical complexity limitation shows that climate researchers and extension workers should improve communication procedures that transform raw data into understandable information to farmers (Hansen *et al.*, 2019). Climate information can be simplified by use of farmer-friendly languages, localised scenarios, analogies, and visuals to fill the comprehension gaps. The joint creation of communication materials by scientists, extension agents and farmers can lead to practical recommendations based on complex information that is nevertheless understandable and verifiable by agricultural communities.

Farmers who are smallholders are usually burdened with labour and time poverty and they must concentrate on the most important activities in farming and livelihoods (Harvey *et al.*, 2014). This does not give farmers much time to carefully authenticate all the climate adaptation recommendations they get through extension agent sources. Verifying data sources, contrasting alternative opinions, and reading scientific literature are time- and effort-consuming activities that limit farmers.

Furthermore, farmers do not have sufficient finances to get paid professional advice or educational materials that would help them assess the accuracy of information. Physical access and financial constraints are also barriers to fact-checking information by visiting local extension offices, research institutions, and regional field sites where climatic changes can be directly

verified by the farmers. The solution to these time and resource constraints is central to enabling farmers to engage in thorough fact-checking of climate data without compromising their livelihood roles (Wawire *et al.*, 2017; Mbagwu *et al.*, 2017; Haworth *et al.*, 2018; Abate *et al.*, 2023).

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

Climate change, a critical global issue with consequences for societies, ecosystems, and economies, has spurred increased attention to its urgency. As the issue of addressing climate change becomes more apparent, the role of media in shaping public perceptions and policy responses is also gaining more attention. This empirical review examines a series of studies that looked into media coverage, framing, public perceptions, adaptation and mitigation strategies, as well as the issues of information disorder in the context of climate change.

Popoola (2014) conducted a study utilising content analysis and dialectical hermeneutics to examine selected nationally circulated Nigerian newspapers (Daily Trust, Guardian, Punch, Thisday) from 1999-2000. Using systematic and purposive sampling, 480 editions of the newspapers were selected over the 2-year period. From these, 520 journalistic issues and editorial items were analyzed using four environmental issues as content categories: flood, erosion, pollution, and deforestation. The study found that the newspapers gave considerable coverage to environmental topics, especially erosion and flooding. Features were commonly used, allowing for extensive description of the issues. The newspapers devoted significant space to environmental coverage based on story length and paragraph counts. However, the issues did not receive high prominence in terms of front page placement and headline size.

As a result of the disappointing media coverage of climate change in advanced and developing nations, Kakonga (2020) embarked on the investigation of challenges and opportunities for increasing media coverage of climate change in Kenya. One of the major findings of the study was the fact that reporting on climate change by Kenya's leading newspapers and television channels from 2010 to 2019 was not much. The findings also revealed that lack of strong political and financial support is a major challenge for the media to sustain their momentum in reporting on climate change and producing informative and engaging stories. He recommended that capacity-building and educational initiatives should be prioritized to enhance journalist knowledge and expertise in climate change reporting.

More so, Neondo, Lando, and Odhiambo (2021) focused on Kenyan newspapers, evaluating the framing and placement of climate change stories. With the utilization of the framing and agenda setting theory, the findings revealed that there were insufficient coverage for climate change issues in the country as climate change stories usually did not make it to the front page or other important spots in the newspaper. They noted that this may have contributed to the Kenyan government's failure to fully implement international agreements on climate change. The study recommended engaging gatekeepers and public relation practitioners to enhance the visibility of climate change issues, highlighting the potential of media advocacy to drive action.

The news media play an influential role in shaping public opinion on a wide range of issues, climate change inclusive. This was emphasized in a study by Stecula and Merkley (2019), who investigated the developing space of climate change coverage within important U.S. media outlets by utilizing the frame theory to investigate the prevalence of different frames in climate change news of prominent news sources such as the New York Times, Wall Street Journal, Washington Post, and Associated Press from 1988 onwards. The study found that there are

significant shift in media framing patterns. Frames that historically prevents public support for climate action, like those highlighting potential economic drawbacks or uncertainties, have witnessed a decline in mainstream media coverage. Conversely, frames conducive to public engagement, including the economic benefits of climate action, have gained prominence. The study also highlights the increasing use of risk-focused language and present tense constructs in news content. This implies that, the evident changes in media framing could be instrumental in driving public awareness and action on climate change issues.

Rong and Zanuddin (2018) investigated the role of two Malaysian Chinese newspapers in influencing the opinion of the population on climate change. Applying the content analysis and agenda-setting theory, they discovered that the coverage of climate issues was rather low, but it rose during the major international events on climate. The two newspapers were different in terms of emphasis: Sin Chew Daily emphasized adaptive strategies whereas China Press paid more attention to the negative local effects.

Moreover, Okoro (2023) investigated the level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of climate change adaptation in Anambra State. The study relied on the knowledge-gap theory, and used both surveys and focus group discussions in two vulnerable communities, Onitsha North (urban) and Aguleri (rural). A sample size of 40 was purposively selected. The Findings show that approximately 60 percent of the urban respondents were aware of causes and effects of climate change, whereas the level of awareness was very low among rural respondents. This findongs shows that there are evident differences between urban and rural residents, with the former being more informed and active in adaptation measures. Okoro pointed out the necessity of specific interventions, suggesting more media campaigns and educational programs to overcome the gap in knowledge in rural areas.

Coverage of climate and sustainability topics in the news aids in improving awareness and understanding of environmental concepts among the public. This was averred in a study by Nirmala and Aram (2018) who conducted a content analysis of two Indian newspapers to ascertain the framing of climate change and sustainability issue in the country. While it was revealed that both newspapers underreported local stories and environmental challenges, indicating a lack of journalistic capacity and understanding of local environmental issues, they also found that scientific and international perspective frames received significant coverage, especially during the Paris Climate Summit (COP21). Also, they discovered that public accountability/governance and economic frames were present in both newspapers.

Deductively, the studies discussed above reveal that media has a big role in how people understand climate change. They show that the way media report about climate change, called "framing," can shape how the public thinks and what actions they take. These studies looked at different countries and found that media coverage and framing can be influenced by where you live and what issues are important there. Some studies found that media is starting to talk more about the benefits of climate action and the risks of not doing anything, which can help people care more about the issue. We can safely say here that the use of framing in investigating how the media report climate change issue has been overflogged and there is need for scholars to take in-depth look into other areas of concern in the area of media and climate change reporting.

Consequently, recent studies have shown a noticeable shift towards sustainable development and the formulation of better strategies for adaptation and resilience, particularly within communities and regions (Tiamiyu, Ugalahi, Fabunmi, Sanusi, Fapojuwo, and Shittu, 2018). This shift has been influenced by the United Nations' Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), which has emphasized the importance of conducting extensive research on climate change and its impact on

agriculture. The FAO's commitment to addressing these challenges is reflected in its 2016 directive, which highlights the critical role of research in bolstering the sustainability of agriculture in the face of a rapidly changing climate. This transformation encompasses a growing emphasis on building resilience within communities and ecosystems, with a particular focus on farmers in Africa. Some of these studies are reviewed below.

A recent study focusing on the agricultural sector was conducted by Ifeanyi-obi *et.al* (2023) to investigate traditional perceptions and their impact on climate change adaptation decisions among women crop farmers in southern Nigeria. This study employed the survey research approach to engage a sample of 420 rural women crop farmers using a multi-stage sampling method. Data were also collected through structured interviews and focus group discussions. The study revealed that a significant portion (approximately 89%) of these women had taken the step to adapt to climate change, with 81% of them translating their decision into action by implementing climate change adaptation strategies. The study pinpointed a range of traditional beliefs that shaped their perspectives on climate change, including notions of complexity, human negligence, rainfall and temperature variations, violation of traditional farming rituals, and divine intervention. This highlights the vital role of these traditional perceptions in influencing their adaptive choices. Therefore, the study emphasized the importance of fostering knowledge and awareness through training workshops on climate change.

More studies in the area of perceptions of farmers regarding climate change-related events was carried out by Goyol and Pathirage (2018). They examined the perceptions of farmers regarding climate change-related events in two regions of Nigeria (Shendam and Riyom). Their research revealed that farmers in these areas were able to identify indicators of climate change, particularly changes in rainfall and temperature patterns. The study also found that floods had a

significant impact on road transport systems, while droughts adversely affected irrigation infrastructure. Both events leading to negative effects on agricultural activities, economic activities, and livelihood systems. They recommended that there is need to strengthen institutional capacity for risk reduction through the provision of resilient infrastructures to mitigate the adverse impacts of climate-related events on agrarian systems and livelihoods.

Also examining climate change adaptation in Nigerian agricultural sector, Onyeneke *et al.* (2020) conducted a systematic review and resilience assessment in their study titled "Climate Change Adaptation in Nigerian Agricultural Sector: A Systematic Review and Resilience Check of Adaptation Measures." Utilizing the Ifejika-Speranza Resilience Check Toolkit, the review aimed to understand how well the measures adopted by farmers in Nigeria contribute to addressing climate change risks and enhancing sustainability. Findings from the review revealed that the changing climate in Nigeria is adversely affecting the productivity and livelihoods of smallholder rural farmers and that majority of the adaptation studies in Nigeria focus on crop farming. This means there is need for more research in other agricultural sectors in Nigeria. More so, they discovered a research gap in the resilience aspect of adaptation measures adopted by these farmers.

The role of knowledge sharing and support systems, such as extension services, in facilitating effective adaptation among poultry farmers was emphasized in the study by Sanou *et al.* (2022) to explore the perceptions and adaptation strategies of poultry farmers in Nigeria in response to higher temperatures associated with climate change. The researchers investigated the perception of farmers' as regards temperature changes, their understanding of the impacts of higher temperatures on poultry production, and the adaptation strategies they employ to mitigate these effects. The research made use of a mixed-method approach, with a combination of surveys and

interviews among poultry farmers in osun state, Nigeria. One major finding drawn from the study is that poultry farmers in the region have a high level of awareness and perception of temperature changes and their impacts on poultry production. The farmers reported observing increased heat stress, reduced feed intake, decreased egg production, and increased mortality rates among their poultry due to higher temperatures.

Adepoju and Osunbor (2018) studied small scale poultry farmers by examining the factors influencing their choice of adaptation strategies to climate change. The study collected data from 121 representative farmers in Ogun State, Nigeria, using a two-stage random sampling procedure. It was discovered from the findings of the study that a significant proportion of the respondents were crop producers (43%) and livestock producers (31%). Most farmers reported adjusting the timing of their farming operations and increasing the use of agricultural inputs as their primary adaptation strategies. The study further identified several factors influencing farmers' selection of climate change adaptation measures, including age, gender, educational attainment, farming experience, access to credit, farm or herd size, membership in cooperatives, household income, and availability of weather information and extension services. Additionally, access to credit, extension services, and information on weather conditions were found to influence farmers' decision-making regarding climate change adaptation. This study further highlights the importance of awareness creation, education, and extension services in promoting climate variability adaptation approaches among small-scale poultry farmers, all of which fall under the purview of mass media. It was suggested that the government should enhance public awareness of high-temperature conditions and adaptive strategies to address heat stress, thereby shaping farmers' perceptions and willingness to adopt climate change adaptation measures.

On the same note, Odok, Unaeze, Ogueri, Essien, Ukpong, Bassey, and Ohajianya (2018) examined climate variability and its effects on poultry farming in Abia State, Nigeria. In their study, they compared 30 years of climate data (1983-2012) with farmers adaptive responses. The analysis showed that there was a lot of inter-annual variation in rainfall but the correlation with time was not significant. However, these fluctuations had adverse impacts on poultry production, which led to increased mortality, disease outbreaks, smaller egg sizes, poor egg shell quality, heat stress, and decreased feed consumption. To overcome these challenges, farmers resorted to various coping mechanisms, such as use of climate-resistant breeds, better feeding, mixed farming, artificial cooling and changing stocking patterns in extreme weather.

Similarly, Popoola, Monde, and Yusuf (2019) investigated the perceptions and adaptation responses of smallholder poultry farmers in Amathole District, Eastern Cape, South Africa, to the effects of climate change. The study revealed that farmers experienced a number of adverse consequences such as decreased egg production, low quality eggs, weight loss among birds, increased feed prices, disease outbreaks, and high mortality using a multi-stage survey method. These results are consistent with those of Anosike *et al.* (2020), who found that the most significant limitations to poultry farming in Nigeria were frequent diseases, pest infestation, credit and loan challenges, high cost of feeds, poor quality chicks, inadequate extension services and lack of veterinary services. Although these challenges were experienced, adaptation measures among South African farmers were very minimal and were mostly confined to rearing of different bird breeds, downsizing of flock sizes and reliance on social welfare. The researchers suggested the implementation of wider and more varied measures to enhance resilience in poultry production.

More studies have in recent times looked into adaptation and mitigation strategies employed against climate change especially in the poultry agricultural sector. One of such is the study by Liverpool-Tasie, Sanou and Tambo (2019) which delved into the intricate landscape of climate change adaptation strategies among poultry farmers in Nigeria. The study population were drawn from kaduna and Oyo state with the aim of comprehensively assessing the adoption of these strategies among the poultry farmers. The findings of the study revealed that poultry farmers in Nigeria adapt to climate change differently based on farm size. Small farms rely on traditional strategies, while medium and large farms adopt modern technologies. Furthermore, farmers who experience losses due to heat stress are more likely to adopt modern agricultural practices and multiple adaptation strategies. This means that the importance of farm size and contextual challenges such as heat-related losses cannot be overlooked especially in formulating effective adaptation policies and strategies. They however recommended the need for effective communication to share and disseminate innovative agricultural strategies, including cost-effective modifications of existing techniques and the potential for breeding heat-tolerant breeds, particularly when traditional modern methods are not feasible for smaller farms or specific contexts. This burden of information dissemination relies on the media.

In addition, Liverpool-Tasie, Pummel, Tambo, Olabisi, and Osuntade (2020) investigated perceptions and exposure to climate events across Nigeria's agricultural value chains. Using a mixed-methods design that combined surveys and interviews with farmers, traders, processors, and other stakeholders, the study highlighted that different actors experience and interpret climate impacts differently, with farmers being the most directly affected. Key events such as droughts, floods, and extreme temperatures were found to reduce crop yields, lower livestock productivity, and increase post-harvest losses. Focusing on the maize-poultry value chain, the

research further revealed gaps in awareness and understanding of the link between economic activities and climate change, emphasizing the need for targeted education and improved adaptation strategies along the value chain.

Likewise, when considering the maize value chain, a study by Adeagbo *et al.* (2021) which seeks to investigate the factors influencing the adoption and intensity of climate change adaptation strategies among smallholder maize farmers in South-west Nigeria, also pointed out the need for targeted interventions to support farmers in adapting to changing climatic conditions. In a manner that is consistent with Liverpool-Tasie *et al.* (2020), this research show that farmers in the study area are aware of climate variation and its impacts on their farming activities. The farmers perceive variation in precipitation patterns and rising temperatures, which have introduced unfavorable growing conditions and modified growing seasons, affecting crop productivity and food security. The study also identifies factors such as access to credit, household size, non-farm income, and age as significant determinants of farmers' uptake and amount of climate variability adaptation technique.

Likewise, Durodola (2019) reviewed the effects of climate change–induced extreme events on agriculture and food security in Nigeria. Drawing on both electronic and non-electronic sources, the study synthesized existing research on how floods and droughts disrupt agricultural productivity and threaten food availability. The review underscored the urgent need for adaptation strategies to cushion the sector against these shocks. These conclusions align with Tiamiyu *et al.* (2018), who also stressed that stronger efforts and further research on climate change mitigation and adaptation are essential for safeguarding Nigeria's agricultural output

According to Popoola, Wahab, Hangwelani, Chipungu and Adeleye (2020) the reality of climate variability is evident across all sectors of the economy including the agricultural sector. One concept that has emerged in recent climate change studies as a result of the pressing challenges posed by climate change and the growing interest in ecological agricultural practices is Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA). The concept of climate-smart agriculture (CSA) has gained significant attention and recognition as a pathway to reducing emissions and building resilience in agriculture. The United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) have championed CSA as a key approach to addressing climate change impacts on agriculture (Chuang *et al.*, 2020). It therefore emphasizes the need to enhance agricultural productivity while simultaneously building resilience to climate variability and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the agricultural sector.

One study in this area, Fawole *et al.* (2021) who conducted a research by employing the Adoption Theory to investigate the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices (CSAPs) among rural farmers in Nigeria. The study found that the adoption of climate-smart agriculture practices was low but despite this, the farmers are adopting various climate-smart agricultural practices to boost productivity, like using organic manure and growing drought-resistant crops. However, the researcher also identified challenges, such as insufficient funding, limited practical knowledge of the approach, and restricted access to information on climate-smart agricultural practices, and socio-economic constraints at the farm level. They suggested that raising awareness and providing support can help farmers better adopt these climate-smart strategies, ultimately improving agricultural sustainability and resilience.

Likewise, Kutyaauripo, Mavodza and Gadzirayi (2021) studied media coverage on food security and climate-smart agriculture. The study aimed to find out the factors influencing media

coverage and highlight the importance of effective communication in addressing climate change and food security challenges. From the findings of the study, it was evident that climate change impacts, such as excessive rainfall, droughts, and temperature increases have negative effects on crop yields and livestock productivity, increasing the risk of food insecurity. More importantly, newspaper coverage on climate change and food security tends to focus more on business, political news, and social issues, with limited coverage of agricultural and developmental issues. They recommended that news on climate-smart agriculture should address all stages of the food system and also emphasize the need for effective communication strategies to simplify scientific findings and promote climate-smart agricultural practices.

Climate change awareness, extension services, and the adoption of climate-smart agriculture practices in mitigating the impacts of climate change on rice farming was consequently studied by Onyeneke, Nwajiuba, Emenekwe, Nwajiuba, Onyeneke, Ohalete and Uwazie (2021) in their paper titled climate change perception and uptake of climate-smart agriculture in Rice Production in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Making use of cross-sectional data from 347 rice farmers in the state, the study found that Perceived climate events include increased rainfall intensity, extended dry seasons, frequent flooding, rising temperatures, severe windstorms, irregular rainfall patterns and distribution, delayed onset of rains, and early cessation of rainfall. Farmers' perceptions of climate change were influenced by their socioeconomic, farm, and institutional characteristics. It was also discovered that the adoption of climate-smart agriculture practices, such as crop and land management practices, water and soil conservation, and adjusting planting and harvesting dates were strategies utilized to mitigate the effects of climate change on rice production in the state. Evidently, this study revealed the need for effective climate change

communication, extension services, and sustainable agricultural practices to enhance the resilience and productivity of farmers in the face of climate change challenges.

Similarly, Chuang, Wang and Liou (2020) conducted a study to find out farmers' knowledge, attitude, and adoption of smart agriculture technology in Taiwan. The study emphasized various aspects related to smart agriculture, including its role in addressing agricultural problems, the integration of digital technology in farming practices, the influence of psychological factors on innovation adoption, and the relationship between farm characteristics and smart agriculture adoption. They also noted that the climate-smart agriculture initiative proposed by the Food and The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations has attracted international attention, thereby positioning smart agriculture as a significant trend contributing to agricultural development. With this in mind, they conducted a survey of 321 farmers in 2017 and 2018. The showed strong positive relationships between smart agriculture knowledge, perceived importance, and adoption behavior; Knowledge of smart agriculture and its perceived importance had a significant influence on the adoption of smart agriculture technologies. Hence, lower adoption levels of Smart agriculture technologies may perhaps be explained by insufficient information, limited knowledge, low awareness of the technologies, and a perceived lack of practical relevance. This means there is an information gap for the lower adoption of smart agriculture which brings to bear the role of the media in the dissemination of information.

Alalade (2023) conducted a study to find out the Status of climate smart agriculture among farmers in North-Central Nigeria. His study was to establish the determinants of climate smart agriculture in the region by randomly selecting two hundred and forty-seven farmers the study area and also conducting focus group discussions. The result of the study revealed that mass media exposure is one of the determinant for the adoption of climate-smart agriculture is

influenced by various factors. This includes farming experience, education level, access to extension services, livestock ownership, income, land tenure, household size, access to credit, size of cultivated land, proximity to markets and water resources, leadership roles, risk orientation, and gender.

Kompat, *et.al* (2021) conducted a study by reviewing the uptake of climate-smart agriculture technology by agricultural households in sub-saharan Africa. The research which employed a mixed methodology and an integrative literature review highlighted the fact that the adoption rates of climate-smart agriculture technologies in Sub-Saharan Africa remain low. They discovered that the adoption of climate-smart agriculture technologies is influenced by various factors, including farmers' knowledge and awareness of climate-smart agriculture, access to resources, and the suitability of technologies to local conditions. More important from their findings is the fact that the dissemination of information and best practices through agricultural research and development networks and agricultural extension services is important for promoting climate-smart agriculture adoption. While they recommended that measures should be put in place to ensure that climate-smart agriculture actions are implemented using bottom-up approaches, they also emphasized the importance of helping farmers to shift their understanding of the impacts of climate change and the most appropriate practices to implement in order to achieve the goal of sustainable development one and two (eradication of poverty and zero hunger) by the year 2030.

In their study, roles of social networks in the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices among rural farm households in southern Nigeria, Ogunnaike, Osinowo and Olabode, (2021) focused on rural farm households in Nigeria, where climate change poses significant challenges. The study which was carried out in selected farming communities in Southern Nigeria, known

for their maize and rice production in Southern Nigeria gathered data through structured questionnaires, covering socioeconomic and cultural activities, social networks, and adopted climate-smart agricultural practices on cultivated land. The results revealed that farmers gain awareness of new resource management practices and their implementation through participation in various groups while they believe that maintaining social networks is essential for effective knowledge sharing and mutual support. The study further reveals that the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices is influenced not only by the size of farmers' social networks but also by household, farm, and institutional characteristics. They however recommended that in the absence of formal information channels, social networks and community ties play a crucial role in the adoption of new technologies along the climate-smart agricultural practices chain.

More climate-smart agriculture adoption research was conducted by Faleye and Afolami (2020) to understand the factors that influence the adoption of Climate Smart Agricultural practices among yam-based farming households in Ogun State, Nigeria. The researchers employed a multi-stage sampling technique methodology in selecting a sample of 160 respondents from different Agricultural Development Programme (ADP) zones in the state. The findings from the study revealed that the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices is influenced by various factors which includes access to radio information, farm size, volume of credit, farming experience, and number of household members/farm activities were also considered contacts with extension agents, and membership in cooperative society; all these believe are positively significant to the adoption. This is consistent with the findings of Ogunaike *et.al* (2021) above. They recommended that the introduction of climate-smart agricultural practices to yam-based farmers should not be in an entirely new technology model, but rather as improvements upon

indigenous practices they are familiar with. This they believe will facilitate faster and more effective adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices in the region.

The study conducted by Oresanya and Olajide (2023) explores the potential of reality television shows (RTS) as a medium for disseminating information on climate-smart agriculture (CSA) strategies in southwestern Nigeria. The researchers highlight the popularity of RTS as an entertainment education tool and its potential for conveying targeted educational messages to specific audiences. A multi-stage sampling procedure was utilized to select 121 farmers and data were collected through interviews, focusing on farmers' socio-economic characteristics, sources of information on climate change and climate-smart agriculture, awareness of reality television shows, perceived constraints, and propensity to use reality television shows for information on climate-smart agriculture strategies. The findings of the study revealed that the majority of the farmers were male, smallholders, and had an average age of 44.9 years. While television was identified as a common source of information for most farmers, none of them were aware of any Nigerian reality television shows specifically used to promote agriculture. Further findings from the study show that the perceived Constraints to the use of reality television shows included poor network reception, unstable electricity supply, limited sponsorship, and concerns about sustainability. Despite these constraints, the study revealed that a considerable proportion of farmers (69.4%) demonstrated a strong tendency to rely on reality television shows as a source of information on climate-smart agriculture.

In addition, Oyewole, Oyewole, and Isola (2022) discussed how climate-smart agricultural (CSA) practices can enhance resilience and profitability among maize farmers in Oyo and Ogun States. The study examined the connection between CSA adoption and profit efficiency using a multi-stage sampling of 370 farmers in four LGAs and 16 communities. Results showed that

adoption of CSA practices was low across the board with the exception of improved seed varieties, which was adopted by over half of the respondents. Farm size, labor costs, and herbicide use were found to have significant effect on profitability. The study also found out some of the important CSA practices like cover cropping, agroforestry, and crop rotation, but the rate of adoption of these practices was low.

Studies have also examined the role of the media, specifically agricultural radio programs in promoting the adoption of agricultural production innovations among farmers. One of such studies was conducted by Chinda, SalamatuShuwa and Yagana (2019) among farmers in Girei Local Government of Adamawa State. Data were collected using the survey method with a random selection of 113 farmers in ten villages. The study found that a large proportion of respondents were aware of agricultural programs broadcast on local radio stations, particularly Gotel FM (80.5%) and Adamawa Broadcasting Corporation (63.7%). The study also revealed that farmers' age, level of education, farm size, and ownership of radio devices were key factors influencing the adoption of agricultural technologies promoted through radio programs. They however recommended on the one hand that radio stations should give more airtime slots to agricultural programmes so as to create awareness for farmers and on the other hand that farmers should attain some level of formal education to enhance their ability to effectively utilize technologies promoted through radio broadcasts. In addition, radio stations were advised to allocate more airtime to agricultural programs in order to increase farmers' awareness

On the other hand, Akwiwu and Patrick (2020) evaluated the effectiveness of Agricultural Development Programmes (ADPs) in the dissemination of agricultural information through mass media in Imo State. The study based on a multi-stage sample of 120 farmers showed that radio was the most prevalent media with 88.3% of respondents using it. Nevertheless, the general use

of mass media remained low with only 58.3% reporting to have accessed agricultural information using the mass media. Significantly, the correlation between the frequency of media use and the perceived effectiveness of ADPs communication efforts was positive. The authors suggested that ADPs should develop their own indigenous media to enhance content control and delivery of extension.

Additionally, Danjuma, Agir, Zubairu and Agya (2021) conducted a study on the role of radio agricultural programs in farmers' education, specifically focusing on Radio Benue in Makurdi, Benue State. The study aimed to analyze the role of radio in educating farmers and utilized a survey research design with a questionnaire as the data collection instrument. The sample consisted of 384 respondents selected through purposive, stratified, and simple random sampling techniques. The findings of the study revealed that farmers gained knowledge through listening to the radio programs. For example, 28.4% of the respondents gained knowledge about appropriate fertilizer application through programs such as "Farming World" and "Tom Sule" (in Tiv) aired by Radio Benue. Additionally, 26.8% of respondents reported gaining knowledge about agricultural practices, while 25.8% acquired information on preventing post-harvest losses. The study concluded that radio serves as a vital medium for raising awareness and disseminating agricultural information among farmers. It further recommended that the government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) provide grants and farm loans through agricultural programs to promote and support farming activities.

Similarly, Sulaiman (2021) investigated the effects of modern media on the access to agricultural information among poultry farmers in Lagelu Local Government Area of Oyo State. The study evaluated the use of tools including smartphones, radio, television, newspapers, and magazines using a survey design and structured questionnaires. The results indicated that men were more

active in poultry production, whereas women were more active in processing and marketing, which means that gender-sensitive communication strategies are needed. The youth and middle-aged farmers were also found to be very active implying that they are willing to use modern media to access agricultural information. Smartphones, especially, became important sources to get information on diseases, vaccines, feed formulation, and marketing. Media use was strongly influenced by socio-economic factors, including age, education, years in poultry production, farm size and income. The research concluded that modern media, and in particular smartphones, have increased the productivity and livelihoods of farmers and suggested that internet access should be improved and that print materials should be distributed by extension visits.

In the same vein, Yahaya, Adamson, and Kareem (2018) examined the extent of agricultural program coverage in broadcast media in Oyo State and the factors influencing program selection. Using questionnaires administered to 60 respondents, the study revealed that only five broadcast stations featured agricultural content, with 55.6% of them offering very limited coverage. Advertisement emerged as the main determinant of program choice, while inadequate use of indigenous languages in broadcasts was found to reduce audience engagement and trust. The authors stressed the need for greater inclusion of local languages to improve farmers' understanding of agricultural content and called for expanded coverage of agricultural programs in the media. They also pointed out the scarcity of research in this area, recommending further studies to strengthen media contributions to agricultural development.

On their own part, Sule, Datsu, Abubakar and Tauheed (2021) conducted a study in Bosso Local Government Area of Niger State, Nigeria, to examine the effectiveness of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in disseminating agricultural information to rural farmers. Findings showed that 62% of farmers were aware of ICTs, while 63% reported having access.

Additionally, 41% owned radio, television, and mobile phones, and 27% owned radio and mobile phones. They also discovered that all respondents perceived ICTs as effective tools for extension service delivery. Moreover, 63% of respondents considered mobile phones to be timely and relevant for accessing agricultural information. This findings are in consonance with the discovery of Sulaiman (2021) where the majority of the respondents prefer the use of smart phones in getting agricultural information. This points to the fact that farmers are becoming aware of the power of information communication technology gadgets and they are actually making use of it to garner agricultural-related information.

In a 2019 study, Ifejika, Asadu, Enibe, Ifejika, and Sule investigated the extent to which Agricultural Development Programmes (ADPs) in the North Central Zone of Nigeria have integrated social media into e-extension service delivery. The study aimed to assess the utilization of social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, and mobile phone tools in the communication strategies of Agricultural Development Programmes (ADPs). The findings of the study revealed that there were insufficient field extension agents to effectively reach out to the 1.412 million farm families in the zone. The study also found that social media platforms were not included in the communication strategies of ADPs, with more focus on traditional media such as radio and television and the use of traditional media was found to be costly and achieved low projected targets. They recommended the mainstreaming of social media in e-extension services to effectively reach out to farm families and overcome the shortage of field manpower. This study shows the need for training and capacity building of ADP staff on social media to improve their competence and skills in extension delivery to the agribusiness community considering the fact that a large percentage of farmers are now aware and use information communication technology gadgets to access information.

Furthermore, Ojo and Koledoye (2022) examined how agricultural information is disseminated in Nigeria through indigenous language newspapers and national print media using content analysis. Using a comparative approach by looking into popular Yoruba indigenous newspapers in south west Nigeria (Akede Agbagye and Alaroye) as indigenous language newspapers and The Nation and Punch as national newspapers for analysis. The findings of the study revealed that the newspapers featured a relatively low amount of agricultural-related information. The study also notably found that there was a significant difference in the coverage of agricultural news between indigenous language and national newspapers, with national newspapers featuring more agricultural news. They however concluded that agricultural news was not adequately disseminated in the newspapers, particularly in local dailies that farmers rely on for information. They recommended that agriculture-related information should be published on platforms accessible to the target audience for effective communication. This implies that local newspapers, which are essential sources of information for farmers, are not effectively covering and disseminating agricultural news, potentially hindering farmers' access to valuable information

In addition, the research by Eta, Idiku, Elemi and Eremi (2022) was conducted in Cross River State. They looked into access of crop farmers to electronic information (e-information) to climate-smart agriculture. The authors utilized multistage sampling process to identify 191 respondents and information was gathered using a structured questionnaire. The results showed that agroforestry, water harvesting practices, were least used climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices. irrigation facilities, land reclamation practices, and construction and use. One important finding from the study revealed that information for climate-smart agriculture was primarily through the radio, with some use of internet websites and social media platforms. The study

however found a weak positive relationship between farmers' use of climate-smart agriculture practices and their access to e-information. This indicates that while some farmers who have access to electronic information are adopting climate-smart practices, this access alone does not strongly drive or guarantee their adoption of such practices.

In a similar vein, farmers were aware and utilized the climate-smart agricultural practices as investigated in a study conducted by Waaswa, Nkurumwa and Kibe, (2021) which focused on the communication of climate change adaptation strategies, specifically climate-smart agriculture (CSA) information dissemination pathways among smallholder potato farmers in Gilgil Sub-County, Kenya. More so, The study highlights the importance of extension officers as key sources of climate-smart agricultural information for smallholder potato farmers, they suggested that extension services should be strengthened to effectively disseminate climate-smart agricultural information and promote the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices among farmers.

Farmers' perception of climate change is often associated with climate change knowledge, this was discovered in the investigation carried out by Madaki, Muench, Kaechele and Bavorova (2023) in a study to know Climate Change Knowledge and Perception among Farming Households in Nigeria. By interviewing One thousand and eighty (1080) smallholder farmers across six agro-ecological zones (AEZs) of Nigeria using a structured questionnaire, the result further revealed that most farmers know that deforestation and land clearance by bush burning contributes to climate change but in contrast, many farmers did not know that methane emissions from livestock (enteric fermentation) can cause climate change. With their discovery that farmers make use of radio in receiving climate change information, they recommended that using government services, environmental NGOs, and radio as channels for climate change

information can further guide and shape farmers' perceptions of scientific findings, thereby promoting appropriate actions. This further emphasizes the pivotal role that media play in dissemination of agricultural information.

In the dissemination of climate-smart agricultural information, the knowledge of extension agents on climate-smart agricultural initiatives in South-West Nigeria was investigated by Olorunfemi, Olorunfemi, Oladele and Malomo, (2021). A total of two-hundred and seventy-seven extension agents were administered questionnaires in oyo, ekiti and ondo. The results indicated that extension agents demonstrated relatively high knowledge of crop-mix (56.3%) and tillage-smart (53.4%) initiatives, with more than half scoring above the mean benchmark. However, their knowledge was low in most other areas, including water management (59.2%), fossil-fuel use (94.2%), soil-related practices (75.8%), ICT, and other adaptive initiatives (98.9%), where the majority scored below the benchmark. They therefore recommended that extension organizations should organize seminars and workshops to enhance agents' knowledge of these initiatives, thereby equipping them to provide effective advisory services to farmers.

In Anambra state, Nwalieji *et al.* (2019) investigated mass media utilization by poultry farmers in the state by assessing media usage patterns, discerning primary channels, and gauging utilization levels across poultry farming issues. Through a survey of 120 farmers, findings revealed a diverse range of media sources used by the respondents, including newspapers, radio, television, agricultural books, journals, mobile phones, and the internet. It was also clear from the findings that farmers exhibited the highest media engagement regarding disease control, chicks' rearing techniques, feeding, housing, and routine management. The major constraints to effective mass media utilization were inadequate funds, irregular power supply, and the lack of needed poultry information in newspapers and radio.

Chukwuji, Tsafe, Sayudi, Yusuf and Zakariya (2019) conducted a study in Zamfara State, Nigeria, focusing on farmers' awareness, access, and use of climate change information. The study found that 95% of Zamfara's population are farmers, showing the significance of agriculture in the region. This emphasizes the importance of targeting agricultural communities with climate change information through media. Also from their findings, radio, television, and extension services, play a vital role in disseminating climate change information to farmers as the majority of the farmers say radio is the major source of getting this information. These climate change information from media sources, according to their findings helped farmers to make decisions about crop selection and planting time.

Fadairo, Williams and Nalwanga (2020) conducted a study on the perceived livelihood impacts and adaptation of vegetable farmers to climate change in Ghana, Uganda, and Nigeria. The study employed a development planning approach to assess climate change vulnerability and adaptation among the respondents using a multi-stage sampling method to gather data from 193 vegetable farmers in prominent vegetable production areas. They identified inadequate climate information and poor agricultural extension services as major factors constraining farmers' capability to adjust to changing climate in Nigeria. The study shows the different effects of climate change on vegetable farmers in Nigeria, Ghana, and Uganda, as well as the varying priorities for adaptation strategies in these countries. The findings proposed need for local climate adaptation strategies to address the challenges faced by farmers in each region.

Das, Ahmed and Awal, (2022) conducted a study specifically focusing on the role of radio and television in the dissemination of agricultural technologies among farmers in Bangladesh. The study revealed that radio and television had an effective role in improving awareness and

increasing farmers' knowledge of modern agricultural technologies. These media platforms also facilitated farmers' access to marketing information.

In a similar study, Oyedele (2018) thesis examined the source of climate change information and knowledge, attitudes and practices of climate friendly farming among farmers in Osun, Oyo, and Ondo States. Based on the Protection Motivation and Planned Behaviour theories, the researchers used survey data to demonstrate that farmers received information primarily through radio, extension officers, television, newspapers, rural associations, the Internet, and personal networks, with the radio being the most influential source. Farmers were more knowledgeable on man-made causes of climate change (e.g., pollution, illegal logging) than natural ones. Their favorable attitudes were determined by exposure to radio and extension services, credibility of the messages, complexity of the messages and socioeconomic factors. There was also a strong correlation between access to information and better knowledge of climate risks. Although adaptation strategies were more common than mitigation, factors like farming experience, better seeds, land rights, cultural and religious practices influenced adaptation. Most of the respondents were crop farmers. The research findings were that effective climate communication needs greater participation of extension officers, media practitioners, and farmers in the design and implementation of communication policies to facilitate informed adaptation and mitigation choices. On the other hand, Ternenge and Sabo (2022) examined the public perception of radio surveillance in the distribution of COVID-19 palliatives to smallholder farmers in Nigeria. They found that radio played a significant role in monitoring the distribution of palliatives, although the impact was not significantly felt among smallholder farmers.

usage of new media among farmers have also been investigated by Ogunsola, Alarape, Adesida, Ojo-Fakuade and Marizu (2021) in their study which seek to examine the utilization of new

media for communication between extension agents and farmers in Oyo state, Nigeria. Data for this study was collected by randomly selecting forty extension agents and eighty farmers. The study found that majority of extension agents and farmers are aware of and have access to various new media platforms such as social media, agricultural websites, and agricultural blogs. More so, it was discovered from the findings of the study that the use of new media have benefits for both extension agents and farmers, including enhancing job commitments, saving time and money, and sourcing information on farmers' livelihoods and improving their living standards. They however recommended training for extension staff on the importance of new media use and the provision of broadband connectivity to enhance the use of new media in agricultural and rural development. This study therefore shed more light on the potential of new media in facilitating communication and knowledge sharing in agricultural sector.

In the field of climate change discourse and communication, one pressing concern that deserves our attention as regards this study is the challenge of information disorder. As the media plays an important role in shaping public perceptions and informing the society about climate change and strategies of coping with it, it becomes imperative to acknowledge the dissemination of inaccurate, misleading, or deliberately false information about climate change. In the context of climate change, misinformation can take many forms, from outright denial of its existence to misleading portrayals of its impacts and potential solutions. This issue not only obstructs the effectiveness of climate-smart agriculture, mitigation and adaptation strategies but also erodes the public's trust in the media as a reliable sources of information.

Making use of the hierarchy of influence theory to establish how reporters deal with misinformation on climate change and their perceptions of using fact-checking tools to combat it, Ejaz, Ittefaq and Arif (2022) averred that complex and scientific nature of climate change,

particularly within a contemporary media setting that includes growing misinformation, has challenged environmental journalists. In their study where 21 climate and environmental journalist were interviewed, it was found that lack of expertise and education hinder individual coverage of environmental issues. Interestingly, the study added that the journalists interviewed believe there is no widespread climate misinformation in Pakistan, which may reduce the perceived need for fact-checking tools.

In the same vein, Popoola, Yusuf, and Monde (2020) averred that the dearth of climate change information is one amongst many agricultural production challenges faced by the majority of rural farming communities. Consequently, they conducted a study to examine the information sources and constraints to climate change adaptation among smallholder farmers in the Amathole District Municipality in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. Anchoring the study on media dependency theory, the researchers found that extension services play only a limited role in enhancing rural farmers' knowledge of climate change, as most farmers obtain such information from alternative sources, particularly television, radio, and newspapers, play a significant role in disseminating climate change information, shaping public perceptions, and influencing behavior regarding climate change. The study also discovered that lack of access to agricultural extension services and limited climate change information are significant constraints for smallholder farmers in rural communities, hindering their capacity to adapt to climate change. The study recommended that awareness, knowledge, and skills related to climate change should be strengthened through greater utilization of media within the study area

Additionally, Vu, Baines, and Nguyen (2022) highlighted the rising importance of fact-checking in climate change journalism. Their cross-country study analyzed fact-checked climate claims in the U.S., U.K., Germany, and Australia, focusing on issues such as the existence, causes, effects,

and solutions to climate change. Findings showed that U.S. fact-checks mostly centered on the existence of climate change, while those in Australia, the U.K., and Germany were more concerned with solutions. Importantly, not all fact-checks reached definitive conclusions, and verdicts were not always clear-cut. More falsehoods were identified in U.S. claims, reflecting the polarized political debate around climate change. Politicians were the main sources of disputed claims, particularly in the U.S., where many were found to be false or mostly false. The authors recommended expanding such studies to include more countries with diverse economic and media systems to deepen understanding of global fact-checking practices

Misinformation has become a significant concern in today's society, particularly in the context of climate change. Public misconceptions about climate change can have detrimental effects on the acceptance of its reality and the support for necessary mitigation policies (Cook, Lewandowsky & Ecker, 2017). Cook *et al.*, (2017) study employed an experimental approach to investigate the effectiveness of different strategies in countering misinformation. The study make use of prebunking and inoculation theory experiment by exposing participants to misleading argumentation techniques commonly used in climate change denial. By exposing participants to these techniques and providing them with counter-arguments, the researchers aimed to inoculate them against the influence of misinformation. The findings of the study revealed that the inoculation approach was effective in reducing the influence of misinformation. Participants who were exposed to the misleading argumentation techniques and provided with counter-arguments were less likely to be influenced by subsequent misinformation. This suggests that preemptively addressing and debunking misinformation can help to mitigate its impact on public perception and decision-making.

In their research to investigate the effectiveness of fact-checking warning labels and social endorsement cues in mitigating the influence of fake news, Koch, Frischlich and Lermer (2021) applied the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) to understand the psychological processes underlying individuals' responses to these interventions. The study which employed Heuristic-Systematic Model (HSM) of information processing discovered that adding warning labels from fact checkers to fake news posts, lowered the perceived credibility of a fake news post that exaggerated the effect of climate change. This suggests that warning labels can be effective in countering the influence of fake news on perceived credibility. More findings from the study also establish that warning labels also had a significant effect on participants' self-reported likelihood to amplify fake news. More so, the study found that individuals with left-leaning political views perceived the climate change-related fake news to be more credible. This finding which is consistent with Cook *et al.*, (2017) finding indicates that political ideology can influence the perception of fake news and the effectiveness of interventions. They recommended that warning labels should be complemented with preventive measures that encourage systematic information processing by enhancing users' media literacy and inoculating them against common fake news strategies.

Edet (2024) investigated farmers' engagement with confusing climate change information and the motives driving the dissemination of misinformation within the farming community. The study which was conducted among farmers in Lagos, utilized a mixed-methods approach, including an online survey of 128 members of the Iju Water Works Farmers' Association and semi-structured interviews with 6 farmers, 1 extension agent, and 2 government officials. The findings revealed that misinformation was the most prevalent form of information disorder among the farmers, with 55.4% of instances involving the unintentional spread of inaccurate

information due to uncertainty about its authenticity. The study also identified key factors influencing the spread of misinformation, including trust in information sources, cognitive biases, and social dynamics within the farming community. Major barriers to accurate information dissemination were found to be cognitive failures, such as the lack of consideration of the consequences of sharing misinformation, and social drivers, including the desire to avoid conflict and maintain positive social interactions. The research shows the need for improved communication strategies, fact-checking processes, and collaborative efforts to establish reliable sources and norms for accurate agricultural communication.

The role of partisanship in correcting misinformation on social media platforms was investigated by Jennings and Stroud, 2023. The study found that fact-checking can help correct misperceptions and reshape beliefs, especially when presented in a manner that avoids reinforcing the original misinformation. However, they also noted that motivated reasoning can influence the processing of fact checks when they contradict individuals' existing beliefs. It was also discovered that this situation where people react differently to information based on their political beliefs has big consequences for how false information spreads and gets corrected on platforms like Facebook. The study shows that it is not easy to fix false information when people's political biases affect how they judge and accept information. This therefore emphasizes the importance of using specific strategies to deal with false information that take into account people's political leanings.

In the same vein, Treen, Williams and O'Neill (2020) did a study to explore the phenomenon of misinformation related to climate change on online platforms. They examined the characteristics of climate change misinformation, its spread, and its impact on public perceptions and understanding of climate change. The researchers also analyzed the factors that add to the

dissemination of misinformation, such as echo chambers, algorithmic biases, and the effect of digital platforms. The various forms and sources of misinformation, including false claims, conspiracy theories, and misleading narratives were also looked into. The research revealed that a network of actors is engaged in the funding, production, and dissemination of climate change misinformation, which is subsequently repeated and amplified by the media, politicians, and skeptical bloggers to influence public opinion. They added that Social media networks enable misinformation to propagate rapidly and widely, with the participation of fake accounts which include bots and astroturfers. While the study recommended that educational approaches, inoculation strategies, technological solutions, corrective and collaborative measures, as well as regulatory frameworks, should be part of strategies to counteract misinformation they suggest that further research should focus on the diffusion of climate change misinformation via social media platforms.

In order to examine the prevalence and characteristics of climate change disinformation in Malaysia, Hassan, Musa, Azmi, Abdullah and Yusoff (2023) conducted a content analysis of 124 news articles in selected online newspapers from Malaysia (The Star and New Straits Times) to investigate the types of disinformation, the agents involved in spreading it, and the media platforms where it is disseminated. The study, which analyzed data from newspaper digital archives between August 2015 and October 2021 using the keywords ‘climate change’ and ‘disinformation,’ revealed that disinformation on climate change was more frequently disseminated by politicians, organizations, and anonymous agencies than by business tycoons, celebrities, or academics. This finding is in line with the discovery of Treen *et.al* (2020). Also, the study found that deceptive and fictional contents represent the most common kinds of disinformation spread by politicians with politics and social media representing the most critical

factors influencing climate change. They therefore advocate for collaborative efforts among activists, media practitioners, and governments to curb climate change disinformation.

In their study titled *Why Is Misinformation a Problem*, Adams, Osman, Bechlivanidis and Meder (2023) investigated widespread prevalence of misinformation in the modern digital and look into its speculated causes and effects. This study which examined different disciplines which includes computer science, economics, history, information science, journalism, law, media, politics, philosophy, psychology, and sociology found that misinformation is not a new problem but has intensified in the digital age due to the sheer volume of misinformation generated and disseminated through modern technology. They also discovered that hyper connectivity of the current information and media landscape plays a significant role in the spread of misinformation, leading to shifts in how individuals form their worldviews and perceive truth. The study emphasized the importance of developing more effective strategies to address this problem they recommended that Future research should aim to determine the precise impact of misinformation in specific contexts, such as its potential to establish or significantly strengthen related beliefs and explore the development of tools and strategies to address the problem of misinformation.

One study that has looked into the issue of fake news and misinformation in Nigeria is that of Okocha and Akpe (2022). They seek to explore the implications of fake news and misinformation related to COVID-19 on media credibility in Nigeria. This investigation which focus on the information needs and concerns of Nigerians during the start of the COVID-19 pandemic, examined the prevalence of fake news and misinformation surrounding COVID-19, its impact on public perceptions and trust in the media. Utilizing the framing theory as a theoretical framework and conducting interview with 30 respondents from the six geo political zones of Nigeria, this study noted that although some Nigerians were not personally affected by

fake news or misinformation, they were well aware of its harmful effects on people within their social circles. While concluding that there is a need to enhance the credibility of media content by strengthening professionalism in media practice. and legal control they recommended that further investigation need to be carried out on why Nigerians continue to place trust in the media despite the infiltration of misinformation and the growing influence of fake new.

Hassan, Musa, Azmi, Abdullah and Balogun, (2022) utilized content analysis to explore the strategies used by various agents to deny scientific evidence of climate change. Data was gathered by searching two Malaysian online newspapers over 6 years for disinformation and climate change with a result of 124 relevant articles. The findings shows that politicians, organizations and anonymous sources leverage denial strategies the most compared to scientists, business leaders or celebrities adding that the platforms where disinformation appeared most frequently were social media, broadcasting and digital news. The significant role of political actors in propagating climate falsehoods is was also highlighted, sabotaging climate efforts. This study reveals how multiple agents leverage various influential media to deliberately deny and spread misconceptions regarding climate science.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

2.4.1 Diffusion of innovation

The diffusion of innovation theory, developed by Everett Rogers in the 1960s provides a suitable lens to analyze the way new ideas, practices, or technologies are diffused in a social system over time. An innovation in this model is any idea, method or technology that is considered new or unfamiliar in a community and diffusion is the process by which the knowledge of any innovation is passed on to others in the social system (Rogers, 2003).

The rate and extent of adoption are influenced by the attributes of the innovation, the characteristics of the adopters, and the structure of the social system in which diffusion takes place. The communication channels in this respect, as they are relevant to this research, are the means through which farmers get information on the innovation (Climate Smart Agriculture) and how useful it is to them. It is a combination of mass media and interpersonal communication. The adopters are the farmers that get the information about the innovation of climate-smart agriculture using various communication channels and make the decision whether to adopt and implement the new practices.

Their personal attributes, including their attitude to change, educational level, risk-taking, access to resources and experience, determine how easily they adopt and incorporate the innovation into their farming systems. The social system is the social environment and social structures in which farmers live, their cultural norms, economic systems and networks of relationships. The social system determines the way in which innovations are disseminated via communication channels and whether the emerging ideas and practices are in line with the values, needs, and priorities of the communities. A favorable social system that promotes innovation and collaboration can

hasten the diffusion process whereas a resistant system that promotes tradition and independence can slow down the process of adoption.

Moreover, Rogers also noted that innovations have five perceived attributes, which determine its adoption; relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. Relative advantage is the degree to which an innovation is considered to have more advantages or improvements over current practices or technology. Compatibility is the degree to which an innovation fits the existing technical environment, cultural beliefs and social standards of the people that will use it (Rogers, 2003). Trialability is the capacity of an innovation to be tested without full commitment and with low investment. A more trial-able innovation has more chances of being adopted by people. Lastly, observability is the degree to which the value of a given innovation can be seen by the prospective adopters (Rogers, 2003).

Rogers (2003) further categorised individuals in a social system into five groups in terms of their attitude towards innovation as innovators, early adopters, the early majority, the later majority and laggards. The first group to embrace an innovation are innovators who constitute 2.5 percent of the population within a social system. Rogers (2003) opines that innovators can understand and put into practice complex technical knowledge that is critical in introducing innovation into the social system. The second category are the early adopters who are more integrated in the social system compared to the innovators. They are more knowledgeable about innovation, more networked to new technologies and more economically successful. The two initial adopters groups make up 16 percent of a social system population. The other two groups, representing 68 percent of the population of the social system are early and late majority adopters. The remaining 16 percent of the people in the social system are referred to as laggards. They are the most resistant to the introduction of an innovation and more so, they are likely to become non-adopters

due to their inadequate resources and ignorance or lack of knowledge of the innovation (Rogers, 2003). According to the theory of Rogers (2003), a social system is defined as a group of interrelated units, which are involved in solving a problem together in order to achieve a shared objective. It is a system in which diffusion of innovations occurs. According to Rogers, the attitude of the individuals towards innovation and, in turn, the rate of innovations adoption, are influenced by the structure of a social system.

Moreover, the theory acknowledges the presence of barriers and challenges to the adoption of innovations. It recognises that resistance to change, uncertainty, and cultural factors can impede the diffusion of innovations within a social system. Overcoming these barriers is essential for the successful adoption and widespread diffusion of innovations (Bakkabulindi, 2014).

2.4.2 Justification of the theory to the study

This theory has been applied to various fields, including the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices. Studies have shown that the adoption of innovations, such as climate-smart agricultural practices, is influenced by factors such as demand, supplier promotion and socioeconomic determinants (Lapsley & Wright, 2004; Tiarniyu *et al.*, 2018; Mishra *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, the adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices is significantly determined by the adaptive capacity of farm households, including human, physical, natural, financial, and social capacity (Sardar *et al.*, 2019).

The diffusion of innovation theory provides a framework to examine how misinformation, malinformation and disinformation can distort the process of climate-smart agriculture adoption, as it explains the role accurate information exchange plays in shaping farmers' perceptions and adoption decisions regarding new agricultural practices. Key concepts like communication

channels, attributes of innovation, adopter characteristics, and the social system will help explain the sources of information disorder and how information and new ideas permeate through the farming community. Also, the knowledge and persuasion stages of the adoption process are critical junctures where information disorders, such as misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation, could impede further diffusion by distorting farmers' understanding and attitudes towards climate-smart techniques.

Determining farmers' knowledge and understanding of information disorder relates directly to the knowledge stage of the innovation-decision process. This implies that exposure to information disorder may act as an obstacle that inhibits the uptake of innovative practices. Analysing these effects can uncover barriers impeding wider climate-smart agriculture diffusion. Our objectives of determining farmers' knowledge, identifying misinformation sources, and examining misinformation's influence on climate smart practice adoption directly align with diffusion theory concepts involving the innovation-decision process, communication channels, and information exchange. Analysing these dynamics through the diffusion theory lens will uncover critical barriers, sources, and impacts of information disorder stalling climate-smart agriculture diffusion.

Overall, diffusion of innovation gives a valuable theoretical foundation and practical tools to study the specific challenge of information disorder hindering climate smart agriculture adoption and derive targeted solutions for enabling farmers to access and apply validated climate smart agriculture information.

2.4.3 Inoculation Theory

Inoculation theory is a prominent communication theory that has gained attention in the context of countering misinformation, including climate change. The theory which is a persuasive communication theory developed by social psychologist William J. McGuire in the 1960s, offers an approach to counteracting information disorder and resistance to persuasion. Inoculation theory is based on the concept of using weakened forms of misinformation to build resistance to it, similar to how a vaccine works. The theory draws on a medical analogy, suggesting that by preemptively exposing individuals to weakened doses of misinformation, cognitive immunity can be developed (Basol, Roozenbeek, and Linden, 2020). This approach involves presenting and refuting existing or anticipated persuasive arguments against a particular belief before or after individuals are exposed to misinformation (Ramirez, Despres, Chalela, Weis, Sukumaran, Munoz and McAlister, 2022).

According to Cook, Ellerton and Kinkead (2018), the core premise of inoculation theory is to provide individuals with a form of cognitive resistance against persuasive misinformation. The theory further posits that individuals can be inoculated against persuasive attacks by preemptively exposing them to weakened forms of the arguments they are likely to encounter, thereby strengthening their resistance to subsequent persuasive attempts. It has been suggested that inoculation theory can be applied not only to specific instances of misinformation but also to the techniques and strategies commonly used to mislead or misinform individuals (Roozenbeek, Traberg and Linden, 2022). Furthermore, the theory has been found to confer resistance to persuasion and has been considered a consistent and reliable method for achieving this goal (Miller, Ivanov, Sims, Compton, Harrison, Parker and Averbek, 2012).

As Cook *et al.* (2017) opine, there are two elements to inoculation: an explicit warning of an impending threat and a refutation of an anticipated argument that exposes the imminent fallacy. For instance, in the context of climate change scepticism, an inoculation might involve alerting individuals to the existence of efforts aimed at casting doubt on the established scientific consensus. This proactive exposure to false information serves to deliver the misinformation in a debilitated form. Consequently, when individuals subsequently encounter a deceptive argument, the inoculation functions as a cognitive shield, furnishing them with a readily available counterargument to promptly dismiss the misinformation.

2.4.4 Justification of the theory to the study

The effectiveness of inoculation against information disorder in climate change has been supported by several studies. Cook *et al.* (2017) conducted an experiment that looked at misinformation in the form of ‘false balance’ media coverage, which misinforms by conveying the impression of evenly balanced discourse in the scientific community regarding climate change. The study shows the efficacy of inoculation theory in neutralising misinformation by exposing misleading arguments, thereby reducing their influence. Additionally, Treen, Williams and O’Neill’s (2020) study found that proactively cautioning people about politically driven attempts to spread misinformation helps to advancing and safeguarding public attitudes about the scientific consensus on climate change. Furthermore, recent research by Linden, Leiserowitz, Rosenthal and Maibach (2017) suggests that political polarisation on climate change is more likely the result of selective exposure to partisan media than motivated reasoning alone. The result of this study also reveals the importance of inoculation theory in countering misinformation, as it addresses the role of media exposure in shaping individuals’ perceptions of climate change.

Perhaps inoculation theory's application in this study is relevant given the prevalence of information disorder and the urgent need to enhance public understanding of climate science. Inoculation theory provides a useful framework for the study's objectives, including investigating how farmers fact-check information and understanding the challenges they face in detecting misinformation. By identifying common climate smart agriculture information disorder narratives among the farmers and equipping farmers to refute misinformation claims, inoculative techniques can potentially curb the influence of information disorder on climate smart agriculture adoption. Achieving these objectives will be helpful in understanding how targeted inoculation messages through agricultural extension services could empower farmers to make informed decisions, thereby strengthening climate resilience and adaptation.

2.4.5 The Global Village Theory

Global Village theory is the brainchild of the work by Marshall McLuhan (1964) in *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man*, in which he suggested that the world was becoming a global village due to electronic communication. McLuhan believed that the introduction of new media technologies, particularly those that cross geographical boundaries, time and space is compressed, and therefore, individuals in remote areas can communicate like they were in the same locality. In the global village, communication is instant and bi-directional and societies are characterized by a new social organization and awareness that is created through the technology (McLuhan, 1964).

The theory stresses that communication technologies are not the means of relaying information only, but they determine the manner in which human beings perceive, experience and act upon the surrounding world. Carey (1989) also developed this idea by suggesting that media

technologies brought about a shared symbolic space, in which events taking place in the world are made local experiences, producing a sense of coevalness among people all over the world.

In the modern world, digital media and mobile access has transformed the global village. International interdependence has been further enhanced by the Internet, social media and mobile phones, which have changed local information systems into globally connected communication systems. This interconnectedness is, however, coupled with the rise of new types of information disorder such as misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation because messages are now freely circulated through unverified sources. Castells (2009) argues that this networked society has provided a dual reality: on the one hand, it has democratized the access to information; on the other hand, it has increased the amount of unverified content and undermined the traditional gatekeeping functions.

In communication perspective, the global village concept brings into focus the conflict of connection and confusion. On the one hand, it enables smallholder farmers to acquire a wide range of agricultural knowledge and innovations that are not limited to their communities. Conversely, it subjects them to misinformation around the world, which may mislead local perception of climate-smart agriculture (CSA). The theory, thus, highlights the revolutionary but destabilizing role of digital connectivity in the construction of agricultural communication landscapes.

2.4.6 Justification of the theory to the study

The Global Village theory is very applicable in the study since it is a theory that will help explain how digital communication technologies influence the access and understanding of climate-smart agricultural (CSA) information by farmers in Oyo State. WhatsApp groups, radio-enabled online

programmes, social media platforms, and mobile phones are all drawing farmers into a global networked communication space in which local and international agricultural information collide. This is in line with the vision of the global village by McLuhan (1964), where people, irrespective of their location, become a part of a common informational space.

In this globalized communication arena, the distinction between checked agricultural information and deceptive information is obscured. The flow of digital farming advice, some of which may be credible, such as FAO or research organizations, and others may be unverified by online users, generates an information disorder that makes it difficult to distinguish between genuine CSA messages and fake ones in farmers. The network society as Castells (2009) elaborates, enhances the strength of connectivity and dilutes the control over the accuracy of information. Therefore, the availability of a variety of information sources, both reliable and not, to the farmers is an example of how the global village makes the coexistence of enlightenment and confusion possible.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter is concerned with the methods employed to gather data for the study. It is essential for any research to use appropriate techniques to collect data, ensuring that findings are based on well-defined gaps and research questions. This aligns with the view of Silverman (2013), who emphasized that research methodology is the structured approach through which researchers seek to answer specific research questions. Therefore, this chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the methodology utilized to collect key information necessary to achieve the aim and objectives of the study. It discusses the research design, the study population, data collection instruments, sample size, validation of instruments, and method of data analysis.

3.2 Research Design

This study employed an exploratory sequential mixed-method research design to examine information disorder among Oyo State farmers and its influence on the adoption of Climate-Smart Agriculture through qualitative and quantitative research methods. Sequential exploratory mixed-method research design is an approach that begins with qualitative data collection, followed by a quantitative phase to test or generalize the findings. This design is useful when researchers need to develop instruments, identify variables, or refine research questions before conducting a broader quantitative study (Creswell & Clark, 2017; Berman, 2017; Katz-Buonincontro, 2024; Shiyabola *et al.*, 2021). At the first phase, this study conducted in-depth interviews with extension officers and then went on to utilize survey questionnaire to gather quantitative data while additional in-depth interviews were conducted with selected farmers in

each farm settlements. The survey questionnaire were informed by the responses obtained from the in-depth interviews with the extension officers.

3.3 Population

The population for this study covered practicing farmers in Oyo state. This include livestock, crop and fish farmers. Oyo state is known predominantly to be popular for the production of crops and livestock (Oyegbami, 2018). According to Oxford business group data (2017), Oyo state ranks as the 12th-largest producer of crops and the 15th-largest producer of livestock in the country. In 2016, agriculture accounted for 24.4% of the state's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), with crop production comprising 90% of this output. In Ashley-Dejo, *et al.* (2016) study, Oyo state was divided into four agricultural zones namely Ibadan/Ibarapa, Ogbomoso, Oyo and Saki under which we have all the farm settlements recognized by the Oyo state government. All these farm settlements have the reach of the official agricultural extension agency of Oyo state government known as OYSADEP (Oyo State Agricultural Development Programme). These include Ipapo, Ilora, Eruwa, Ogbomoso, Iresaadu, fashola, Akufo, Lalupon, Iseyin and Ijaiye.

Out of all these farm settlements, Eruwa, Akufo, Ijaye and Ogbomosho were purposively selected due to the intensity of farming/agricultural activity going on in these zones and the adoption of the National Fadama Development Project (NFDP) by the farmers in the area. The population also included agricultural extension officers from OYSADEP (Oyo State Agricultural Development Programme).

The population data of farmers in the selected farm settlements as gotten from OYSADEP is as follow:

FARM SETTLEMENT	FARMERS POPULATION
Akufo	235
Eruwa	200
Ijaye	500
Ogbomosho	179
Total	1114

3.4 Sampling Procedure

3.4.1 Stratified Sampling within Farm Settlements

Within each selected farm settlement, the farmers were divided into strata based on the type of farming they engage in, such as crop farming, livestock farming, and fishery. The identification of these strata was facilitated by referencing the list of different commodity members obtained from the association of settlers in the farm settlements.

3.4.2 Proportional Allocation of Sample Size

The sample size of 294 was proportionally allocated to each farm settlement based on their respective population sizes. Below is the calculations:

Total Population = 1114

Total sample size = 294

- Akufo - $(235/1114) \times 294 = 62$ respondents
- Eruwa - $(200/1114) \times 294 = 53$ respondents
- Ijaye - $(500/1114) \times 294 = 132$ respondents
- Ogbomosho – $(179/1114) \times 294 = 47$ respondents

3.4.3 Sampling for the questionnaire

From the proportionally allocated sample size for each farm settlement, a purposive sampling technique was employed to select farmers for the questionnaire. The following criteria were used to identify the suitable respondents:

- a. Years of farming experience
- b. Farm size
- c. Engagement in the Fadama project
- d. Recommendations from farm executives

With the help of the above criteria, participants were purposively selected from each stratum within each farm settlement to serve as respondents in the questionnaire. The purposive sampling process continued until the required number of farmers were selected according to the number of allotted respondent in each settlement.

For the in-depth interview, 10 percent of allotted respondent farmers were purposively selected to participate in each farm settlements. The following was the number of respondent selected for in-depth interview in each farm settlement.

In-depth Interview Respondent Selection by Farm Settlement

FARM SETTLEMENT	RESPONDENTS	10% OF RESPONDENTS
Akufo	62	6
Eruwa	53	5
Ijaye	132	13
Ogbomosho	47	5
Total	294	29

From each of the strata, opinion leaders were selected based on their leadership role, experience, credibility, and years of engagement in farming to answer questions relating to information disorder and adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices in Oyo State. Moreover, an in-depth interview was also conducted with four agricultural extension officers assigned to each of these farm settlements from the Oyo State Agricultural Development Program (OYSADEP).

3.5 Sample Size

To determine an appropriate sample size from a known population, the Taro Yamane formula provides a simple and reliable technique. This formula was introduced by Taro Yamane in 1967 as a simplified method to calculate reasonable sample sizes required for a given margin of error and confidence level when conducting research. As Yamane himself demonstrated, his formula allows calculation of an ideal sample that is large enough to be representative of the population and ensure a certain acceptable level of sampling error. Therefore from the known total of one thousand, one hundred and fourteen (1114) population of farmers in the four selected farm settlements, the following sample size will be determined:

Using the Taro Yamane formula to calculate the sample size (n)

$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size

e = margin of error

Therefore

N = population size (1114)

e = margin of error (0.05)

$$n = 1114 / (1 + 1114(0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 1114 / (1 + 1114(0.0025))$$

$$n = 1114 / (1 + 2.785)$$

$$n = 1114 / 3.785$$

$$n = 294$$

Therefore, the required sample size for the population of 1114 with a 5% margin of error is 294.

3.6 Research instruments

The data collection for this study was carried out using two research instruments and these are: questionnaire and in-depth interview guide.

3.6.1 In-depth interview guide

This study aims to examine the issue of information disorder as it relates to climate smart agriculture (CSA) in Oyo State, Nigeria. In-depth interview was conducted with agricultural extension officers from the Oyo State Agricultural Development Program (OYSADEP) and with farmers from identified strata (crop, livestock, and fishery) in four purposively selected farm

settlements. The data gotten from the extension officers further informed the development of the questionnaire and in-depth interview for the farmers.

In-depth interview with Extension Officers

At the first phase of data gathering for this study, in-depth interview was conducted with agricultural extension officers who work with the Oyo state government and have been assigned to each of these farm settlements (Eruwa, Ijaye, Akufo and Ogbomosho). The in-depth interview guide for extension officers was structured into five sections, each designed to explore key aspects of information disorder in climate-smart agriculture (CSA) in Oyo State. Extension agents have been identified in studies as the most utilised source of information for farmers in Nigeria (Suleiman *et al.*, 2021; Ajayi, Alabi, & Akinsola, 2013). The interview guide is structured around the five main research questions, each focusing on a specific aspect of information disorder in climate-smart agriculture.

The first section examined extension officers' understanding of information disorder, including their experiences with misleading agricultural information and farmers' awareness of the issue. The second section focused on sources of misinformation, identifying the channels through which farmers obtain CSA information and whether certain communication channel or individual frequently spread false content. The third section was to answer the impact of information disorder on CSA practices, assessing how misinformation influences farmers' decisions and whether it has led to changes in farming techniques or resistance to the adoption of CSA innovations. The fourth section investigates fact-checking mechanisms. Examine how farmers verify CSA information and the barriers they face in distinguishing credible sources from misinformation.

The final section addresses the challenges farmers encounter in verifying CSA information. It aims to understand how misinformation affects their adoption. Based on the findings from the interviews with extension officers, the researcher was able to refine and finalize the interview questions for the farmers. The qualitative responses from the extension officers guided the adjustments needed to ensure that the questions for farmers address key issues identified in the first phase.

In-depth interview with Farmers

In order to get deeper understanding of the issue of information disorder, in-depth interview was also carried out with farmers. This guide for farmers was structured to look into the farmer's knowledge, awareness, sources, fact-checking mechanisms, and challenges related to information disorder in climate-smart agriculture (CSA) in Oyo State. It consists of five sections, each addressing key aspects of how farmers receive, interpret, and act on CSA information.

The first section examined farmers' knowledge of information disorder, assessing their understanding of misleading agricultural information and whether they can identify false or unreliable sources. The second section focused on sources of CSA misinformation, exploring where farmers typically obtain agricultural information and whether they have encountered misleading content from extension officers, social media, fellow farmers, or conventional media.

The third section explored the impact of information disorder on farming practices, analyzing how misinformation affects decision-making and whether it has led to changes in farming techniques, input choices, or resistance to CSA innovations. The fourth section investigates fact-checking mechanisms, examining how farmers verify Climate smart agricultural information and whether they use experts, multiple sources, or indigenous knowledge to confirm its accuracy.

The final section addressed challenges in verifying CSA information, identifying barriers such as limited access to credible sources, low literacy levels, and conflicting messages from various communication channels. Additionally, the guide includes a list of CSA practices—such as drought-resistant crops, conservation tillage, rotational grazing, and renewable energy use—to understand if farmers are aware of these CSA practices.

As stated earlier, 10 percent of the sampled respondent farmers were purposively selected to participate in each farm settlements. They were interviewed by the researcher to get in-depth understanding from their perspective of issues that relate with information disorder in the adoption and practice of climate smart agriculture in Oyo state. This process was carried out after questionnaire had been conducted with some farmers who are representative of the groups in each starta.

3.6.2 Questionnaire

The questionnaire has both open and closed ended questions to get responses from members of the selected categories of farming (e.g Crop, Livestock and fishery) in the four purposively selected farm settlements in Oyo State: Eruwa, Akufo, Ijaiye and Ogbomoso. It was structured to examine farmers' awareness, sources, influences, fact-checking mechanisms, and challenges related to information disorder in climate-smart agriculture (CSA) in Oyo State. This instrument consists of six sections, each designed to assess farmers' experiences and decision-making processes regarding CSA information.

The first section covers demographic information, including age, gender, education level, farm size, years of experience, and farm settlement location. The second section assessed farmers' knowledge of CSA and information disorder, asking them to describe their understanding of

CSA and whether they have encountered misleading agricultural information. The third section focused on sources of CSA information to find out whether farmers rely on extension officers, traditional media sources, social media, or agricultural institutions and how trustworthy they perceive these sources to be. The fourth section examined the impact of misinformation on their farming practices, assessing whether misleading information has influenced decision-making, discouraged CSA adoption, or led to ineffective farming practice.

The fifth section investigates fact-checking mechanisms, exploring how farmers verify CSA-related information through experts, personal experience, or media sources, and assessing their challenges in accessing reliable information. The final section identifies barriers to accurate information verification, including limited access to experts, language barriers, and misinformation from fellow farmers, and conflicting information from different sources.

3.7 Method of Data Collection

Data for this study was collected by the researcher with the help of four trained research assistants. The researcher obtained a letter of introduction from the Faculty of Media and Communication Studies to the Oyo State Ministry of agriculture. Thereafter permission was obtained from the Director of extension services through the Commissioner for Agriculture to carry out this study in the four purposively selected farm settlements. This approval gave access to the extension officers who helped in contacting the Settler's Association heads in each of the selected farm settlements. The researcher conducted the In-depth interview with the four extension officers by himself and after this, permission was obtained to conduct in-depth interview and get responses with the questionnaire at the four farm settlements.

After responses were received from the in-depth interviews conducted with the four extension officers, they were used as a guide to refine the in-depth interview and questionnaire for farmers to ensure that the questions were contextually relevant, addressed key issues identified by the extension officers, and captured farmers' real-life experiences with information disorder in climate-smart agriculture.

The questionnaire was translated into Yoruba language for easy understanding. Data collection was done by the researcher and four trained research assistants, with the support of extension officers, who facilitated our meeting with the farmers' association executives in the four selected farm settlements (Eruwa, Akufo, Ijaiye, and Ogbomoso). To ensure a sizable number of respondents, the interviews were conducted during the farmers' monthly meeting days, when most members were present. The research assistants assisted in administering the questionnaire. They helped farmers understand the questions and explain to elicit the right answers.

At Ijaiye, where the number of respondents was higher than all other farm settlements, the researcher found it difficult to administer the questionnaires in one sitting. To address this, the extension officer assisted by taking the researcher to the farms of the farmers, to ensure that the require number of respondents were captured.

The in-depth interviews were conducted by the researcher, alongside the extension officers, who helped explain the purpose of the study and encourage farmers to provide honest responses. Some farmers were reluctant to participate due to the length and detail of the questions, as well as the time required to complete the interview. However, with the extension officers' persuasion and reassurance, the farmers eventually agreed to participate. All in-depth interview sessions were recorded with the consent of the participants and later transcribed for analysis.

3.8 Data Analysis

Data collected from the multiple choice questions in the questionnaire were analysed quantitatively using appropriate statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies and percentages, are computed to summarize the demographic characteristics of the respondents, sources of CSA information disorder, influence of information disorder on adoption of CSA and fact checking mechanism used to verify CSA information. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to also examine the influence of climate smart-Agriculture information on the farmers in Oyo State. The qualitative data from the in-depth interview with extension officers and with selected farmers were transcribed and used to backup claims from the questionnaire. Also, descriptive statistics was deployed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) 20.0 edition.

Moreover, open ended questions of CSA knowledge and understanding among the farmers were analyzed using NVivo following a four-step process: (1) Data preparation and importation, where responses were organized ; (2) Coding and categorization, where responses were systematically coded into themes and sub-themes based on both predefined and emerging categories; (3) Analysis of themes and patterns, using matrix coding queries and word frequency analysis to identify dominant trends; and (4) Interpretation and synthesis. The results were presented in a table format, summarizing the key themes, coding frequencies, and representative definitions from farmers to illustrate their perspectives.

3.9 Validity

Validity ensures that research instruments measure what they are designed to measure. First, the questionnaire and in-depth interview guides for both farmers and extension officers were

subjected to review by the researcher's supervisor and experts in agricultural extension and rural development. Their evaluation focused on the clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of the items in relation to the study's objectives, leading to adjustments that enhanced both content and face validity.

3.10 Reliability

Reliability refers to the consistency and stability of research instruments in producing dependable results when applied under similar conditions. To ensure reliability, the instruments in this study (questionnaire and in-depth interview guides) were carefully pre-tested on a small sample of farmers. This pilot exercise helped to identify ambiguous items, refine question wording, and confirm that the instruments would yield consistent responses.

3.11 Methodological Challenges

One key difficulty was obtaining accurate responses from farmers, as some were initially hesitant to share information due to mistrust or repeated surveys by different agencies survey. This was minimized by building rapport through the extension officers and farm executives. In addition, differences in literacy and language required translation into local dialects in some cases, which sometimes slowed data gathering. Finally the farmer's busy schedule also caused delays. The extension officers had to in some cases take the researcher to meet the farmers on their farms.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter provides answers to the five research questions put forward to study incidences of information disorder and its influence in the adoption of climate smart agriculture among farmers in the four purposively selected farm settlements in Oyo state. The data gathered through questionnaire, in-depth interview with the extension officers and in-depth interview with selected farmers were quantitatively and qualitatively analysed.

In order to ensure accuracy of the data collected and inputted into SPSS 20.0, data cleaning and screening were done. Data were cleaned by running frequencies of all variables. Data were screened to attain the acceptable multi colinearity level. A total of 294 copies of questionnaire were distributed in the four selected farm settlements (Ogbomoso, Ijaye, Akufo and Eruwa) and 271 which represents 92% were retrieved which were used to answer the research questions.

4.2 Demographic Analysis

Table 4.1 Socio-Demographic Attributes of Respondents

Socio-demographic Variables	Survey Sample % (n)
Gender	
Male	74.5% (202)
Female	25.5% (69)
Age (Years)	
18-25	5.9% (16)
26-35	10.0% (27)
36-45	24.7% (67)
46-55	16.6% (45)
56-65	37.6% (102)

66 and above	5.2% (14)
Education Level	
No formal education	26.2% (71)
Primary	24.4% (66)
Secondary	21.4% (58)
Tertiary	28.1% (76)
Farm Size	
1-5 Acres	35.1% (95)
6-10 Acres	27.3% (74)
11-15 Acres	19.9 % (54)
16-above Acres	17.7% (48)
Type of Farming	
Food Crop	33.6% (91)
Cash Crop	34.7% (94)
Livestock	10.0% (27)
Livestock and Crop	12.2% (33)
Fishery	9.6% (26)
Year of Experience	
1-5 years	8.1% (22)
6-10 years	64.9% (176)
11-15 years	22.5% (61)
16-20 years	4.4% (12)

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

This socio-demographic attributes of respondents gives deeper understanding of the characteristics of the population of the study. These attributes, including gender, age, education level, farm size, type of farming, and years of experience, form the basis for understanding the context and variables that may influence the outcomes of the study (Table 4.1). In this analysis, we will explore the socio-demographic profile of the respondents based on the provided data and draw inferences about them.

The gender distribution of respondents shows a pronounced skew toward male participants in Table 4.1. Of the total respondents, 74.5% (202 individuals) were male, while 25.5% (69 individuals) were female. This disparity in gender representation is often seen in rural agricultural area, where men typically dominate in the management and ownership of farms,

particularly in developing countries. It also aligns with the findings of Oyedele (2018) where male farmers dominate the female. According to him, this may confirm the existing cultural belief that agriculture is an occupation for men.

Age is another crucial factor that influences the farming practices and the socio-economic activities of respondents. The age distribution reveals a predominantly older group of individuals, with the largest segment of respondents (37.6%, n=102) falling within the age group of 56-65 years. This is followed by 24.7% (67 respondents) in the 36-45 years age bracket. The relatively low percentage of younger farmers (5.9%, n=16 for 18-25 years) may reflect the challenges young people face in engaging in agriculture, such as limited access to land, finance, and training (FAO, 2017). However, most of the respondents are within the productive age of bracket (18 to 54= 57%).

The educational level of the respondents reflects a significant portion of the sample with no formal education. A total of 26.2% (71 respondents) reported having no formal education, while 24.4% (66 respondents) completed primary education, and 21.4% (58 respondents) attained secondary education. Surprisingly, 28.1% (76 respondents) of the sample had tertiary education. The fact that 73.8% of respondents have some level of formal education suggests majority of the farmers are somewhat equipped to understand and process information about climate-smart agricultural practices.

The farm size of respondents is a significant indicator of the farming system and the scale of agricultural activities. 35.1% (95 respondents) of the sample have access to between 1 and 5 acres, while 27.3% (74 respondents) had farm sizes ranging from 6 to 10 acres. As discovered in the farm settlements, livestock farmers have allocations of land ranging from 1 to 5 acres while

crop farmers are entitled to farm land above 6 acres. This distribution reflects the agricultural land use pattern in Oyo State farm settlements, where crop farming dominates in terms of land allocation. The data shows that approximately 64.9% of respondents (176 farmers) operate farms larger than 5 acres, which may primarily be crop farmers. According to Thomas and Sanyaolu (2016), Oyo State is one of the leading producers of food crops in Southwestern Nigeria with major production of cassava, maize, yam, and various vegetables, with crop production accounting for over 70% of agricultural activities in the region.

The type of farming the farmers engage in further supports the above distribution pattern, showing that crop farming (both food and cash crops combined) accounts for 68.3% (185 respondents) of the agricultural activities. Specifically, 33.6% (91 respondents) are engaged in food crop production and 34.7% (94 respondents) in cash crop production. However, 12.2% (33 respondents) also engage in both crop and livestock farming, while 10.0% (27 respondents) engage in livestock farming, and 9.6% (26 respondents) are involved in fishery farming.

Experience plays a crucial role in shaping the knowledge and practices of farmers. Majority of the respondents (64.9%, n=176) had between 6 to 10 years of farming experience, followed by 22.5% (61 respondents) with 11 to 15 years of experience. A smaller proportion, 8.1% (22 respondents), had 1 to 5 years of experience, and only 4.4% (12 respondents) had 16 to 20 years of farming experience. The predominance of respondents with 6 to 10 years of experience suggests that most farmers have accumulated some practical knowledge and skills but may still be in the process of mastering advanced farming techniques or managing larger-scale operations. The lack of extremely experienced farmers in the sample could point to the aging population of

farmers, as older farmers (over 55 years) may retire or scale down their operations, leaving behind those with intermediate experience.

4.3 Answer to Research Questions

4.3.1 Understanding and Knowledge of Oyo State farmers about climate-smart agriculture information disorder

Table 4.2: Farmers' Knowledge and Understanding of Climate-Smart Agriculture Information Disorder

SN	Level of Understanding	Ogbomoso	%	Ijaiye	%	Akufo	%	Eruwa	%
1	Detailed Understanding	20	45.3	48	40.0	20	35.1	19	38.0
2	Basic Awareness	15	34.3	28	23.3	24	41.9	23	47.0
3	Unfamiliar	9	20.4	38	31.7	13	23.0	8	15.0
Total		44	100	120	100	57	100	50	100

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

In Ogbomoso, the majority of farmers (45.3%) reported having a detailed understanding of CSA information disorder, suggesting that they have a strong grasp of the subject. Only 20.4% of farmers were unfamiliar, while 34.3% had basic awareness. This indicates that a substantial proportion of the farmers in Ogbomoso have a good knowledge of what inaccurate information about CSA constitute, with fewer being unfamiliar with or only having basic knowledge of the subject. In Ijaiye, 40.0% of farmers reported a detailed understanding of CSA, while 28.3% have basic awareness. Only 31.7% of respondents were unfamiliar.

Akufo also had 35.1% of farmers reporting a detailed understanding of CSA information disorder, while 41.9% had basic awareness. Only 23.0% of farmers were unfamiliar. This indicates that although a significant portion of farmers in Akufo have a basic awareness of CSA,

a good number also have a more detailed understanding, highlighting the effectiveness of educational interventions in this region. In Eruwa, 38.0% of farmers reported a detailed understanding of CSA information disorder, while 47.0% had basic awareness. Only 15.0% were unfamiliar. Across all four farm settlements, the trend indicates that a good proportion of farmers have a detailed understanding of CSA information disorder, though the level of awareness still varies.

The ANOVA results ($F = 6.57, p < 0.05$) indicated that there are statistically significant differences in the levels of understanding of CSA among farmers in the four farm settlements. This supports the observation that knowledge and awareness of CSA vary across regions, with some areas having a higher proportion of farmers showing detailed understanding or basic awareness, while others remain unfamiliar with CSA practices. These findings highlight the need for continued efforts to improve CSA knowledge and ensure that farmers in all areas have access to essential climate-smart information.

4.3.2 Thematic Analysis of Farmers' Knowledge and Understanding of Climate-Smart Agriculture Information Disorder

Table 4.3 Thematic Analysis of Farmers' Knowledge and Understanding of Climate-Smart Agriculture Information Disorder

Theme	Definition by Farmers	Akufo	Eruwa	Ijaye	Ogbomoso	Total (n=271)	Percentage (%)
Misleading Agricultural Products	Exaggerated claims about seed varieties, fertilizers, or pesticides	15	14	31	11	71	26.2%
Inaccurate	Incorrect or	18	15	38	12	83	30.6%

Weather Forecasts	misunderstood weather predictions (e.g., NIMET forecasts)						
Incorrect Agricultural Advice	False or misleading farming practices (e.g., planting schedules, planting spacing, pesticide use, misapplication of inputs)	10	10	28	9	57	21.0%
Government Unfulfilled Promises	Failed agricultural programs, subsidy delays, or unfulfilled policy commitments	14	11	22	12	59	21.8%

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

From the analysis of the in-depth interview and questionnaire open ended responses, farmers in all selected farm settlements (Ijaye, Akufo, Ogbomosho, and Eruwa) demonstrated a considerable level of awareness of most of the CSA practices, such as drought-resistant crop varieties, crop rotation, intercropping, irrigation, and organic soil improvement, as evidenced by their responses in interviews and ticked practices in the questionnaire. It was clear that the percentage of knowledge and usage of CSA practices correlates well with the practices that are well-known and widely used in each settlement.

For instance in Ijaye, farmers are well known in this location for irrigation farming as well as in Eruwa. This was discovered in the high number of farmers who signified to the knowledge of this practice unlike Akufo and Ogbomosho where crop farming is the major practice. This

suggest that there is a widespread awareness of CSA practices in these areas. This findings is in consonance with Ifeanyi-obi *et al.*'s (2023) observation that crop farmers in southern Nigeria recognized and adapted to climate change using practices shaped by their environment and knowledge.

However, knowledge and understanding of CSA information disorder varies among the farmers across the farm settlements. When the farmers were asked what their understanding of CSA information disorder is, they presented different interpretations of the term and this may be based on the experiences they have had in the past or exposure. Some farmers described it as when the information given about farming is not correct, some say it is when they see or buy fake agricultural products on the internet while other refer to it as unfulfilled government promises.

Table 4.3 shows that, one of the most common themes across the farm settlements was the issue of Inaccurate Weather Forecasts, which 30.6% (83 respondents) of farmers identified as a major concern. Farmers, in Ijaiye, Ogbomosho, Akufo and Eruwa pointed to discrepancies between weather predictions and actual rainfall, which disrupted their planting and harvesting schedules. Most maize farmers complained that the failed weather forecast made them to experience financial loss during the period. For instance a farmer at Eruwa farm settlement noted

Last year when Nimet told us that rain will fall till the end of November, many of us did late planting of maize but all of a sudden rain stopped mid-November and most of our crops suffered from drought. We lost money as a result of this (In-depth interview-2024).

This finding is in alignment with the finding of Oyedele (2018) where it was discovered that some of the forecast about weather especially on rain sometimes fail as confirmed by the farmers. Further elaboration from the extension officers shows that the farmers were misled as a

result of misinterpretation of Nimet weather information of extended rain till November 2024.

According to the Ogbomosho extension officer

It is true they got weather information that rain will last till November, 2024 ending but sometimes our farmers do not pay attention to details. Nimet did not say that the rain will fall everywhere. The rain fell in some locations that are not closer to this place but because what they have heard did not happen as they want, they will say it is incorrect information. (In-depth interview-2024).

Perhaps, the above information shows that there is a gap in the ability of the farmers to contextualize and understand weather forecasts, which revealed one of the challenge of information disorder, where incomplete understanding or miscommunication of scientific data can mislead farmers, thereby affecting their planning and adaptation strategies. Moreover, it shows the vital role the extension officers have to play in bridging the gap of incomplete information by ensuring that information are clarified and understood by the farmers

Misleading agricultural products are a major concern among the farmers, with the highest number of affected farmers in Ijaye (48.1%), followed by Akufo (34.0%), Eruwa (29.8%), and Ogbomosho (21.3%). Farmers in all settlements confirmed that they usually encounter exaggerated claims about improved seed varieties, fertilizers, and pesticides, with cases of fraudulent agricultural products being most common in Ijaye and Akufo. In Akufo, 66.7% of farmers specifically show their understanding of information disorder from the perspective of deceptive advertisements for high-yielding maize varieties, while in Ijaye, 57.5% confirmed they did not perform as promised. This was noted by a farmers from Akufo farm settlement,

There was a time i saw an advertisement of a maize seedling which produces up to 5 cobs of maize at harvest. We have the popular maize that we plant here especially premier seedling but this one was attractive. After I tried to verify the maize by showing the information to a fellow farmers he said it is not true. I also confirmed it from some other farmers in our midst who confirmed that it is not a real maize variety. (In-depth interview-2024)

Similar experiences were also reported by farmers in other farm settlements. Farmers at ijaye mentioned that they have bought a tomato seedling which they got to know through radio advertisement and did not bring the expected result at harvest as advertised. Likewise in Eruwas, farmers explained information disorder in terms of fake agricultural input that was given to them by the government. This shows that farmers are very much aware of information disorder in the agri-food sector but the identification of misinformation varies based on experiences and exposure to information.

Another theme recognized from farmer's responses is incorrect agricultural advice. This theme includes misleading or false farming practices such as improper planting schedules, wrong spacing advice and pesticide use, was mentioned by 21.0% of farmers. For instance, a farmer from Akufo shared his experience with usage of vaccine

I wanted to use vaccine for my birds and I heard from a fellow farmer that I can add milk and honey to the vaccine so as to increase its motility. I decided to confirm this from the internet. I already know about the use of milk to increase vaccine motility but that of adding honey is a misleading information. (In-depth interview-2024).

The above revelation shows the role of farmer to farmer information exchange, where farmers rely on information from their fellow farmers. While this can be useful, the spread of incorrect information is inevitable.

In addition to this, when asked about their understanding of information disorder a substantial number of the respondents (21.8%) described it as unfulfilled government promises, particularly relating to agricultural programs, subsidies, loans or policy commitments that were not met. Farmers in Eruwa and Ogbomosho lamented that promised subsidies and support programs never materialized, leaving them financially vulnerable. One respondent noted the disappointment

when government initiatives, such as subsidies on fertilizers, failed to arrive in time for planting.

One of the farmers noted

Government has promised us farm inputs a lot of times but we have not received any of their promises. Any time they promise, they always fail. Some officials will come to us, collect our names about loan, fertiliser, herbicide and farm tools but we will not receive anything. Although they tried about this year’s Tractorisation project but still we don’t trust them. (In-depth interview-2024).

This perception of misinformation, or unmet expectations, contributed to the farmers' understanding of information disorder. They see it as a form of misleading communication from authorities which undermines their trust in government agricultural policies and advice.

In summary, the findings show that farmers have an understanding of information disorder, but it varies based on their experience, location and exposure. This perception influences how they interpret each experience in terms of information disorder. Moreover, the miscommunication and incomplete understanding of weather forecasts and other agricultural information may further hinder effective planning and adaptation strategies as regards climate-smart agriculture. Extension officers have a key role to play here in ensuring that accurate and timely information gets to the farmers so as not to jeopardise the comprehension and adoption of climate-smart agricultural practices.

4.3.3 Sources of Climate Smart Agriculture Information among Farmers in Oyo State

Table 4.4: Sources of CSA Information among Farmers

S N	Sources of Climate Smart Agriculture Information among Farmers									
	Sources		Ogbomoso		Ijaiye		Akufo		Eruwa	
			Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	Extension Officer	Very Reliable	29	65.9	79	65.8	12	21.1	26	52.0
		Somewhat Reliable	9	20.5	31	25.8	38	66.7	16	32.0

		Not Reliable	6	13.6	10	8.3	7	12.3	7	14.0
2	Radio	Very Reliable	22	50.0	69	57.5	30	52.6	24	48.0
		Somewhat Reliable	15	34.1	41	34.2	19	33.3	17	34.0
		Not Reliable	7	15.9	10	8.3	8	14.0	9	18.0
3	Television	Very Reliable	9	20.5	50	41.7	26	45.6	22	44.0
		Somewhat Reliable	10	22.7	31	25.8	18	31.6	19	38.0
		Not Reliable	25	56.8	39	32.5	13	22.8	9	18.0
4	Newspaper	Very Reliable	21	47.7	45	37.5	38	66.7	20	40.0
		Somewhat Reliable	9	20.5	19	25.8	12	21.1	15	30.0
		Not Reliable	14	31.8	56	8.3	7	12.3	15	30.0
5	Fellow Farmer	Very Reliable	26	59.1	75	62.5	24	42.1	9	18.0
		Somewhat Reliable	12	27.3	35	29.1	21	36.8	15	30.0
		Not Reliable	6	13.6	10	8.3	12	21.1	26	52.0
6	Social Media	Very Reliable	8	18.2	28	23.3	6	10.5	9	18.0
		Somewhat Reliable	10	22.7	30	25	12	21.1	13	26.0
		Not Reliable	26	59.1	62	51.6	39	68.4	28	56.0
7	Agriculture Cooperative	Very Reliable	24	54.5	79	65.8	31	54.4	22	44.0
		Somewhat Reliable	9	20.5	31	25.8	16	28.1	19	38.0
		Not Reliable	11	25.0	10	8.3	10	17.5	9	18.0
8	Family Member	Very Reliable	19	43.2	45	37.5	15	26.3	18	36.0
		Somewhat Reliable	10	22.7	42	35	12	21.1	13	26.0
		Not Reliable	15	34.1	33	27.5	30	52.6	19	38.0
9	Religion Group	Very Reliable	8	18.2	35	29.1	13	22.8	8	16.0
		Somewhat Reliable	21	47.7	37	30.8	15	26.3	15	30.0
		Not Reliable	15	34.1	48	40	29	50.9	27	54.0
10	Mobile Advisory	Very Reliable	6	13.6	32	26.6	10	17.5	26	52.0
		Somewhat Reliable	9	20.5	25	20.8	8	14.0	15	30.0
		Not Reliable	29	65.9	63	52.5	39	68.4	9	18.0
11	Online Search	Very Reliable	11	25.0	21	17.5	11	19.3	15	30.0
		Somewhat Reliable	7	15.9	33	27.5	6	10.5	22	44.0
		Not Reliable	26	59.1	66	55	40	70.2	13	26.0
12	NGO's in Agriculture	Very Reliable	20	45.5	58	48.3	31	54.4	21	42.0
		Somewhat Reliable	14	31.8	31	25.8	17	29.8	11	22.0
		Not Reliable	10	22.7	31	25.8	9	15.8	18	36.0

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Data in the table 4.4 shows the sources of climate smart agricultural information and it also shows the reliability or not of these sources in each of the farm settlements. The table shows that agricultural extension agents ranked as the most reliable source of climate-smart agriculture information among farmers in the four farm settlements. In Ogbomoso, 65.9% of farmers considered extension officers to be Very Reliable, followed by Ijaiye (65.8%) and Eruwa (52%). However, Akufo had a slightly lower percentage, with 21% rating extension officers.

Radio is another key source of CSA information, with reliability ratings close to that of extension officers. The proportion of farmers who consider radio very reliable is highest in Ijaye (57.5%), followed by Akufo (52.6%), Ogbomoso (50.0%), and Eruwa (48.0%). Farmers in all locations also recognize radio as somewhat reliable, with percentages ranging from 19% in Akufo to 34.2% in Ijaiye. Despite this, a notable fraction finds radio unreliable, indicating that factors such as language barriers, signal coverage, and program content may influence trust in this source.

Interestingly, farmers in all farm settlements found fellow farmers to be a crucial source of climate-smart information, with Ogbomoso (59.1%) and Ijaiye (62.5%) reporting high levels of reliability. This indicates that communication and knowledge sharing among farmers play an essential role in the dissemination of information, particularly in rural areas where trust and shared experiences are highly valued. Meanwhile, social media and online search was viewed with skepticism, particularly in Ogbomoso and akufo, where 59.1% and 68.4% respectively of farmers rated it as Not Reliable. This could be attributed to concerns over the accuracy of information or lack of familiarity with digital platforms among some farmers.

In the view of a farmer at Ogbomosho (Agric) farm settlement

Radio and extension officers are our major source of receiving climate information. This is because it is easier to use and we get frequent update from agricultural programme that we listen to on it. For instance I don't miss Agbe Asejere by Taiwo oduola on Ajilete Fm every Tuesday by 9pm. Through this we get agric information on planting season, rain and seedling issues. (In-depth interview-2024).

Moreover apart from radio, extension officers remain one of the most trusted source of CSA information to farmers. Many farmers prefer extension officers because they provide face-to-face explanations, demonstration of new farming techniques, and the fact that they speak the local languages which most farmers understand.

The extension officer from Eruwa emphasized this:

Farmers trust us because we are the ones they know. We always reach out to them not only forthrightly but sometimes on weekly basis. They have our mobile number and whenever they are in doubt of any issue as regard farming their president will reach out to me. Anytime we visit the farm settlement, we gather them, they ask many questions. Even if they hear something on the radio about government incentives, fertiliser or a particular agricultural programme, they always come to us to confirm. (In-depth interview-2024).

Similarly, the extension officer at Ijaye stressed their relationship with the farmers:

No matter the situation, we always try to reach the farmers. Although we have challenges but if you ask any of them, they will tell you we are the closest to them in terms of agricultural information. Some do not have mobile phones, and some cannot read, but when we visit, they see us in person, ask questions, and we explain everything to them in their local language. (In-depth interview-2024).

The in-depth interview findings revealed Social media as a major force in the dissemination of CSA information, depicting a shift from previous studies that found that there were low farmer engagement with digital platforms (Oyedele 2018). Social networking platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, TikTok and YouTube are now key sources of agricultural knowledge, and these has

exposed farmers to real-time updates, discussions on forums, and exposure to new and latest farming practices. The in-depth interview with farmers also revealed that some farmers now frequently access CSA-related information on social media. In the response of a farmer at eruwa farm settlement

For me, I have seen a video on youtube about irrigation before, I followed the process and it worked. So I make use of social media to get information and learn about new things. (In-depth interview-2024)

It is clear that social media now compete with traditional sources of agriculture information dissemination like radio and extension officers. It was also observed during the interview that the farmers have among them educated farm owners who with their presence have drawn more people who are educated to take part in agriculture.

A farmer in Akufo had this to say of adoption of social media in agriculture

Before, our fathers who introduced us to farming are used to radio and extension officers but for me now, I am educated and I have an android phone which I always use to check and receive information relating to agriculture. I belong to 4 whatsapp groups where we receive information of weather forecast, fertiliser, and seedlings and even we receive notice of meetings with our commodity groups and extension officers. Our monthly settler meeting is always posted and announced on the farm settlement whatsapp group. (In-depth interview-2024)

The extension officer from Akufo had this to say on the use of social media:

Yes, we use social media platforms especially WhatsApp and to share Agric updates with farmers. But you know, this is only common among the younger and educated farmers. It helps us reach them faster when we are very busy. (In-depth interview-2024)

Similarly, the extension officer from Ogbomoso noted:

Social media is used here but we just started with the younger farmers not the old farmers who don't know anything about android phones. Their children sometime

help to explain and pass across the message. But it is not reliable. (In-depth interview-2024).

4.3.4 Sources of CSA Information Disorder among Farmers

Table 4.5: Sources of Climate-Smart Agriculture Information Disorder among Farmers in Oyo State

SN	Sources	Settlement	(Yes)	(No)
1	Extension Officers	Ogbomosho	6 (13.6%)	38 (86.4%)
		Ijaiye	10 (8.3%)	110 (91.7%)
		Akufo	7 (12.3%)	50 (87.7%)
		Eruwa	9 (18.0%)	41 (82.0%)
2	Radio	Ogbomosho	25(56.8%)	19 (43.2%)
		Ijaiye	55 (68.8%)	25 (31.2%)
		Akufo	30 (52.6%)	27 (47.4%)
		Eruwa	35(70.0%)	15 (30.0%)
3	Television	Ogbomosho	25 (56.8%)	19 (43.2%)
		Ijaiye	39 (32.5%)	81 (67.5%)
		Akufo	13 (22.8%)	44 (77.2%)
		Eruwa	9 (18.0%)	41 (82.0%)
4	Newspaper	Ogbomosho	14 (31.8%)	30 (68.2%)
		Ijaiye	15 (12.5%)	105 (87.5%)
		Akufo	10 (17.5%)	47 (82.5%)
		Eruwa	9 (18.0%)	41 (82.0%)
5	Fellow Farmers	Ogbomosho	6 (13.6%)	38 (86.4%)
		Ijaiye	15 (12.5%)	105 (87.5%)
		Akufo	12 (21.1%)	45 (78.9%)
		Eruwa	10 (20.0%)	40 (80.0%)
6	Social Media Platforms (WhatsApp, Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, Twitter, etc.)	Ogbomosho	30 (68.2%)	14 (31.8%)
		Ijaiye	50 (41.7%)	70 (58.3%)
		Akufo	47 (82.5%)	10 (17.5%)
		Eruwa	35 (70.0%)	15 (30.0%)
7	Agricultural Cooperative Groups	Ogbomosho	11 (25.0%)	33 (75.0%)
		Ijaiye	10 (8.3%)	110 (91.7%)
		Akufo	10 (17.5%)	47 (82.5%)
		Eruwa	9 (18.0%)	41 (82.0%)
8	Family Members Involved in Farming	Ogbomosho	15 (34.1%)	29 (65.9%)
		Ijaiye	33 (27.5%)	87 (72.5%)
		Akufo	30 (52.6%)	27 (47.4%)
		Eruwa	15 (30.0%)	35 (70.0%)
9	Religious Groups or Gatherings	Ogbomosho	15 (34.1%)	29 (65.9%)
		Ijaiye	48 (40.0%)	72 (60.0%)
		Akufo	29 (50.9%)	28 (49.1%)

		Eruwa	9 (18.0%)	41 (82.0%)
10	Mobile Agricultural Advisory Services	Ogbomosho	29 (65.9%)	15 (34.1%)
		Ijaiye	63 (52.5%)	57 (47.5%)
		Akufo	39 (68.4%)	18 (31.6%)
		Eruwa	9 (18.0%)	41 (82.0%)
11	Agricultural Research Institutions	Ogbomosho	10 (22.7%)	34 (77.3%)
		Ijaiye	31 (25.8%)	89 (74.2%)
		Akufo	9 (15.8%)	48 (84.2%)
		Eruwa	9 (18.0%)	41 (82.0%)
12	Government	Ogbomosho	30 (68.2%)	14 (31.8%)
		Ijaiye	55 (45.8%)	65 (54.2%)
		Akufo	40(70.2%)	17 (29.8%)
		Eruwa	35 (70.0%)	15(30.0%)
13	Online Search (Google, agricultural websites)	Ogbomosho	18 (40.9%)	26 (59.1%)
		Ijaiye	36 (30.0%)	84 (70.0%)
		Akufo	17 (29.8%)	40 (70.2%)
		Eruwa	9 (18.0%)	41 (82.0%)
14	NGOs Involved in Agriculture	Ogbomosho	10 (22.7%)	34 (77.3%)
		Ijaiye	31 (25.8%)	89 (74.2%)
		Akufo	9 (15.8%)	48 (84.2%)
		Eruwa	9 (18.0%)	41 (82.0%)
15	Other (Please State)	Ogbomosho	11 (25.0%)	33 (75.0%)
		Ijaiye	7 (5.8%)	113 (94.2%)
		Akufo	8 (14.0%)	49 (86.0%)
		Eruwa	10 (20.0%)	40 (80.0%)

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

In table 4.5, Government agencies, expected to be a reliable source of CSA information, was perceived as an inaccurate source of information disorder by a significant number of farmers. The highest percentage was reported in Akufo (70.2%) and Eruwa (70.0%), while Ogbomosho (68.2%) and Ijaiye (45.8%) also show distrust. This supports our findings above, where farmers express their distrust in information coming from the government. It reveals inefficiencies in policy communication and a lack of engagement with farmers at the grassroots level.

Social media platforms, such as WhatsApp, Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram, were also seen to be a source of inaccurate agricultural information. Farmers in Akufo (82.5%) and Eruwa (70.0%)

report high levels of misinformation, due to the reported cases of exaggerated claims of farm inputs that farmers encounter on social networks. Similarly, online searches (Google, agricultural websites) are perceived as inaccurate, particularly in Ogbomosho (40.9%) and Ijaiye (30.0%), indicating challenges in accessing trustworthy digital resources.

Despite being popular sources of information, radio and television were perceived as sources of inaccurate information. Radio was particularly recognized by the farmers as a source from which they have received misinformation in Eruwa (70.0%), Ijaiye (68.8%), and Ogbomosho (56.8%). This shows concerns about wrong information that farmers may have perceive to be from these sources especially the example that was given at Ijaye farm settlement about farmers encountering information disorder as a result of radio agricultural advertisement. Television follows a similar trend, with Ogbomosho (56.8%) and Ijaiye (32.5%) reporting significant skepticism, possibly due to sensationalized reporting or insufficient expert-backed content.

Social media as a source of Information disorder

From the findings gotten during the in-depth interview it was discovered that, Farmers frequently encounter misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation on social platform such as their whatsapp group, Facebook, and YouTube, where unverified agricultural claims, such as advertisements on the usage of organic fertiliser mixture which can double planting yield. Exaggerated benefits of CSA practices and fake improved seedling.

The extension officer at Ogbomosho had this to say regarding social media as source of inaccurate information

Social media is good for sharing agricultural information, but it is also full of wrong information on agric. We have seen a situation where farmers tell us they

saw some advertisement online about a particular maize variety we immediately warned them not to fall for it because it is not true. We are the major source of information to farmers and when this new generation farmers come they are trying to bring some methods from the social media that have not been tested by we the approved extension agent to the farmers. We always warn them to be careful. (In-depth interview-2024).

Exaggerated Claims on Radio Advertisements

As stated earlier, radio has long been regarded as one of the most trusted and accessible sources of agricultural information for farmers, particularly in remote areas where digital access is limited. Studies have shown that radio programs play an important role in disseminating Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) information. However, despite its advantages, radio has also become a source of misinformation, particularly through advertisements and promotion of exaggerated claims about agricultural inputs. The farmer at Ijaye recounted their experience on this

There was a time we heard an advert from an agricultural expert on fresh FM about a particular tomato seedling that produces high yield of tomato at harvest. The person said that the seed will grow into a tree and we can harvest tomato on the tree for up to 6 months. One of us went to buy the product and after we planted it, it was a fake product. We went to buy the seedling from Joke plaza that year. (In-depth interview-2024).

Farmers as source of Information disorder

Beyond social media, interpersonal and word-of-mouth was also identified as a source of CSA information disorder. A lot of farmers revealed that they rely on fellow farmers especially those who are experienced and knowledgeable for agricultural knowledge, yet some information may lack scientific confirmation or may have been distorted through repetition. Also farmers pre-existing knowledge and experience may serve as a hindrance to the adoption of new improved variety of farm products. The extension officer at Ijaye has this to say about the above

There was a time around 2008 when we introduce the yellow cassava to the farmers, they reluctantly adopted it because they are used to TSM 3055 and TMS 30572. Most of them ignored it because they don't believe in it not until the

educated one among them begin to convince them to adopt it. The old farmers among them discouraged a lot of them that the cassava may not make much sales in the market as the ones they have known before. So most of the time they carry misleading information from among themselves. (In-depth interview-2024)

The extension officer also added that

Famers get information on the radio but sometimes they relay half-baked information to their colleagues. They don't listen to the end of the programme on the radio and thereby they begin to pass across information that is not complete to their fellow farmers. (In-depth interview-2024)

This finding revealed that fellow Farmers are also sources of information disorder in situations where they pick up only parts of the intended message. This half understanding results in the spread of incomplete or misleading information when they share it with their fellow farmers.

Extension officers as Source of Information disorder

However, contrary to the above perspective, some farmers in Eruwa reported that misinformation also come from agricultural extension officers. A farmer cited the instance below

Extension officers were here with us to demonstrate a new variety of cassava to us. The standard planting spacing recommendation was 1m × 1m. After the demonstration we tried it on our farms but we realized that this variety requires more spacing than the one we know which is sanmi (TME 419) the one planted by the extension officers came out good because it was on a small space. But the one we planted was different because we discovered that the spacing was not favourable with our system, so we have to change to a wider spacing the following year to get a good result. "It is not that we do not trust them, but our experiences count a lot. We notified them of these results, but you know, their work is just to carry out demonstrations and report to their bosses that they have done it. (In-depth interview-2024)

This account and finding shows that there can be discrepancies between recommendations that were given through demonstration and when the farmers actually carryout the recommendations. Farming practice may not be only effective on demonstrations alone but experiences of stakeholders must be considered in order to review the communication process. Although the

farmers stated that this does not mean they do not trust the extension officers but they always prioritize their experience on a particular information.

Government as source of Information disorder

The Farmers also expressed frustration over unfulfilled government promises of agricultural support programs, farm inputs, provision of tractors, subsidies. They identified these as a form of information disorder. Many farmers noted that government officials and policymakers frequently announce their intervention programmes through the radio, extension officers, and NGOs, but a lot of the time these promises are not implemented or they get into the wrong hands who are not farmers. This situation led to distrust of information from the government.

A President of Eruwa farm settlement voiced his frustration

We have been deceived a lot of the time by the government and it is disappointing. We don't trust them again even when they make new promises. There was a time that I was asked to collate our names to the Oyo state secretariat which we did. We did not hear anything from them, luckily someone informed me that farm input are being shared at the secretariat. I decided to go that same day but in my presence they were giving the inputs to people that we know are not farmers and even some suppliers who will resell these product to farmers. In my presence I saw some of the farmers who could not get the input buy from those who are willing to sell. This has made us not to trust the government again even if they promise heaven and earth. (In-depth interview-2024)

4.3.5 Influence of Information Disorder on Farming Practice and Adoption of Climate

Smart Agriculture among Farmers in Oyo State

Table 4.6: Influence of Information Disorder on Adoption of CSA Practices among Farmers in Oyo State

Influence on Farmers	Ogbomosho (n=44)	Ijaye (n=120)	Akufo (n=57)	Eruwa (n=50)
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Avoided spending on CSA tools	13 (29.55%)	36 (30.00%)	17 (29.82%)	15 (30.00%)
Conflicting information	30 (68.18%)	56 (46.67%)	27 (47.37%)	24 (48.00%)
Consulted experts/community groups	29 (65.91%)	89 (74.1%)	38 (66.67%)	43 (86.00%)
Delayed adoption	16 (36.36%)	44 (36.67%)	21 (36.84%)	18 (36.00%)
Lack of trust in CSA information	30 (68.00%)	65 (54.10%)	28 (49.12%)	25 (50.00%)
Lost money due to misinformation	25 (57.00%)	70 (58.00%)	20 (35%)	30 (60.00%)
Returned to traditional farming	9 (20.45%)	24 (20.00%)	11 (19.30%)	10 (20.00%)
Sought information from other sources	26 (59.09%)	70 (58.33%)	33 (57.89%)	32 (64.00%)
Used wrong practices	15 (34.09%)	40 (33.33%)	25 (43.85%)	16 (32.00%)

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

From the responses of farmers across the four farm settlements in table 4.6, trust in CSA information remains a significant challenge as farmers in Ogbomosho (68%) and Ijaye (54.1%) are in doubt of CSA information, while 49.12% of Akufo farmers and 50% of Eruwa farmers shared similar concerns. This lack of trust has led to hesitation in adopting CSA practices. Incidences of misinformation has also led to financial losses among the farmers. The highest reports of losses were recorded in Eruwa (60%), followed by Ijaye (58%) and Ogbomosho (57%). The farmers noted that they incurred huge losses as a result of the inaccurate information about weather forecast last year November. These shows that incorrect information can have direct economic consequences on agricultural practice and consequently lead to discouragement of investment in CSA practices.

Conflicting information was reported by 68.18 percent of farmers in Ogbomosho, 46.67 percent in Ijaye, 47.37 percent in Akufo, and 48.00 percent in Eruwa, indicating that inconsistent messages about CSA is a critical issue across all four farm settlements.. Farmers in Akufo

(36.84%) and Ijaye (36.67%) said they delayed adopting CSA due to unclear or contradictory messages which has reduced their willingness to try new agricultural methods. Moreover, in response to unreliable information, farmers say they have returned to traditional farming methods. This trend was observed among 20.45% of farmers in Ogbomosho, 20% in Ijaye, and 19.30% in Akufo. The findings suggest that when farmers perceive CSA information as inconsistent or misleading, they revert to agricultural practices they are familiar with.

The data clearly shows how misinformation influenced the adoption of CSA by Oyo State farmers. While farmers recognize the importance of CSA, many of them have challenges with deciding which practices to adopt due to unreliable or misleading information. It is important to note that these challenges requires that agricultural communication systems are strengthened, so as to improve the credibility of information sources, and ensure that CSA messages are consistent and accessible to farmers.

The level of trust farmers have in official sources as regards issues that relate with inputs, fertilizer, loan and other sustainable agricultural practice has been eroded over the years and this was echoed in all the farm settlements by the farmers during the in-depth interview. This situation poses a big challenge to the implementation of effective climate change strategies, as farmers are less likely to act on government-backed recommendations or policies. As seen in the findings from the in-depth interviews, one farmers in Eruwa expressed;

At a time the government packaged expired tomato seedlings and herbicide. When our farmers got there they did capturing and all other verifications. They were given the input. We then decided to verify from the company whose label was on the input and they asked us where we got the product that it is not a real product. We went ahead to test the seedlings but it did not germinate. This has made us loose trust in the government. Although we trust the extension officer sent by them because of the relationship we have developed with them but once

they inform us of one government agricultural product distribution for farmers we don't take it serious. (In-depth interview-2024).

Misleading information shared from one farmer to the other also had economic implications on their farming practice. The in-depth interview revealed this in the farm settlements as farmers expressed how the misleading information had led them to take wrong CSA decisions and in the long run experience financial loss. In the words of a farmer in Ijaye farm settlement

I lost a lot of money after the tomato I planted did not give me the expected result. I was expecting bountiful harvest like it was advertised on the radio but it was not so. I have been very careful since then. Before we go ahead and try any new product, we now ensure to verify very well, especially from our extension officers. (In-depth interview-2024).

The Eruwa extension officer also mentioned that

Most of the time their wrong decision on climate smart agriculture has led to a lot of loss. When you have not verified an information with us the extension officers, we have warned them, whenever you hear anything that you are not sure of, please put a call through to us and we will help in verifying the information. (In-depth interview-2024).

However, despite the trust issues in some official sources of information i.e government, farmers still maintain their trust in NIMET weather predictions although they fail sometimes. Perhaps it could be because they recognise Nimet as the official and most accessible source of weather predictions and this predictions are subject to climate change. Just as the Nimet Ibadan Zonal manager stated in September 2024 that forecast are about 80 to 85 percent accurate (Isawade, 2024). A farmer at Akufo farm settlement noted:

Nimet is an Organisation we trust. We depend on them for weather prediction especially at the start of planting season to make planting decisions. Although we hear about weather forecast from other sources in the radio and from our whatsapp groups but we always cross check them with Nimet information not minding that their predictions fail sometime. It is not all the time that their predictions fail. (In-depth interview-2024)

Moreover, the influence of Information disorder on the farmers also results in farmers unwilling to adopt CSA practice after they have been exposed to misleading information. Some of the farmers who have encountered misinformation said it made them to go back to their previous practices. This means that adoption of new farming practices or technology is being affected negatively. This was expressed by a farmer at Ijaye farm settlement.

I have tried many new techniques of farming. For instance one time I used a liquid organic fertilizer, because our extension agent always preach to us to make use of organic because it is safer for human health. So there was one I tried and did not give me the expected result. This made me to go back to the use of our old NPK. I cannot continue to waste money and time on something that doesn't work. Many information out there just make it hard to trust new methods. (In-depth interview-2024).

4.3.6 Regression Analysis of Influence of information Disorder on Adoption of Climate Smart Agriculture

The regression equation is:

$$y = -0.1331 + 0.2283X_1 + 0.1869X_2 + 0.4310X_3 + 0.3023X_4 + 0.3183X_5 - 0.0204X_6 + 0.0900X_7 + 0.3474X_8 + 0.2380X_9$$

Where:

y = Influence on Farmers (Dependent Variable)

X₁ = Avoided spending on CSA tools

X₂ = Conflicting information

X₃ = Consulted experts/community groups

X₄ = Delayed adoption

X₅ = Lack of trust in CSA information

X₆ = Lost money due to misinformation

X₇ = Returned to traditional farming

X₈ = Sought information from other sources

X₉ = Used wrong practices

Table 4.7 Multiple Regression Results for the Influence of information disorder on adoption of CSA practices

Independent Variable	Coefficient (Beta)	Standard Error	T	p-value
Avoided spending on CSA tools	0.2283	.030	-.163	.000
Conflicting information	0.1869	.020	.552	.001
Consulted experts/community groups	0.4310	.000	-.178	.858
Delayed adoption	0.3023	.000	7.873	.000**
Lack of trust in CSA information	0.3183	.028	-3.846	.000**
Lost money due to misinformation	-0.0204	.029	-5.490	.000**
Returned to traditional farming	0.0900	.083	4.110	.000**
Sought information from other sources	0.3474	0.28	-1.88	.059
Used wrong practices	0.2380	0.30	-.164	.071

Note statistics is significant at 0.05 (**)

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

The coefficient of 0.2283 in Table 4.7 suggests a positive relationship between the avoidance of spending on CSA tools and the influence of information disorder on farmers. For every one-unit increase in the avoidance of spending on CSA tools, there is an expected increase of 0.2283 units in the influence of information disorder. This finding highlights that farmers' decisions to avoid investing in CSA tools may be influenced by misinformation or confusion regarding the utility and efficiency of these tools. The coefficient of 0.1869 shows that as the amount of conflicting

information increases, the influence of information disorder on farmers increases as well. This implies that conflicting messages, perhaps from different sources or organizations, contribute significantly to the hesitation or confusion experienced by farmers, which in turn affects their adoption of CSA practices. Although the coefficient of 0.4310 appears large for Consulting experts or community groups, the relationship is not statistically significant. This means that consulting experts or community groups did not have a consistent effect on the influence of information disorder in this study. The coefficient of 0.3023 shows that delayed adoption of CSA practices correlates positively with the influence of information disorder. The more the information disorder, the longer the farmers take to adopt CSA practices, which reflects the hesitation or the need for more time to process and verify the information they are receiving. Lack of trust in CSA information (0.3183), is another factor that increases the influence of information disorder on farmers. This result signifies that mistrust in the available information further compounds the difficulties that farmers face when making decisions regarding CSA practices. The negative coefficient of -0.0204 suggests that farmers who lose money due to misinformation may not experience the same increase in information disorder compared to others. However, the small magnitude of this coefficient may indicate a weak influence of this factor compared to others. The positive coefficient of 0.0900 indicates that farmers who revert to traditional farming due to the influence of information disorder are slightly more affected by misinformation, though this effect is not as pronounced as some of the other variables.

The coefficient of 0.3474 implies that seeking information from alternative sources may be a response to information disorder. Farmers who do not trust the conventional sources of information may seek alternatives, which can either alleviate or intensify the disorder depending

on the reliability of the new sources. The coefficient of 0.2380 shows that when farmers adopt wrong practices, this is positively correlated with the influence of information disorder. This suggests that misinformation or poorly understood practices may lead to incorrect farming strategies, which could ultimately have detrimental effects on CSA adoption.

4.3.7 Fact-Checking Mechanisms Utilized By Oyo State Farmers to Verify Climate Smart Agricultural Information

Table: 4.8 Fact-checking Methods for Climate-Smart Agriculture Information by Farm Settlement

Verification Methods	Ogbomoso (n=44)	Ijaye (n=120)	Akufo (n=57)	Eruwa (n=50)
Consult agricultural extension officers	18 (40.91%)	30 (25.00%)	14 (24.56%)	12 (24.00%)
Ask from fellow farmers	10 (22.73%)	18 (15.00%)	8 (14.04%)	7 (14.00%)
Depend on my personal experience	14 (31.82%)	24 (20.00%)	11 (19.30%)	9 (18.00%)
Conduct small trials	6 (13.64%)	12 (10.00%)	5 (8.77%)	5 (10.00%)
Check online sources (Google, agricultural websites)	10 (22.73%)	21 (17.50%)	10 (17.54%)	9 (18.00%)
Verify from government bulletins or advisories	6 (13.64%)	15 (12.50%)	7 (12.28%)	6 (12.00%)
Seek advice from agricultural institutions	15 (34.09%)	27 (22.50%)	13 (22.81%)	11 (22.00%)
Verify through radio/TV/newspaper sources	8 (18.18%)	19 (16.00%)	9 (15.79%)	7 (14.00%)
Ask family members with farming experience	7 (15.91%)	16 (13.33%)	7 (12.28%)	6 (12.00%)
Consult agricultural cooperatives or community groups	10 (22.73%)	23 (19.17%)	11 (19.30%)	9 (18.00%)

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

The implementation of Climate-Smart Agriculture is confronted by a problem which is the difficulty of farmers to distinguish between factual and wrong information. To combat the

incidences of information disorder, Farmers revealed that they utilize different types of information verification methods. This helps them to authenticate the information received from any source. Moreover, the effectiveness of these fact-checking methods varies depending on access to fact checking tools and trust in the sources.

The finding as shown in table 4.8 above shows that more farmers make use of the extension officers as their major source of CSA information verification. The findings revealed that 40.91% of farmers in Ogbomosho, 25% in Ijaye, 24.5% in Akufo, and 24% in Eruwa relied on extension officers for CSA information. A farmer at Eruwa expanded on this

Extension officers are our friends they are the ones we run too whenever we have issues with information that we are not sure of. Although they may not be around all the time we have access to their phone number and whenever we call them they answer us. (In-depth interview-2024)

The President of settlers at Eruwa further explained that

As you are here with us now it is because of the person that referred you to us, that is the reason why we gave you audience. If not we do not just entertain any visitor as such. We may not trust the government because they have disappointed us many time but we trust the extension officers. (In-depth interview-2024)

The above assertion by the farmers shows that they have built a considerable level of trust in the extension officers as their major information verification source. As confirmed from the farm settlements, extension officers are known to provide correct agricultural advice, training, and on-the-ground support to farmers, which helps to ensure the accuracy of agricultural practices, including climate-smart techniques.

In addition to consulting extension officers, a good percentage of farmers also seek verification from agricultural institutions such as research instituitons, colleges of agriculture, and state agricultural development programmes. The findings revealed that 34.09% of farmers in

Ogbomosho, 22.5% in Ijaye, 22.81% in Akufo, and 22% in Eruwa rely on these institutions for confirming the authenticity of climate-smart agriculture information. These institutions are considered credible because of their technical expertise, periodic trainings, and collaboration with government agencies and extension units, which enhance farmers' confidence in the accuracy of information received.

Furthermore, farmers also rely fellow farmers to confirm information they have received from unverified sources. The findings shows that 22.73% of farmers in Ogbomosho, 15% in Ijaye, 14.04% in Akufo, and 14% in Eruwa rely on fellow farmer's experiences. These discussions according to the farmers, take place face to face, when they go for their monthly meetings, cooperative and commodity group meetings where they share ideas and ask question on farming issues. As a farmer at Akufo noted

We verify information from among ourselves especially from older and experienced ones among us. We share ideas in line with our commodity groups. Although some farmers do give half or wrong information at times. (In-depth interview-2024)

A farmer from Ijaye also recounted:

We discuss and share information with other farmers before trying new things. Sometimes, it works, but other times we find out that what we heard wasn't true. (In-depth interview-2024)

While the traditional media, especially radio has been established in studies to be one of the major sources of agricultural information for farmers (Chapman *et al.*, 2003; Munyua, 2000), more importantly among farmers with low literacy, few farmer rely on this method as their primary method of fact checking CSA information. Although 16% of farmers in Ijaye, 15.79% in Akufo, 18.18% in Ogbomosho, and 14% in Eruwa reported using a combination of radio, TV, and newspapers for verification, the increasing use of digital communication has enabled some

farmers, perhaps those who have digital communication knowledge to turn to social media for CSA verification. It was found that 22.73% of farmers in Ogbomosho, 17.5% in Ijaye, 17.54% in Akufo, and 18% in Eruwa now check online sources such as Google and agricultural websites to verify CSA information. It was discovered that, farmers in Akufo, Ogbomosho, and Ijaye farm settlements make use of social media platforms as a means of accessing and verifying CSA information. This shows there is a shift towards digital verification methods among farmers. A farmer from Ijaye shared:

The GMO issue that they are talking about, I verify it online. There are a lot of information that it causes cancer, but when I checked on google and from other sources, I saw that those claims are not true. Many of our farmers here have their minds already polluted with these information but to me I am waiting to try it out because I have confirmed that GMO is not to kill human but to help us adapt to climate change and increase our production. (In-depth interview-2024)

We can establish from these findings that farmers are exposed to information disorder about CSA practices, including myths around Genetically Modified Organisms and other agricultural technologies. The farmer at Ijaye who shared his experience about the false claims about GMOs causing cancer and how he fact-checked this information online shows the process of inoculation, where farmers encounter weaker forms of misinformation, and by verifying this information on reliable sources, they strengthen their immunity against future misleading messages. Essentially, this process of verification works as a form of inoculation, making farmers build resistance to future misinformation. The Biotechnology Society of Nigeria (BSN), had in 2024 established the safety of GMOs. They noted that concerns about GMO safety are mostly based on misinformation.

Moreover, the above finding also revealed that digital literacy is increasing among the farmers, who can now access, interpret, and verify CSA information on different platforms other than the

traditional media and extension officers. This depicts a shift as it contributes to the independence of the farmers in making decisions on CSA information and its adoption.

4.3.8 Challenges Faced by Farmers While Trying to Fact Check CSA Information

Table 4.9: Challenges faced by farmers while trying to fact check CSA information

Challenges Faced	Ogbomoso (n=44)	Ijaye (n=120)	Akufo (n=57)	Eruwa (n=50)
Limited access to reliable information sources	12 (27.27%)	34 (28.33%)	16 (28.07%)	14 (28.00%)
High cost of consulting agricultural experts	10 (22.73%)	29 (24.17%)	13 (22.81%)	11 (22.00%)
Poor mobile network coverage	18 (40.91%)	50 (41.67%)	24 (42.11%)	21 (42.00%)
Conflicting information from different sources	22 (50.00%)	65 (54.17%)	30 (52.63%)	28 (56.00%)
Language barriers or technical jargon	12 (27.27%)	42 (35.00%)	16 (28.07%)	15 (30.00%)
Lack of internet access	13 (29.55%)	38 (31.58%)	19 (32.50%)	15 (30.00%)
Difficulty in finding trustworthy sources	15 (34.09%)	46 (38.33%)	22 (38.60%)	19 (38.00%)
Time constraints due to farming activities	16 (36.36%)	44 (36.84%)	21 (36.67%)	18 (36.00%)
Insufficient support from extension officers	19 (43.18%)	52 (43.86%)	26 (44.17%)	22 (44.00%)
Misinformation from other farmers	20 (45.45%)	55 (45.83%)	26 (45.61%)	23 (46.00%)

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

The data in table 4.9 shows that the most reported challenge faced by farmers while trying to verify CSA information was conflicting information from different sources. This emerged as a leading issue across all locations, with Eruwa (56.0%, n=28) reporting the highest occurrence, followed by Ijaye (54.17%, n=65), Akufo (52.63%, n=30), and Ogbomoso (50.0%, n=22). This suggests that while farmers actively try to verify CSA information, the presence of multiple

contradictory sources leads to confusion. This makes it difficult to verify CSA recommendations.

A farmer in Ijaye remarked,

We hear different things from different people. For instance there was a disease that attacks our tomatoes called Ayoku (tomato rot), there were a lot of information flying around on how to get rid of this disease. We got different types of advice from different source; from extension officers, fellow farmers, radio even NGO on how to get rid of this challenge. Up till now we are still struggling with the problem as no method of attacking it has worked.” Even with the issue of fertilizer some expert will say we should use organic while other will say we should go with chemical fertilizer. They confuse us sometimes. (In-depth interview-2024)

Similarly, misinformation from fellow farmers was another challenge affecting Eruwa (46.0%, n=23), Akufo (45.61%, n=26), Ijaye (45.83%, n=55), and Ogbomoso (45.45%, n=20). While the farmers tend to trust more experienced individuals among them, the spread of inaccurate information still persist. This findings reveal how well intentioned information exchange can result in misleading or outdated information.

The extension officer in Eruwa observed,

Farmers like to spread wrong information among themselves, especially when they get half-baked information and if they try to reach us and they can't some of them who call themselves experienced will just give them wrong advice. We try as much as possible to prevent them from this because we always tell them that whatever they have not conformed from us they should not follow such advice. Some of them have been victim of wrong advice from among themselves. (In-depth interview-2024).

Poor mobile network coverage was another major barrier to verify CSA information, with reports from Ogbomoso (40.91%, n=18), Eruwa (42.0%, n=21), Akufo (42.11%, n=24), and Ijaye (41.67%, n=50). In the process of verifying a confusing information from the extension officers on mobile phone or from the internet, some farmer reported that they face mobile network challenge as their farm location is in the remote areas where mobile network is not strong enough. This limits the ability of the farmers to make informed decisions on time. This was more

pronounced in Ogbomosho and Eruwa, perhaps because these locations are in the rural area where mobile phone network are not strong enough.

Language barriers or technical jargon also hindered access to accurate CSA information, particularly in Ijaye (35.0%, n=42), followed by Eruwa (30.0%, n=15), Akufo (28.07%, n=16), and Ogbomoso (27.27%, n=12). Many CSA training material use scientific language or sometime are in English Language making them less accessible to farmers with limited formal education. Farmers in Eruwa complained that if scientific Jargons about CSA issues should be limited, especially labels on pesticide, herbicide or fertilizers should be translated to the language that most farmers understand. The famers said that

We had to go as far as calling our children from school to help us interpret these jargons. (In-depth interview-2024)

Other important challenges identified by the farmers include time constraints due to farming activities, with 36.36% of farmers in Eruwa, 36.67% in Akufo, 36.84% in Ijaye, and 36.00% in Ogbomoso reporting this issue. Insufficient support from extension officers was another concern, with 43.18% of farmers in Eruwa, 44.17% in Akufo, 43.86% in Ijaye, and 44.00% in Ogbomoso experiencing this challenge. Lack of internet access was reported by 29.55% of farmers in Eruwa, 32.50% in Akufo, 31.58% in Ijaye, and 30.00% in Ogbomoso.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The purpose of this section is to discuss the findings of the study in relation to existing research, literature, with the goal of identifying the gaps that have been addressed and areas that require further research. It also provides an opportunity to support or challenge the findings of previous studies, thereby contributing to the body of knowledge in the field. This process is germane as it

allows for meaningful comparisons between the findings of this study and previous literature, offering insights into how this research advances the understanding of the information disorder.

Knowledge and understanding of farmers on CSA information disorder

The findings of this study show that farmers have varying levels of understanding about CSA information disorder. The detailed understanding reported by the farmers suggests that they are more likely to engage with accurate and factual information as regards CSA. This is important because informed farmers are better equipped to adapt to the challenges posed by climate change. Farmers who demonstrate a detailed understanding of CSA information disorder can make better decisions about adopting sustainable farming practices and can more effectively resist misinformation that could lead them to adopt unsustainable practices. This finding corroborates Chowdhury (2024), who averred that farmers with deep knowledge are more resilient to the effect of misinformation on CSA adoption. More so, the differences in understanding could be linked to variations in the levels of access to credible information, extension services, educational interventions, and exposure to climate-smart agricultural practices in these areas, a point supported by Abugri *et al* (2022) on the role of localised community-based knowledge dissemination, especially in the Nigerian agrifood sector, i.e., making use of local channels, networks, and trusted sources. Previous studies have suggested that educational interventions and effective extension services play a very important role in improving farmers' understanding of agricultural practices (Fadairo, Williams & Nalwanga, 2020). Moreover, the findings from this study align with these assertions, suggesting that farmers with access to regular extension services and agricultural educational programmes in the media are more likely to have a detailed understanding of CSA information disorder. Farmers in Ijaye

and Ogbomoso, who had relatively higher educational levels, were able to differentiate more effectively between misinformation and credible sources on CSA.

The thematic analysis of CSA information disorder revealed that information on misleading agricultural products (26.2%) and inaccurate weather forecasts (30.6%) were among the most prominent issues raised by the farmers. These findings are consistent with Cechmánek (2024), who noted that misinformation, especially concerning seed varieties and agricultural inputs, is rampant in the agri-food sector. Farmers in the study mentioned exaggerated claims made by seed and fertiliser companies, with farmers in Akufo expressing frustration with the marketing of high-yielding seedling varieties that did not deliver as promised. This corroborates Albright (2023), who identified misleading product claims as a key driver of misinformation in agricultural technologies. This finding is further supported by Omodara *et al.* (2023), who found that disinformation from input suppliers promoting non-CSA practices for profit contributes to farmers' misconceptions about the efficacy of improved crop varieties, contributing to the doubt expressed by farmers on climate-smart agricultural technologies.

The theme of deceptive claims about agricultural products has a deeper problem of the lack of trust between farmers and agricultural inputs, based on their previous negative experiences. Most farmers testified that they got misled using uncertified products and so they are not willing to use new innovations. This loss created a deeper systemic issue of agro companies and input sellers taking advantage of information lop-sidedness to sell products of low quality to the farmers. As Ngigi & Muange (2022) point out, lack of credible, localised climate information services contributes to poor decision-making and further reduces the trust of smallholder farmers, especially in cases where the input advice is given by unregulated, local, and private sellers. When the trust in hybrid seeds and fertilisers is lost, farmers will not be willing to use climate-

smart agriculture (CSA) technologies that are key to building resilience and increasing productivity. This is further confirmed by Magesa & Jonathan (2024), who noted that there is a direct relationship between the misperceptions and misinformation about inputs and low adoption rates, which make farmers drift back to traditional methods. This reduces the efficiency of CSA interventions. Moreover, the duty of extension officers and farm input distributors should not be limited to dissemination of CSA information, but they should become the guardians of verified, trusted information that will help farmers to understand the difference between certified products and false claims. This is in tandem with Gemtou *et al.* (2024), who stated that the absence of institutional trust and the perceived irrelevance of technology are the main barriers to adoption, particularly in cases where the farmer doubts and their experiences are not taken into account during the innovation process.

Similarly, weather forecasts were also cited as a form of information disorder, with discrepancies between predicted and actual rainfall leading to poor planting decisions. This finding aligns with Chowdhury *et al.* (2024), who link climate change misinformation to poor adaptation decisions. Oyedele (2018) had previously documented that misinterpreted or unreliable weather information contributed to misinformation among farmers. This discrepancy between forecasted and actual weather patterns most of the time disrupts farmers' planting schedules, and it resulted in reduction in the efficacy of CSA practices such as crop rotation, intercropping, and drought-resistant varieties. Given that climate change has introduced variations in weather patterns, reliable weather forecasting is important for CSA adoption. Moreover, this shows the vital role extension officers have to play in bridging the gap of incomplete information by ensuring that information is clarified and understood by the farmers. As Fadairo *et al.* (2020) averred, inadequate climate information and poor extension services are major constraints for Nigerian

farmers. He noted that misinterpretations of climate data, as seen in this study, hinder effective adaptation and mitigation strategies. This issue, highlighted by farmers regarding the weather forecasting inconsistency, was corroborated by Adelesi *et al.* (2024) when they averred that little forecasting errors could have severe consequences on planting schedules and lower yields among the smallholder farmers. Similarly, Matchaya *et al.* (2025) noted that even with technological advancement, the occasional failure of forecasts is a real challenge, particularly in regions where farmers receive no complementary advisory services to interpret and respond to such uncertainties. Although the accuracy rate of weather forecasts by NIMet, which was put between 80 and 90 per cent, is quite impressive. However, it means that in every ten forecasts, there is a possibility of one of them being inaccurate or less accurate. This may be acceptable in some industries, but in the case of smallholder farmers whose planting and harvesting activities are closely linked to weather conditions, a single misinterpretation or misinformation may result in crop loss or wastage of resources. The fears of the farmers about inaccurate weather forecasts are thus not unfounded. This strengthens the necessity of not only forecast dissemination but also forecast interpretation support. Digital tools and extension officers should assist the farmers to realise that weather forecasts are not absolute but probabilistic and that contingency planning (e.g., staggered planting or drought-resistant varieties, irrigation) should be combined with the use of weather forecasts. Thus, on the one hand, it is essential to develop trust in official meteorological information, and on the other hand, the capacity of farmers to work with uncertainty that is still inherent in climate prediction is to be developed.

The presence of incorrect agricultural advice among farmers, as identified in this study, revealed a persistent and often underestimated source of information disorder in rural agricultural systems. The fact that 21% of the farmers mentioned receiving misleading guidance, ranging

from improper planting schedules to unsafe pesticide use and even incorrect vaccination procedures, suggests that interpersonal communication within farming communities, while trusted, is not always accurate. This reinforces the complex dual nature of farmer-to-farmer interaction. While this relationship helps in community knowledge exchange, it can also serve as a vector for information disorder. Farmers tend to trust peers who appear experienced or successful, but such trust does not always guarantee that the advice is scientifically sound or contextually appropriate. This pattern aligns with Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations Theory (2003), which explains how new ideas, practices, or technologies spread within a social system. The theory warns that when innovations or, in this case, agricultural practices are communicated through informal social channels, especially without verification or input from technical experts, misinformation can proliferate. Farmers in Akufo and other settlements shared experiences of adopting practices based on the advice they got from fellow farmers. This later turned out to be ineffective, not true or even harmful, which ultimately undermines confidence in CSA adoption. Similarly, Abugri *et al.* (2022) agree that unverified advice disseminated through peer networks tends to circulate widely, and when left unchecked by extension officers or credible sources, such misinformation can block the uptake of newer and more beneficial technologies. This becomes a big problem, especially in areas with weak extension coverage or limited access to digital tools.

Another major theme relating to information disorder that emerged from the responses is the issue of unfulfilled government promises. Many farmers expressed frustration with programmes that were delayed, inconsistently implemented, or never materialised. Some expected fertilisers or subsidised inputs but received little or nothing. Others were promised training or access to modern tools, but those efforts were either short-lived or completely absent. These unmet

expectations have left farmers feeling disappointed and, more importantly, not trusting government-led agricultural initiatives. This resonates in all the farm settlements, especially Ogbomosho and Eruwa. The distrust does not just stem from a lack of delivery. It depicts a broader practical fallout. Farmers are no longer confident that official promises will be fulfilled, and that affects how they respond to new programmes coming from the government. In the context of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA), where farmers are encouraged to adopt new and sometimes innovative practices, this kind of scepticism can seriously hinder adoption. The data in this study show that for many, government support feels like a gamble; something uncertain and potentially misleading. This speaks to a deeper credibility issue. When promises are broken repeatedly, it creates a feedback loop: low trust leads to low adoption, which leads to failed programmes, which in turn further weakens trust. This pattern closely mirrors findings by Oyedele (2018), who documented that broken promises and inconsistent support from the government have created long-standing mistrust among smallholder farmers, especially in relation to fertiliser and input subsidies. Similarly, Ikuemonisan (2024) emphasised that policy failures not only frustrate farmers in the short term but also reduce their willingness to participate in future development programmes, even those designed to support resilience and food security.

In essence, the finding of our study reinforces the above findings, that unmet government obligations undermine both trust and adoption of CSA practices. Supporting this further, Arslan *et al.* (2015) found that in Malawi and Zambia, inconsistent government backing, including delayed subsidies and training, reduces trust in CSA programmes. This makes farmers perceive sustainable agriculture as too risky to adopt. Their study highlights the importance of institutional credibility as a foundation for behavioural change. Likewise, Zougmore *et al.* (2016) showed that promises of inputs, funding, or training often go unmet in Sub-Saharan Africa, and

that this erodes confidence in CSA initiatives. Farmers are reluctant to invest time or effort into strategies when they believe the necessary support will not follow through.

Even broader evidence is presented by McCarthy *et al.* (2011) in their FAO report, which pointed out that delays and inconsistencies in government support contribute to widespread scepticism, making farmers question the reliability of CSA-related policies. Across these studies and in the current findings, the implication is clear that effective CSA promotion depends not just on technical knowledge or farmer willingness, but on the trustworthiness and consistency of institutions. Without trust, even well-designed programs may struggle to achieve sustainability.

In summary, the findings show that farmers have an understanding of information disorder, but it varies based on their experience, location and exposure. This is further supported by the argument presented by Cechmánek (2024) that farmers are increasingly being exposed to information disorder within the agri-food sector, which is capable of affecting their decision-making and lead to the adoption of unsustainable practices. More so, the miscommunication and incomplete understanding of weather forecasts and other agricultural information may further hinder effective planning and adaptation strategies as regards climate smart agriculture. Extension officers have a key role to play here in ensuring that accurate and timely information gets to the farmers so as not to jeopardize the comprehension and adoption of Climate smart agricultural practices. As Ngoma, *et.al* (2021) noted, extension officers play important role in training farmers to understand and apply climate information in their farming practices.

Sources of CSA information

In the context of the second objective of this study on information disorder in climate-smart agriculture (CSA), we looked into the sources of CSA-related knowledge from which farmers in

Oyo State get information. The findings indicated major channels, which include extension officers, radio, informal communication between farmers, and social media. These channels influence farmers' comprehension and uptake of CSA messages and practices differently. The extension officers were the most reliable source in all four farm settlements and particularly in Ogbomoso, Ijaiye and Akufo, where over 65 per cent of the respondents rated them as very reliable. The farmers noted that the technical expertise of the officers, their use of local and understandable languages, and the ability to conduct face-to-face communication made them preferable. This aligns with the existing literature, particularly Akwiwu and Patrick (2020), Edet (2024), and Adejo and Opeyemi (2019), which point to the centrality of extension in the transfer of innovations and farming practices to the farmers.

Radio was also found to be an important medium, as the farmers considered it one of the major sources of CSA information. Chinda *et al.* (2019) and Oyedele (2018) findings revealed support for this medium in terms of its accessibility, portability, and cultural resonance. The two studies confirm that rural farmers continue to rely on audio platforms, particularly broadcasts in local dialects, to get timely weather forecasts and input advice. Another essential channel was informal communication among the farmers especially in Ijaiye and Ogbomoso. The respondents noted that they always get information on CSA from experienced farmers. This finding aligns with Waldman *et al.* (2019) and Adejo and Opeyemi (2019) study, who reported peer learning as a potent driver of agricultural innovation in areas where extension services are lacking.

Social media is becoming popular, but it is still secondary to the traditional channels. Despite the fact that the general level of trust in social media is relatively low, online platforms are gaining increasing popularity among younger and better-educated farmers in the area under study. Social media platforms, including WhatsApp, Facebook, and YouTube, have become commonplace to

access CSA-related information, join farming-related groups, and watch educational agricultural content. In line with this shift, Sulaiman (2021) found that youth and middle-aged farmers were especially active in farming and showed a strong willingness to use modern media. Smartphones, in particular, are important sources for information on diseases, vaccines, feed formulation, and marketing. This shift in orientation is also supported by Banmeke and Ajayi (2008) and Ayandiji *et al.* (2021), study which demonstrates how increased internet connectivity and the spread of smartphones are transforming the practices of agricultural communication. Oladele & Olaniyi (2024) also stated that increased literacy levels and an increase in digital infrastructures enable the broader access of farmers to digital resources, but the problem of credibility and the spread of misleading information remains.

Despite the fact that extension officers are still relatively credible, their limited coverage may create experiential gaps that are easily filled by unregulated, informal sources. Farmer-to-farmer communication, though valuable, can perpetuate unverified agricultural advice, as discussed in Abugri *et al.* (2022). Social media, while expanding access, also presents risks of information disorder due to low content regulation and different user literacy levels. These aligns with the concerns raised by Cechmánek (2024) and Magesa & Jonathan (2024), who found that information inequality, particularly from seed/input marketers and informal online networks, contributes to CSA misconceptions and resistance.

Sources of CSA Information Disorder

The second objective of this study was to find out the major sources of CSA information disorder among farmers in Oyo State. One finding as regards this that resonated in all the farm settlements was the fact that social media platforms emerged as one of the major sources of

information disorder among the farmers. Farmers explained that they now make use of social media platforms to get agricultural information, and CSA is not an exception. Platforms such as WhatsApp, YouTube, and Facebook were mentioned. However, while these platforms offer quick and easy access to information, many farmers described them as unreliable, as they have encountered misinformation about climate-smart agriculture on them. In Akufo, about 82% of respondents viewed social media as an inaccurate source of CSA information. In Eruwa, the figure was 70%. This finding supports the findings of Treen, Williams, and O'Neill (2020), who mentioned that social media algorithms and echo chambers often amplify misinformation related to climate issues. It is important to state that social media has emerged as one of the sources of agricultural information in recent years. This is not unconnected to the increasing coverage of internet services in the nation. Also, the study found that there were relatively more educated farmers in the areas under study. The study shows that 73.9% of farmers had formal education (primary, secondary, or tertiary) as against 26.2% with no formal education. This supports the claim of Abioye *et al.* (2024) where it was found that education significantly influenced farmers' willingness to adopt digital application tools such as the IITA herbicide calculator. More so urbanisation is moving closer to the farm settlement under study, therefore the reason for the findings of social media now being used by the farmers. Edet (2024) reported that more than half of CSA-related misinformation among Lagos farmers came from social media, largely due to the trust farmers place in informal networks.

From our findings on the field, farmers explained that they encounter information disorder in CSA on propagated messages through WhatsApp, which promotes fertilisers that do not work as advertised and expected, or some have watched YouTube videos that present incorrect details about hybrid seed varieties. This is in consonance with Ramjattan, Chowdhury, Kabir & Ganpat,

(2024), who described this as misinformation because they were not shared with the intention to deceive but the effect is detrimental to the Farmers. According to Ogunnaike *et al.* (2021) and Allcott and Gentzkow (2017), this situation becomes more serious because there are no standard gatekeeping methods on these platforms, part of which are the major parameters of traditional media. This exposed the farmers to incorrect advice. As explained by Chowdhury *et al.* (2023) this kind of unverified online content is one of the most prominent types of information disorder in agriculture. Farrell (2019), as cited in Ejaz *et al.* (2022), observed that the rise of fake news and the expansion of social media have increased the challenges of how climate issues are reported, especially in developing countries. This allows misinformation to spread quickly without editorial review. As Lazer *et al.* (2018) explained, social bots and coordinated disinformation campaigns can manipulate narratives on social platforms. This shapes the opinions of farmers with misleading or false narratives. Based on this, we argue that digital media, while promising as an informal knowledge space, has created an unstable information environment that often overshadows verified, evidence-based agricultural extension information.

The other dimension that should be mentioned is the influence of visual and emotional appeal to the dissemination of misinformation on social media. Some of the farmers reported being deceived by attractive video materials and testimonies that appeared convincing but turned out to be untrue or overstated. An example that came up during the study was the advertisement of a hybrid maize seed variety, which was said to produce about five cobs per plant at harvest. However, after farmers followed up and confirmed with extension officers, it turned out that the claim was exaggerated and not entirely accurate. This is consistent with the conclusions of Tandoc, *et.al.* (2018), who believed that misinformation on social media is more emotionally suggestive and visually compelling, which makes it more memorable and more prone to sharing,

particularly with low digital experience. In the context of CSA, it implies that farmers may use farming practice methods or buy inputs just because they were presented in a convincing way, but not because they are scientifically correct.

Moreover, this study also discovered that peer validation in the social media platforms is one of the key factors that contributed to the reinforcement of misinformation. Farmers reported that when several farmers in their WhatsApp group support a certain product or technique, others are more likely to believe it is true. This confirms the notion of social proof, which Vosoughi, Roy, and Aral (2018) discovered; that misinformation travels much faster than true information, especially when it is promoted by people who are close or trusted. This behavioural pattern is the reason why educated farmers can get into the trap of misinformation, as the source is known and the content is not questioned. It is also important to acknowledge the distinction between advertisement and agricultural advice on social media. Farmers mentioned that input sellers now use platforms like WhatsApp and Facebook to aggressively market products with exaggerated claims, often disguised as helpful farming tips. This is supported by Garet *et al.* (2023), who found that in the agri-food sector of sub-Saharan Africa, social media has become a tool for commercial persuasion, often without control. In such cases, information disorder is not just an accidental by-product of digital access, but a structural issue embedded in how agricultural knowledge is being commodified online.

Another major source of CSA information disorder identified by the farmers was government source. Farmers mentioned that they had received promises of support, such as fertilisers or farming tools that were never delivered. As a result, they tend to doubt information coming from the government, either those advertised on the radio or relayed to them by the extension officers,

even when it is accurate. This is an example of malinformation. The information may be true, but because of failed policies and broken promises, it is received with suspicion and frustration. This is in alignment with Fadairo *et.al.* (2020) who observed that poor communication from government sources often discourages farmers from adopting climate-smart practices. This study builds on these findings by showing that distrust is shaped not just by lack of access but also by past disappointments. Even accurate information will not be effective unless it is supported by follow-through and delivery. Drawing from the responses gathered, we contend that government credibility in CSA programming cannot rely solely on scientific accuracy. Trust, built over time through consistent performance and participatory engagement, is very important. The findings suggest that policy message dissemination must move beyond technical correctness and reckon with the emotional and historical perceptions farmers hold toward public institutions.

The other thing that appears to be pertinent here is how the past experiences influence how farmers receive current messages. As Arslan *et al.* (2015) observed in their study from Malawi and Zambia that inconsistent government promises, such as delayed inputs and undelivered training, lowered farmers' willingness to adopt sustainable practices, even when the advice was beneficial. The farmers did not lack the understanding of the value, they simply did not feel safe enough to take the risk. This seems to be rather close to what was found in this research. Apparently, farmers are reluctant when the CSA information is provided by the government. Not that the message is necessarily false, but because it brings the memory of the previous disappointments. Zougmore *et al.* (2016) also make a similar observation. They observed that the failure to honour promises regarding funding and training in Sub-Saharan Africa tends to make farmers pull out of CSA efforts. We can infer, then, that the real concern here is not just the truth of the message, but the trustworthiness of the messenger. The government might have

scientifically sound information and even well-crafted programs on CSA. However, when it fails to deliver on a number of occasions, then its communication loses legitimacy. Even good advice is not effective when it comes via a medium that farmers have been trained to suspect.

Radio and extension officers continue to be the most common sources of CSA information for farmers. They are preferred by farmers for their accessibility, use of local languages, and consistency. This confirms earlier studies by Ani and Baba (2010), Akwiwu and Patrick (2020), and Alarima *et al.* (2020), who found that both radio and agricultural extension agents played key roles in knowledge sharing among farmers. However, the findings of this study show that these sources are also starting to lose trust in some cases. Farmers reported that some radio programs now focus on promoting commercial products, often with exaggerated claims about fertilizers or seeds. While radio remains widely used, its credibility may be at risk with the prioritization of advertising over verified agricultural information.

Some farmers in the interviews mentioned that what was initially informative contents have over time turned into promotional contents where bold statements are made about some products which would increase yield or about crops which resist pest attack, only to be found out to be misleading. These false claims, presented as professional advice, cause a gap between educational content and advertisement, whereas farmers are left confused about who to believe. In addition, it seems that the traditional media, though remaining at the core of the rural communication setting, is currently working under a new set of constraints. Radio programming has been questioned in terms of editorial integrity due to the commercial nature of programming. Perhaps, part of the issue is tied to what Popoola (2018) described as the commodification of media, where communication platforms now place more emphasis on commercialization than

dissemination of factual information. This school of thought portrays media houses as airtime and content space sellers and not the transmitters of knowledge to the masses. McChesney (2008) had earlier argued that in such systems, public service journalism gives way to advertising-driven content, shaped by the interests of those who fund it. The danger of this misinformation arises when the product sponsors influence the agricultural messages instead of scientific validation. Farmers expressed concern that media programmes were no longer focused on knowledge, but on persuasion. The overwhelming presence of branded promotions and testimonial-style jingles has made it harder for them to tell the difference between verified information and sales pitches. What seems to be happening, then, is a gradual erosion of trust in one of the most accessible and affordable platforms for rural farmers. We may infer that if these trends continue unchecked, traditional radio could shift from being a source of empowerment to one of confusion. There is a need, therefore, to revisit the regulatory frameworks guiding agricultural broadcasting and consider content verification processes that would protect the credibility of rural information system.

Extension officers also received mixed feedback from farmers. Their knowledge was valued, but trust depended on the outcome of their recommendations. In Eruwa, a large percentage of farmers had reduced confidence in extension advice after a cassava spacing demonstration failed to work on large farms. This supports the conclusion by Fadairo *et.al.* (2020), who argued that one-size-fits-all approaches often fail in rural contexts where farmers face different challenges. Adebayo (2024) also pointed out that gaps in extension officers' knowledge can limit their effectiveness. What this study highlights is that farmers are not just passive recipients of information. They compare it with their own experience. If advice does not align with what works for them, they may ignore it. Ogunnaike *et al.* (2021) encouraged the use of participatory

models in extension services. This is what is now being referred to as extension 4.0. This study strongly supports this approach, showing that farmers prefer to learn through engagement and practical involvement rather than only through demonstrations. From these findings, we assert that extension services must evolve from being delivery mechanisms for pre-packaged information to collaborative facilitators of localised learning. Our findings show that farmers value advice, but they also want to see its effectiveness tested in their context.

Peer networks also played a significant role in shaping how farmers received CSA information. Farmers often listen to each other, especially those with more experience. However, the study found that farmer to farmer advice can also contribute to the issue of information disorder. In Ijaiye, 60.5 percent of farmers reported that their trust in fellow farmers has been affected due to poor results from past recommendations. For example, yellow cassava was once rejected based on the belief that it would not sell, which later proved false. Lewandowsky *et al.* (2012) noted that misinformation can spread when individuals share only partial or misunderstood information. Waldman *et al.* (2019) described how smallholder farmers may ignore new knowledge if it contradicts what they already believe. This was also seen in Oyo State, where some farmers continued using older cassava varieties despite evidence of better alternatives. While peer advice can be helpful, it may also reinforce outdated practices when not supported by verified information. We argue that this reflects a deeper cognitive pattern among farmers, where lived experience becomes the main lens for filtering new information. However, it also highlights the need to blend farmer-to-farmer learning with access to broader, evidence-based guidance that can challenge and expand previously known models.

In summary, this study shows that CSA information disorder in Oyo State comes from many sources. Social media and peer networks are common sources of misinformation. Government communication suffers from malinformation, due to policy failures and unfulfilled promises. Commercialised media messages, particularly on radio, are potential sources of disinformation. Chowdhury *et al.* (2023) provided a useful framework that explains how these three types of information disorder can work together to damage trust and lower the quality of agricultural decision-making. Earlier work by Cook *et al.* (2017) and Treen *et al.* (2020) warned about the risk of climate misinformation. This study builds on this by showing how even trusted sources like radio and extension officers can lose their influence when content is not reliable or locally relevant. In essence, our conclusion on these findings is that trust is the central issue in CSA communication. Without it, even the most scientifically sound messages can fail.

Influence of Information disorder on the adoption of CSA

The results of this objective indicate that the problem of information disorder is not only prevalent in the agricultural information environment of Oyo State, but it has become one of the key factors that make farmers reluctant, hesitate, or even abandon the idea of adopting CSA practices. Findings show that the connection between information clarity and decision-making is not only a statistical one, but social and institutional.

Based on the findings, one of the most significant correlation was between the farmers consulting experts or community groups and the impact of information disorder (0.4310). This in essence, implies that confusion tends to make farmers resort to sources they trust to get clarity. Farmers tend to resort to the community elders, trusted extension officers, or fellow farmers who have the experience. This is in line with the findings of Gupta *et al.* (2019) that peer verification

is a way to break the cycle of misinformation. Perhaps, this may not be absolutely true all the time because farmers sometimes give incorrect advice, which contributes to the cycle of misinformation among the farmers. This is further consistent with Lewandowsky *et al.* (2012) who cautioned that once false notions enter a community circulation, they become difficult to eradicate.

The absence of confidence in some CSA information also appeared with a high coefficient (0.3183). It appears that trust is not just created on the basis of truth, it is created on consistency and lived experiences. Some of the farmers interviewed had at one time or the other come in contact with fertilizers that were not effective, seedlings that failed to yield as expected, or were promised assistance but nothing materialized. Therefore, even when the information was technically correct, doubt still exist. This is the typical example of malinformation, where the message is correct but the track record of the source cannot be trusted. This is in consonance with Fadairo *et.al.* (2020) who stressed that it is not sufficient to enhance the content of agricultural messages but important that the institutional credibility of such content is present. The issue of delayed adoption also supported this point. Confusing messages make farmers to wait for a while before adoption. They prefer to wait and see what the result of the adoption is with those who have tried it. They want to establish such practice works or not. This kind of wait-and-see attitude is understandable. This type of hesitation is a logical means of defence in high-stake situations in farming especially when it involves huge financial commitment. This is in line with Ecker *et al.* (2023), who argued that even after correcting misinformation, its effects can linger and continue to influence reasoning. What this tells me is that correcting a false message is not the same as restoring confidence.

The findings also revealed that information disorder had influenced farmers in avoiding spending on CSA tools. This is important as it reflects a financial perspective to the issue. Most of the farmers are smallholders and invariably they fund their farming activities by themselves. Therefore, when there are contradictory information about a particular CSA practices, be it seedling, fertiliser or planting spacing, they refrain from spending on such practice. Delay in farming however may result in missing out on a planting season. And in farming, hesitation can mean missing planting windows. The accounts from farmers about financial loss due to misleading adverts especially radio promotions or WhatsApp messages support finding by Edet (2023), who noted that smallholder farmers hesitate to invest in CSA inputs when they encounter contradictory or misleading information, leading to critical delays and even loss of planting opportunities.

Moreover, farmers also reported the influence of information disorder to the fact that they lost money. This has a negative coefficient ($\beta = -0.0204$) and reflects what happens after the loss has occurred as a result of misinformation on CSA practice. Some farmers become cautious as a result of this, while other become deliberate and discerning. This is evident in how some farmers now confirm that they crosscheck other sources of information to verify and establish the authenticity of CSA, for instance the issue of weather forecast. In this way, the loss, while it is painful, becomes a lesson. This observation finds support in the study of Loftus (2005) who established that once misinformation is embedded in memory, it changes how future information is processed, even when it is later corrected.

The behavioural response of farmers going back to the old ways of farming in response to information disorder is another important issue. This tendency does not imply only an aversion to innovation but a focus on reliability and trust. The regression outcome validates that

misinformation and confusing messages have the potential to lead farmers to give up newer practices, even those related to CSA, in favour of more previous preferred practices. This was seen in the change in Ijaye where a farmer noted that he opted to go back to the use of NPK fertilisers after having poor outcomes with a liquid organic fertilizer. This findings supports what Stroud (2019) averred as a loss of trust in institutional science. It was not a denial of progress as such, but a decision based on the fact that the farmer had been disappointed before and on the sense that new practices were not to be trusted.

In the same vein, the positive correlation between information disorder and adoption of wrong practices (0.2380) indicates yet another implication that although new practices in agriculture are embraced, they might be used in the wrong way because of misinformation or ambiguity. This highlights the importance of quality and regular extension services. The interviews have shown that a large number of farmers now rely on extension officers to validate or clarify information. This is what Ogunnaike *et al.* (2021), found that interpersonal trust between farmers and extension workers can serve as a protective factor against the propagation of misinformation.

Also, the effect of alternative sources of information seeking has a two-fold impact. On the one hand, some farmers have access to a variety of information channels, including WhatsApp groups and YouTube channels; on the other hand, others can be exposed to unverified or misleading information more frequently. It is in line with the arguments of Treen, Williams, and ONeill (2020) who state that digital platforms are more focused on engagement and reach than on the accuracy of the information, thus contributing to the misinformation spread. Likewise, McChesney (2008) cautions against the commercial interests that undermine the editorial independence of the media channels resulting in an information environment where truth is often neglected.

In all, the analysis proves that the impact of information disorder is in different dimensions which include cognitive, emotional, social, and institutional. Distorted or conflicting information at the cognitive level changes the process of reasoning and memory. On the emotional level, past disappointments result in an increased level of scepticism. Socially, peer networks can either support or debunk misinformation based on their own accuracy in information. Institutionally, the failure of policy and the failure to deliver on promises undermines trust in official sources. These layers interact to influence the willingness of the farmers to adopt, reject, or misapply the CSA practices. Therefore, such findings support the necessity of the agricultural communication system that would not only focus on the accuracy but credibility, building trust, and media literacy to make sure farmers receive actionable and reliable pieces of information.

Mechanism through which farmers fact-check CSA information

The findings of this objective indicated that farmers in Oyo State use a multi-layered mechanism to fact check information on CSA. This is done through extension officers, interpersonal networks, direct observation and growing social media platforms. At the center of this process is the role of extension officers, who farmers continually point to as their most trusted and reliable source of CSA verification. The extension officers are not merely viewed as the agents of technical information but as reliable sources, who guide the farmers through conflicting information ecosystem. This is consistent with the study of Alarima *et al.* (2020) who observed that farmers will be more willing to receive and follow CSA advice when it is presented by trusted individuals like extension workers, researchers, or community leaders. Likewise, Oyedele (2018) identified that the positive attitude towards climate information was highly determined by the level of trust that farmers had in the credibility of the message and the messenger.

This trend of using extension officers as a source of verifying CSA information indicates a greater principle at play, which is that trust is not only a social concept but a functional need in the environment where confusing information is prevalent. When farmers are confronted with conflicting, incomplete or overstated claims, whether through social media, from colleagues, or government sources, they tend to go to those who have demonstrated consistency and closeness over the years. It can be concluded, therefore, that the trustworthiness of CSA communication is not necessarily determined by the content, but by the source and the way this relationship has been developed over-time. This finding also indicates that in situations where media fragmentation and digital misinformation are increasing, the interpersonal relationship between extension officers and farmers serves as a stabilizing factor. This concept builds upon Alarima *et al.* (2020) and further suggests that technical knowledge should be complemented with relational trust to achieve behavioural change. Even in cases where other sources such as radio or online sources, present CSA information, farmers appear to cross-check it with the view of extension agents, which is a form of cross-fact checking. More so, based on the results of Oyedele (2018), it can be concluded that the acceptance of the message is not a result of the exposure but rather the perceived authenticity of the message, particularly in rural areas where farmers might have been disappointed with the official sources or have had an experience of the failed inputs in the past. What this means is that when developing communication strategies, one should not only think about the accuracy of CSA messages, but also about the history and credibility of those delivering those messages.

In addition to extension officers, agricultural research institutions play a crucial role in farmers' verification of CSA information by acting as authoritative sources of technically validated knowledge. Corroborating this, Adetola, Akintayo, and Olomjobi (2024) found that National

Agricultural Research Institutes (NARIs) in Southwest Nigeria deploy multiple communication strategies to raise farmers' awareness of agricultural technologies. This has enhanced the reach and credibility of institutional information. Similarly, in a comparative assessment of agricultural technology adoption, Adesiji *et al.* (2017) observed that research institutes and universities influence the adoption of innovations by validating them and serving as information hubs within the agricultural knowledge system. Moreover, in Nigeria where there are multiple extension services, institutions such as the Cocoa Research Institute of Nigeria (CRIN) are well recognized in Oyo State, which enhances farmers' trust in institutional data and advisory outputs. These studies affirm that agricultural institutions are more than peripheral actors; they are central validators and communicators whose involvement helps resolve conflicting information, reduce misinformation, and strengthen trust in CSA communication.

More so, the farmers also often confirm CSA information by reaching out to fellow farmers. Such peer networks are essential in the circulation of agricultural knowledge, particularly in communal and rural areas where informal mentoring and experiences are prevalent. As averred by Edet (2024) that even though government extension agents are viewed as credible, a large proportion of farmers continue to depend on their fellow farmers, especially when they are in the community meetings. This process of peer-to-peer verification promotes learning, although it may create problems in situations where misinformation is disseminated through this method. According to Adeagbo *et al.* (2021), local social networks and collective deliberation are usually employed by farmers to assess new methods in agriculture. Nevertheless, such networks can be as good as the news they disseminate. The less experienced farmers can unintentionally transmit inaccurate information, which can make the decision-making process more difficult and make the CSA initiatives less effective.

The fact that the farmers are fact checking Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) information using peer networks is both a strength and a weakness of agricultural knowledge systems. On the one hand, these interpersonal relationships are community-based support systems that are available and that strengthen collective learning and localized adaptation. The validation of information by experienced farmers may increase confidence and lead to faster adoption of CSA practices. Nevertheless, the use of informal peer verification also has dangers, especially when the people spreading the advice are not knowledgeable enough or are working on the basis of hearsay. This dynamic, as it can be observed in the findings and confirmed by Adeagbo *et al.* (2021) and Edet (2024), adds an element of uncertainty to the situation, what may be trusted based on familiarity may, in fact, be inaccurate. This implies that peer verification is a significant social measure, but it should be supplemented with more formal and professionally guided interventions to reduce the unintentional transmission of misinformation and to facilitate more effective CSA decision-making.

New digital platforms are gaining significance as a verification mechanism by farmers, but they are used secondarily to individual and community-based ones. More and more farmers said they make use of Google, agricultural websites and YouTube to verify what they are hear on CSA elsewhere. This increased digital interaction is part of a wider trend in the world of increased rural digital literacy. The present findings deepen the understanding established by Alhassan and Haruna, (2024), who mentioned that younger and more tech-savvy farmers are starting to seek online information to get timely updates on weather, pest outbreaks, and new methods of farming. However, the usage of digital tools also has its problems. The platforms like WhatsApp and YouTube can become a source of information or a source of misinformation, depending on the quality of the information posted. This reinforces the position taken by Treen *et al.* (2020)

that online algorithms tend to give precedence to viral content rather than truthful information, and media literacy is an essential skill that farmers need to learn to operate in the online environment.

The increased adoption of digital tools by farmers is an indicator of an emerging trend of self-directed learning and increased access to CSA information, especially among younger or more digitally savvy people. Nevertheless, this change also puts farmers at risk of un-moderated content, the accessibility of which is not necessarily accurate. The capacity of farmers to identify factual and incorrect information is becoming important as they continue to explore Google and YouTube. That is why it is important to emphasize that digital platforms are both facilitators of agricultural knowledge and potential disruptors of it, and this is why it is necessary to conduct specific media literacy training to make sure that digital empowerment leads to informed decision-making.

Besides these external sources, most of the farmers use their own personal experiences to confirm the CSA claims. An example is that farmers explained that they occasionally experiment with new inputs on a small area of their farm before investing fully. This type of localized testing is consistent with Adeagbo *et al.* (2021), who stated that personal observation is one of the most reliable types of verification among rural farmers. It is not just a control over external information but also a means of reconciling general recommendations and local conditions, including soil type, microclimates, and crop compatibility.

These combination of verification practices show that there is a shifting, holistic fact-checking practice among farmers. Most farmers, has revealed from the findings do not rely on a single source of information but rather triangulate sources of information by cross checking information

with extension officers, other farmers, media, personal observation and occasionally the internet. This practice reflects the principles of inoculation theory, which posits that exposure to minor misinformation, when followed by corrective information, builds cognitive resistance to future misinformation (Cook *et al.*, 2017). In this respect, frequent contact with diverse sources and credible sources equips farmers to be more ready to recognize, challenge, and disregard information disorder.

Challenges faced by farmers while fact-checking CSA information

This objective was to also find out the challenges that farmers face while checking the authenticity of CSA information they receive. Misleading information provided by different sources is one of the most significant problems in all the farm settlements. Farmers reported conflicting information on critical farming issues like control of pests, fertilizers, and plant spacing. Such mixed feedback causes confusion and many people either delay or completely avoid the new practices. This aligns with the findings of Shitaye, Tadesse, and Enkuahone (2024), who stated that discrepancies in agricultural recommendations tend to cause doubt in the minds of farmers, which consequently discourages them to use new innovations. Such a trend of reluctance implies that intention can be overridden by confusion when the messaging is inconsistent, even in situations when farmers have heard of the benefits of CSA. It also shows the delicate aspect of trust in agricultural communication, once lost, it is more difficult to restore. To make CSA policies effective, coherence of messages in different channels should be given priority so as not to erode the confidence of farmers.

The second major issue is the misinformation that occurs among fellow farmers. Although these network is crucial in community learning, farmers in this study reported cases of peers with good

intentions sharing wrong or obsolete information. This was a problem prevalent in all the four farm settlements. Edet (2024) confirms this finding and adds that informal networks of farmers, despite their significance, may occasionally turn into sources of misinformation, especially when there is no established system to certify the knowledge that is being shared. This implies that being close and knowing each other is not sufficient to ensure reliability in sharing knowledge. Uncontrolled misinformation can lead to the popularization of the wrong practices, which makes CSA even more difficult.

Another challenge that impedes the capacity of the farmers to fact-check CSA information further is the poor mobile network coverage particularly in the more rural farm settlements such as Ogbomosho and Ijaye. These locations were situated close to the outskirts of the town. Farmers described the problem of poor mobile signals and unreliable internet connections that prevent them from easily accessing digital agricultural information, weather information, or reach extension officers. This Finding reaffirms the study of Ajayi, *et.al.* (2021), which also emphasized that mobile network inadequacies in rural Nigeria have a devastating effect on the access of farmers to timely agricultural information and limit their capacity to react promptly to new challenges in farming. At a time when digital tools are becoming more common in agricultural extension systems, poor connectivity is more than a challenge; it becomes a gatekeeping mechanism. It makes farmers unconnected with innovation and delays the dissemination of timely interventions.

Also, another significant barrier is the language barrier and excessive use of technical terminologies in CSA materials. Particularly, farmers in Ijaye cited difficulties in working with extension materials written in English or with scientific terms they did not understand. In the

same way, the language of the labels of pesticides and fertilizers raised concerns among farmers in Eruwa. They proposed that materials should be translated to local languages to make them more accessible. This finding is consistent with the observation of Munyua (2000) who stressed the significance of culturally relevant communication and simplified language in agricultural extension services so as to make them inclusive and clear. This indicates that even correct information can be inaccessible when not framed well. When the language employed is either too complicated or not well known, it becomes a kind of passive exclusion. It stresses that CSA communication must not only be scientifically correct but linguistically and culturally sensitive to its recipients.

Finally, the problem of time and the lack of support of extension officers was also discussed as another challenge in fact-checking CSA information. Agriculture is a time consuming endeavour and most of the farmers observed that they did not have time to clarify or cross check information. Most of the farmers are usually busy on their farms during the day. Moreover, there were not enough extension officers and therefore, it was not always possible to have the support in time. These, together with the poor internet access, further decreased the capacity of farmers to factcheck CSA information at the time they most required to do so. In the absence of timely feedback, farmers will tend to resort to less dependable sources of information or to trial-and-error methods of learning. An increase in the capacity of extension, not simply in numbers but in responsiveness and reach, has the potential to make a difference in the capacity of farmers to make confident, informed decisions.

4.5 Theoretical Implications of the Study

This study utilised two theories namely; inoculation theory and diffusion of innovation theory.

The findings of this study can be linked to the usage of the theories as follows.

Inoculation Theory: According to Inoculation Theory, when people are exposed to weaker forms of misinformation, and then followed by corrective information, they can strengthen their resistance to future persuasive information that is capable of misleading them. This theory is relevant in the context of this study, where farmers actively engage in fact-checking by reaching out to sources like the extension officers or verifying from fellow farmers, and checking on the internet to verify CSA information. Through this verification process, farmers are actively and effectively inoculating themselves against misleading information. For instance, a farmer at Ijaye who noted how he verified claims about GMO on the internet had gone through the process of inoculation and with more confirmation from the extension officer. This process allows farmers to build resilience or immunity against false claims and enhance their ability to critically evaluate future information. The increased reliance on extension officers and the use of trusted digital platforms for information verification indicate that farmers are actively developing immunity to misinformation, aligning with the core tenets of Inoculation Theory. It is important to note that the process in information disorder can only be broken when people inoculate themselves with factual information from trusted sources.

In addition, although the main objective of the inoculation theory focuses on pre-exposure, theorists like John Cook and van der Linden have shown that the inoculation can also be therapeutic or post-exposure. This means that those who have already been misled can develop resistance or immunity after they are made to understand how and why the information was

untrue. In the context of this study, farmers who lost money as a result of information disorder, inaccurate weather forecasts or unmet government promises can turn those negative experiences into a form of learning inoculation. When extension officers come in to clarify why such claims are misleading, farmers not only regain some confidence in the sources they can trust but also become less susceptible to similar falsehoods in the future. This implies that corrective communication can be used even after damage has occurred to build resilience in the long term.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory: This theory suggests that innovations (like CSA practices) spread through social systems over time, with adoption occurring at different rates depending on individual and social factors. The findings from this study support this theory, as farmers' adoption of CSA practices is strongly influenced by the information they receive and the sources of information. While studies have established that formal channels of agricultural information dissemination such as extension services and radio play a crucial role in the transfer of information of agricultural innovations, the study also established the influence of informal networks, more importantly, fellow farmers and social media. Inaccurate information, especially from social media, fellow farmers or misleading media advertisements, can slow down the adoption of CSA practices. Adoption of CSA practices is delayed by misleading information which farmers receive from their fellow farmers or misleading advertising in the media. Farmers hold back new technology implementation including improved seedlings and organic fertilizers because they received conflicting advice and struggled with negative experiences in the past. When farmers encounter false information they tend to stay with their traditional farming practices which prevents the adoption of new CSA in the settlements. The theory also emphasized the importance of trust and communication within social networks, as demonstrated by the role

of extension officers and fellow farmers in overcoming the barriers to the adoption of innovation.

More so, according to Rogers Diffusion of Innovations theory, there are factors that affect adoption which include the attribute of the innovation, the communication channels, the characteristics of the adopter and the social system in which the adopters dwell (Rogers, 2003). Nevertheless, from the findings of this study, one more aspect that should be taken into consideration, is information disorder. The dissemination of misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation has become a major factor affecting adoption choices. For instance, inaccurate information about new farming inputs, misinterpreted weather forecasts, or politically driven promises from the government may deter farmers to use climate-smart practices, irrespective of the innovation quality. In this way, information disorder serves as a disruptive element in the diffusion process, influencing perceptions, adding to distrust, and even reversing adoption. By suggesting the addition of information disorder as a mediating variable to the diffusion of innovation theory, this study expands the theory to be more representative of the communication issues of the digital age.

Global Village Theory

The theory of Global Village, developed by Marshall McLuhan (1964), describes the way in which contemporary communication technologies bridges time and space, integrating people and communities into one interactive system where information flows instantly. Within the framework of this research, the theory has been used to point out how digital communication tools, including mobile phones, WhatsApp groups, radio-internet convergence, and social media platforms have transformed farmers in Oyo State into members of a global network of

agricultural knowledge. The platforms have enabled farmers to now receive global climate information, weather predictions, and climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices in real-time, without regard to geographic and institutional boundaries.

The results of this research support the major assumptions of the Global Village theory by demonstrating that digital connectedness has altered the local agricultural communication landscape into a connected space where the local and global sources of information are becoming more and more unclear. Farmers no longer have to be limited to the use of extension officers or community meetings; instead, they can communicate with the world agricultural experts, online communities and digital advisory services. This online connectedness increases exposure to various CSA information and innovations that would otherwise have not been available in the traditional communication mediums.

But, the same interconnectedness which the Global Village fosters, enhances the spread of misinformation and disinformation. This study found that the very platforms that linked farmers with correct CSA information are also the ones that spread false or misleading information regarding farming. This is in accordance with the fact that McLuhan (1964) noted that new media redefine the human association and perception not only in terms of linking people but also in terms of changing the nature of truth, authority, and trust in the communication systems. In this respect, the village formed by digital technologies turns into the one where rumors and facts co-exist and spread at the same speed, contributing to the issue of information disorganization among farmers.

Moreover, the results are consistent with the modern understanding of the Global Village theory as expounded by Roudometof, (2023) and Coker, (2023) who avered that globalization via

digital technologies generates not only informational inclusivity but also epistemic inequality. Whereas farmers can access expertise globally, others are caught up with the overload of information that is too much and conflicting or unverified. Such an imbalance illustrates the fact that digital globalization has produced an information-saturated and verification-lite world.

Hence, the Global Village theory assists in understanding the contradiction of digital communication in agrifood setting, that democratizes access to climate-sensitive information and increases the dissemination of misinformation. The theoretical implication on the study is that to encourage the use of CSA in Oyo State, it is necessary to not only enhance digital access of the farmers but also reinforce local information verification systems in the global network. Creating local villages that are smart in the broader global information ecosystem, by developing trusted community-based interfaces, controlled digital avenues, and extension-media partnership would reduce the impact of misinformation and preserve the benefits of global connectivity.

In conclusion, the theoretical implications of these findings revealed the importance of targeted communication strategies in promoting the adoption of CSA practices. Extension officers, digital platforms, and fellow farmers play a major role in both the inoculation process and the diffusion of CSA innovations. Farmers must be trained to make use of the available verification tool such as the internet to verify wrong information they may have encountered. Digital literacy will not only enhance their ability to verify CSA information but also empower them to adopt innovative farming techniques more efficiently. By addressing information disorder and ensuring the accuracy of information coming from sources, the farming communities will become more informed and resilient, leading to more acceptance and implementation of climate-smart practices.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations of the study. The summary of findings is about the abridged version of the results of this study, while the conclusion states what the study contributes to the field of knowledge. Moreover, the recommendations focus on suggestions for further studies in this field of knowledge, policies and practice that can be derived from the findings of the study by the concerned policy makers and stakeholders.

5.2 Summary of Findings

The major findings of the study are summarized as follow

The study revealed that there are different degrees of understanding and knowledge of CSA information disorder among the farmers. A significant proportion demonstrated a detailed understanding, particularly in Ogbomosho (47.0%) and Akufo (41.9%) having the highest levels, while Ijaye (28.3%) and Ogbomosho (34.3%) showed moderate awareness. A smaller percentage of farmers were unfamiliar with the concept, most notably in Ijaye (31.7%), indicating that while many farmers understood CSA issues, some are unaware of information disorder among farmers in Oyo State. The thematic analysis of CSA information disorder knowledge and understanding among the farmers in Oyo state identified four major themes. First, the farmers were able to relate their understanding and knowledge of CSA information disorder to misleading weather forecasts which was seen to be a major issue especially in Eruwa and Ijaye. This was because according to the farmers, incorrect predictions of weather by Nimet was tagged as misleading

and this resulted in loss for the farmers. Another theme which was misleading agricultural products was identified as a noticeable challenge. Farmers revealed that they encountered exaggerated claims about improved seedlings and varieties, which were later found to be untrue and has led to growing distrust in some CSA products and sources of information like social media. Farmers are cautious of advertisements on the internet talking about improved seedling. Moreover, Farmers also received incorrect agricultural advice from fellow farmers. 21% of farmers identified misleading information on CSA practices such as planting schedules, spacing and use of input such as pesticide. Finally, a theme that resonates through all the farm settlements as regards information disorder is unfulfilled government promises which have contributed to distrust, of government programmes among the farmers. The study therefore found that farmers have a good understanding of what constitute information disorder but this is dependent on their experiences and level of exposure to such issue.

The study also found that the major sources of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) information among farmers in Oyo State, just as it has been with other agricultural information and established in previous studies remain extension officers and radio. In most of the farm settlements, farmers rated extension officers as very reliable, with Ogbomoso (65.9%) and Ijaye (65.8%) showing high levels of trust. Radio also ranked high, particularly in Ijaye (57.5%) and Akufo (52.6%), though some farmers found it less reliable due to issues like language barriers and poor signal coverage. However, Social media which was once noted in studies to be where farmers have low engagement (Oyedele, 2018), has gained popularity, especially among younger and more educated farmers. Social networking platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, and YouTube now serve as sources of information to farmers. Farmers said they make use of social

media to get weather forecast update, check farming techniques, and communicate with extension officers.

Moreover, this study found that there are a number of important sources of information disorder in the communication of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) among farmers in Oyo State. One of the most frequently mentioned source of inaccurate information was social media platforms (WhatsApp, Facebook, and YouTube). Although most farmers often use these platforms to get agricultural tips, they are also exposed to unverified information, particularly on fertilizers, hybrid seeds and quick-yield solutions. This is consistent with what Treen *et al.* (2020) and Vosoughi *et al.* (2018) observed, that social media information travels fast, particularly when it appeals to emotions or has been shared by people of the same age group, irrespective of its validity.

Another notable source of information disorder was government sources. The lack of support and unfulfilled promises was mentioned by farmers as a factor that influenced their perception of CSA messages from the government. Farmers were not ready to accept the information at even when the information was factually correct because of previous experiences of unfulfilled inputs or late programs. This confirms the results of Adebayo (2024) and Fadairo *et.al.* (2020) that demonstrate the role of trust in the public institutions in the reception of agricultural advice.

Traditional media especially radio has been historically an important tool in rural farming communication. Farmers prefer it because it is accessible, it uses their local language, and it is there all the time. Nonetheless, some of the respondents observed that some radio programs are increasingly becoming promotional with advertisement claims on CSA information that do not are later found to be incorrect. This implies a necessity to draw more distinct lines between

education and advertising to preserve the credibility that the traditional media already possesses. As scholars such as Popoola (2018) and McChesney (2008) have warned, sometimes, the increased commercial influence may make the difference between the delivery of information and the promotion of products. However, these results do not undermine the integrity of radio in general but rather the significance of content integrity in a trusted platform.

CSA knowledge sharing is still based on farmer to farmer learning and advice given by extension officers. Nonetheless, the study also discovered that the two sources are sometimes associated with information disorder-particularly when peer advice is given based on incomplete knowledge or when the demonstration of the extension officers does not produce expected outcomes. This is why it is so important to maintain training, participatory communication, and adaptation of recommendations to local realities in order to maintain trust. The evidence presented in this study also suggests that the information disorder encountered by farmers in Oyo State influenced them in their decision-making regarding the adoption of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) practices. One major influence was doubt that has been strengthened in the farmers towards government-backed CSA initiatives. Farmers, expressed distrust toward government programs due to unfulfilled promises and inconsistent communication. This has further led to hesitation by farmers in the adoption of CSA practices promoted by the government.

Misinformation as a result of exposure of farmers to exaggerated claims about improved seedling has led to financial losses and disappointment among farmers, which in turn discouraged them from trying new agricultural techniques. The fear of wasting money on ineffective products or unproven practices has resulted in reluctance to experiment with new CSA methods. This has further pushed them back to old traditional farming methods which are not climate smart friendly. More influence was noticeable in misleading information shared on social media

platforms and word-of-mouth which further increased the reluctance to adopt new CSA practices.

The study found that extension officers are the main fact checking source of CSA information verification utilized by farmers in Oyo State. This was followed closely by agricultural institutions and fellow farmers but this method sometimes leads to the spread of misleading information. Additionally, farmers make use their personal experiences to validate new methods while there was an increasing shift in the usage of online sources to fact check CSA information by the farmers,. However, radio, TV, and newspapers not favourite choice of fact checking mechanism for the farmers.

The study further found that the most significant challenge farmers face while trying to fact-check CSA information is conflicting information from different sources, leading to confusion and difficulty in verifying CSA recommendations. Another challenge was misinformation from fellow farmers, with a significant number of farmers in all settlements facing this issue. Additionally, poor mobile network coverage was also a major barrier, particularly in rural areas like Eruwa and Ogbomosho, where farmers are limited to verify information through mobile phones or online sources. Language barriers and technical jargon in CSA materials also hindered farmers' understanding, especially in Ijaye and Eruwa. Other challenges included time constraints while on farm duties, insufficient support from extension officers, and lack of internet access, all of which impedes the timely and accurate verification of CSA information.

5.3 Conclusion

First, this study has established that the level of understanding and knowledge of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) information disorder among farmers in Oyo State varies, with some farmers

demonstrating detailed knowledge while others are unknowledgeable about it. It was clear that, farmers in Ogbomoso and Akufo had higher levels of understanding compared to those in Ijaye and Eruwa. This shows that there is a gap in knowledge and it brings to the fore the need for more awareness campaign by stakeholder. However, the study also revealed that the knowledge and understanding of CSA information disorder were shaped by a number of factors which include misleading weather forecasts, exaggerated claims about agricultural products, incorrect farmers to farmer advice, and unfulfilled government promises. These factors have led to distrust in CSA-related information, particularly from government agencies and social media platforms. As a result of this, more effort should be put into ensuring that accurate messages on CSA reach the farmers in order to rebuild trust in these sources.

Furthermore, the study found that extension officers and radio remain the most trusted sources of CSA information, while social media is gaining popularity, especially among younger and more educated farmers. However, misinformation from these sources has influenced farmers' decision-making, causing skepticism toward government-backed CSA initiatives and discouraging the adoption of CSA techniques. As a result, some farmers have reverted to traditional, less climate-smart practices.

Based on these findings, policymakers and agricultural stakeholders; this include the extension officers, the government, agricultural input producers, NGOs and others should focus on enhancing the reliability of CSA communication by strengthening extension services. Government should ensure information are not for the purpose of scoring political points but ensure that promises are kept. Additionally, more effort should be put in place to strengthen the fact checking initiatives which will ensure that farmers have access to accurate and trustworthy resources. By addressing these challenges, the adoption of CSA practices can be improved.

5.4 Limitations

This section looked into the limitations of the study and how they were surmounted. Although the study managed to attain its goals and come up with valid lessons regarding the effects of information disorder on climate-smart agricultural (CSA) practices in the context of Oyo State, various field-related limitations were encountered in the process of the research.

1. Geographical Limitation

First, the study was limited to farm settlements in Oyo State, South-West Nigeria. As a result, the findings may not be fully generalizable to some regions of the country, particularly the northern part, which has different climatic conditions, farming systems, and socio-cultural dynamics. However, this limitation was partly mitigated by ensuring that the study covered the major farm settlements in the three senatorial districts of Oyo State.

2. Methodological Limitation

Secondly, the study adopted a cross-sectional study design, which collected data at a single point in time. This meant that changes in farmers' experiences with information disorder and adoption of climate-smart agriculture (CSA) over time could not be fully captured.

3. Bureaucratic Limitation

Delays were experienced in securing permission from the Oyo State Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, particularly from the Extension Services Unit. Gaining clearance required going through different levels of bureaucratic procedure, from the Honourable Commissioner to the Director of Extension Services, and finally to the field. This slowed down the

commencement of fieldwork, but was eventually resolved through official letters and constant follow-up until clearance was granted.

4. Respondent-Related Limitation

Some farmers were initially hesitant to participate due to past experiences with frequent survey exercises or unmet government promises, which had created widespread mistrust of official inquiries and research activities. This challenge was mitigated through the mediation of extension officers, who helped build trust with farm settlement leaders and their members.

5.5 Recommendations

Based on the findings and limitations of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to improve the verification of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) information and increase the adoption of CSA practices among farmers in Oyo State:

1. **Strengthening Extension Services:** as the major source of information to farmers, Extension officers should be further trained and equipped with up-to-date CSA information and practical solutions to ensure they remain the most trusted and reliable source of information for farmers. It was discovered that some extension officers do not have the full grasp of the issues that surround information disorder. They need to increase their knowledge base so as to be able to help the farmers in mitigating against the incidences of information disorder as it relates with CSA. Regular training and field visits should be conducted to build trust and enhance their effectiveness in addressing farmers' concerns.

2. **Promoting Digital Literacy:** With the increase in shift towards online sources for CSA information search and verification, there is a need to enhance digital literacy among the farmers. Training programs should be put in place to help farmers effectively cope in the digital platforms space like facebook, WhatsApp, and others so as to be able to verify CSA information and make informed decisions.
3. **Addressing Misinformation on Social Media:** Efforts should be made to tackle misinformation circulating on social media by increasing awareness about the risks of unverified claims. Agricultural institutions, extension officers, and NGOs should collaborate to provide accurate, verified information on these platforms, while also educating farmers on how to distinguish between credible and misleading sources.
4. **Simplifying CSA Communication:** CSA information should be communicated in clear, simple language, particularly for farmers with limited formal education. Technical jargon should be minimized, and materials should be available in local languages to ensure accessibility and understanding.
5. **Integrating Extension 4.0 Framework:** Adopting Extension 4.0, which combines ICTs, data-driven advisory services, social media, and participatory approaches, will modernize agricultural extension. This approach addresses the reliance on digital platforms found in this study, while reducing misinformation through structured, verified, and participatory systems.

5.6 Contribution to Knowledge

1. This study extends Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory by showing that information disorder disrupts the innovation-decision process, which are the stages of knowledge,

persuasion, and adoption. It revealed that information disorder is as a barrier (or we can refer to it as noise in the context of communication studies) to the adoption of CSA, especially when it spreads faster and more persuasively than verified agricultural information. This contributes to the communication theory by identifying how false information interfere with diffusion of innovation in agri-food sector.

2. The use of Inoculation Theory, the study shows that farmers who are exposed to prebunking messages or who understand the rhetorical techniques used in misleading information are more resistant to CSA-related disinformation. This contributes to media effects literature by demonstrating how psychological resistance to misinformation can be cultivated through strategic communication—not only in health or politics, but also in agriculture and rural development.
3. This study has broadened knowledge in the field of communication studies on how misinformation affects climate-smart agriculture communication. It has provided evidence that communication breakdown limits CSA adoption. This reinforces the role of media literacy, trusted sources, and locally relevant communication in supporting development outcomes, thereby expanding the scope of communication for development (C4D) scholarship.
4. The study contributes to media credibility literature by showing that farmers have higher trust in interpersonal (extension officers) and local radio stations over digital or institutional sources. It reveals how understanding and repetition shape credibility. This has provided more opportunities for designing effective, local communication strategies that counter misinformation at the grassroots level.

5.7 Suggestions for Further Studies

Based on the findings and limitations of this study, the following suggestions for further research are proposed:

1. Future studies could investigate the role of different communication channels (e.g., extension services, Traditional media, and social media) in spreading misinformation about CSA practices. Research could assess the effectiveness of each channel in mitigating information disorder and how well they help farmers distinguish between reliable and unreliable information.
2. Further research should be extended to other regions of Nigeria, particularly the northern part of the country, where climatic conditions, farming systems, and socio-cultural contexts differ. Comparative studies across regions would provide a broader understanding of how information disorder influences the adoption of climate-smart agriculture nationwide.
3. Future research can adopt a longitudinal design to track how farmers' encounters with misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation evolve over time and how these affect CSA adoption. Such studies would provide deeper perspective into changes in farmers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices.
4. Media Framing of CSA Information: Future studies could analyse how CSA-related information is framed in different media (radio, TV, newspapers, social media) and how these frames influence farmers' perceptions, trust, and adoption of CSA practices.

5. Future research could conduct comparative analyses of communication channels- traditional media (such as local radio and print), social media platforms, and interpersonal communication through extension officers and farmer groups, to evaluate their effectiveness in promoting climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1

IN-DEPTH INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR EXTENSION OFFICERS

The following interview questions are designed by the researcher to elicit the perspectives and knowledge of extension officers assigned to the farm settlement under study in Oyo state regarding farmers' awareness, sources, influences, fact-checking mechanisms, and challenges related to information disorder in climate-smart agriculture practices in Oyo State.

False information, Misleading information, Wrong information, Confusing information, Inaccurate information, Fake news, Unreliable information

No ·	Climate-Smart Agriculture Practice	Tick (✓)
1	Drought-resistant and heat-tolerant crop varieties (<i>crops that survive with less water and tolerate high temperatures</i>)	
2	Crop rotation (<i>changing crops each season to improve soil and reduce pests</i>)	
3	Intercropping and companion planting (<i>growing different crops together for soil health and pest control</i>)	
4	Late river side planting- <i>these are farmers who plant during dry season beside the river (ewedu, maize and other crops)</i>	
5	Cover cropping (<i>using plants to protect soil from erosion and enrich nutrients</i>)	
6	Conservation tillage (<i>resting of farm land for a while to gather nutrient</i>)	
7	Organic soil improvement (<i>adding manure, wood ash or compost to improve soil fertility</i>)	
8	Contour farming and terracing (<i>planting on slopes to reduce erosion</i>)	
9	Irrigation (<i>watering crops directly</i>)	
10	Rainwater harvesting (<i>collecting rainwater for use during dry seasons</i>)	
11	Weather and climate forecasting (<i>planning farm activities based on weather forecasts</i>)	
12	Improved animal breeds (<i>using breeds resilient to heat and diseases</i>)	

13	Shade agro forestry (<i>Planting of trees like banana around livestock pen to prevent heat</i>)	
14	Eco friendly Pen construction (<i>Constructing livestock pen in house in a way that helps to ensure heat is not retained or west east pen construction</i>)	
15	Rotational grazing (<i>moving livestock to avoid overgrazing and allow pasture recovery</i>)	
16	Efficient waste management and biogas production (<i>converting waste to biogas and fertilizer</i>)	
17	Renewable energy use (<i>using solar or wind power to cut farm energy costs</i>)	
18	Fuel-efficient machinery (<i>using machines that consume less fuel</i>)	

RQ 1. How well do farmers in Oyo State know about information disorder in climate-smart agriculture?

- i. What do you think "information disorder" means?
- ii. Have you ever come across wrong or confusing information in agriculture?
- iii. How aware are farmers about information disorder in climate-smart agriculture?
- iv. How would you rate farmers' understanding of information disorder or incorrect information in climate-smart agriculture?
- v. Can you give examples that show farmers' knowledge or lack of knowledge about information disorder in climate-smart agriculture?

RQ 2. What are the sources of information disorder in climate-smart agriculture among farmers in Oyo State?

- i. Where do farmers in Oyo State usually get their information about climate-smart agriculture?
- ii. Are there any sources that often spread wrong or misleading information about climate-smart agriculture?
- iii. Can you share any examples of how information disorder spreads in climate-smart agriculture among farmers?

RQ 3. How does information disorder affect climate-smart agriculture practices among farmers in Oyo State?

- i. How does information disorder affect farmers' decisions on climate-smart agriculture?
- ii. Have you seen cases where misinformation or disinformation changed how farmers practice agriculture?

RQ 4. How do farmers in Oyo State check if the information on climate-smart agriculture is correct?

- i. How do farmers usually check if climate-smart agriculture information is true or not?
- ii. Are there any specific ways you and farmers use to fact-check climate-smart agriculture information?
- iii. Can you give examples of times when you or farmers successfully checked the accuracy of information?

RQ 5. What challenges do farmers face when checking the accuracy of climate-smart agriculture information?

- i. What are the main difficulties farmers face when trying to check if climate-smart agriculture information is correct?
- ii. Are there any barriers that make it hard for farmers to fact-check information?
- iii. Can you share examples of times when farmers found it hard to tell accurate information from misinformation in climate-smart agriculture?

Appendix 2

IN-DEPTH INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR FARMERS

The following interview questions are designed by the researcher to elicit the perspectives and knowledge of farmers in the farm settlement under study in Oyo state regarding their awareness, sources, influences, fact-checking mechanisms, and challenges related to information disorder in climate-smart agriculture practices in Oyo State.

RQ 1. How well do farmers in Oyo State know about climate-smart agriculture information disorder?

- i. What does the term 'information disorder' mean to you?
- ii. Have you ever encountered any misleading or incorrect information in your agricultural practices?
- iii. How well do you think you understand the concept of information disorder in climate-smart agriculture?
- iv. Can you give any examples where farmers showed either good or poor understanding of misinformation in climate-smart agriculture?

RQ 2. What are the sources of climate smart agriculture information disorder among farmers in Oyo State?

- i. Where do you usually get your information about climate-smart agriculture?
- ii. Have you noticed any specific sources or channels that often provide inaccurate or misleading information?

- iii. Can you share any instances where false information about climate-smart agriculture was spread within your community?

RQ 3. How does information disorder influence the practice of climate smart agriculture among farmers in Oyo state?

- i. How does misleading information affect your decisions about climate-smart agriculture practices?
- ii. Have you ever seen misinformation leading to changes in the way farmers work?
- iii. What challenges do you face in identifying accurate information from misleading information about climate-smart agriculture?

RQ 4. What mechanisms do Oyo state farmers utilize in fact-checking climate smart agricultural information disorder?

- i. How do you verify the accuracy of the climate-smart agriculture information you receive?
- ii. Are there any specific methods or practices you use to check the facts of this information?
- iii. Can you give examples of successful fact-checking efforts that have helped you or other farmers to avoid misinformation?

RQ 5. What challenges do farmers in Oyo State face when checking the accuracy of climate-smart agriculture information?

- i. What are the main difficulties you face when trying to verify climate-smart agriculture information?
- ii. Have you encountered any barriers that make it hard to fact-check information effectively?
- iii. Can you share any specific instances where it was challenging to tell accurate information from misinformation in climate-smart agriculture?

Appendix 3

Questionnaire for Farmers on Climate-Smart Agriculture Information Disorder

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this interview. This study is a research on climate-smart agriculture practices and the challenges farmers face regarding accurate information and its adoption. This research aims to understand your experiences, perspectives, and decision-making processes related to climate-smart agricultural practices.

Your responses will provide valuable insights that can contribute to improving agricultural practices and the support available to farmers. All the information you provide will be kept confidential and used solely for research purposes.

Information disorder: means information that is wrong, misleading, or confusing. This can happen on purpose or by mistake, and it includes false news, rumors, or incorrect information

Demographic Information

Age: 18-25 26-35 years 36-45 years 46-55 years 56-65 years 66 years and above

Gender: Male Female

Educational level: No Formal Education Primary Education Secondary Tertiary
Postgraduate (Master's/PhD) **Farm Size:** (Acres).

Commodity.....**Years of Experience**..... **Name of Farm settlement**.....

1. General Knowledge:

1a. Which of these climate smart agriculture are you aware of.

No	Climate-Smart Agriculture Practice	Tick (✓)
1	Drought-resistant and heat-tolerant crop varieties (<i>crops that survive with less water and tolerate high temperatures</i>)	
2	Crop rotation (<i>changing crops each season to improve soil and reduce pests</i>)	
3	Intercropping and companion planting (<i>growing different crops together for soil health and pest control</i>)	
4	Late river side planting- <i>these are farmers who plant during dry season beside the river (ewedu, maize and other crops)</i>	
5	Cover cropping (<i>using plants to protect soil from erosion and enrich nutrients</i>)	
6	Conservation tillage (<i>resting of farm land for a while to gather nutrient</i>)	
7	Organic soil improvement (<i>adding manure, wood ash or compost to improve soil fertility</i>)	
8	Contour farming and terracing (<i>planting on slopes to reduce erosion</i>)	

9	Irrigation (<i>watering crops directly</i>)	
10	Rainwater harvesting (<i>collecting rainwater for use during dry seasons</i>)	
11	Weather and climate forecasting (<i>planning farm activities based on weather forecasts</i>)	
12	Improved animal breeds (<i>using breeds resilient to heat and diseases</i>)	
13	Shade agro forestry (<i>Planting of trees like banana around livestock pen to prevent heat</i>)	
14	Eco friendly Pen construction (<i>Constructing livestock pen in house in a way that helps to ensure heat is not retained or west east pen construction</i>)	
15	Rotational grazing (<i>moving livestock to avoid overgrazing and allow pasture recovery</i>)	
16	Efficient waste management and biogas production (<i>converting waste to biogas and fertilizer</i>)	
17	Renewable energy use (<i>using solar or wind power to cut farm energy costs</i>)	
18	Fuel-efficient machinery (<i>using machines that consume less fuel</i>)	

i. what is your level of understanding about climate-smart agriculture?

- Detailed understanding
- Basic awareness
- Unfamiliar

Can you describe it in few sentences?

.....

.....

.....

2. Specific Knowledge:

i. What is your level of knowledge and understanding about climate-smart agriculture information disorder (incorrect or misleading information)?

- Detailed understanding
- Basic awareness
- Unfamiliar

ii. Can you provide examples or explanation of what you think information disorder (misleading information) in the context of climate-smart agriculture is?

Examples.....

.....

.....

3. Sources of Climate-Smart Agriculture information:

i. Where do you always get information about climate smart agriculture and how reliable are they? (Please tick as appropriate)

Source of Information	Yes	Very Reliable	Somewhat Reliable	Not Reliable
Extension officers				
Radio				
TV				
Newspaper				
Fellow farmers				
Social Media Platforms (Whatsapp, Instagram, tiktok, facebook twitter etc)				
Agricultural cooperative groups				
Family members involved in farming				
Religious groups or gatherings				
Mobile agricultural advisory services				
Agricultural research institutions				
Government bulletins				
Online Search (Google, agricultural websites)				
NGOs involved in agriculture				
Agricultural suppliers (seed/fertilizer vendors)				
Other: (Please state)_____				

4. Can you identify any sources that you believe provide inaccurate or misleading information on Climate smart agriculture?

Source of Information	Yes	No
Extension officers		
Radio		
TV		
Newspaper		
Fellow farmers		
Social Media Platforms (Whatsapp, Instagram, tiktok, facebook twitter etc)		
Agricultural cooperative groups		
Family members involved in farming		
Religious groups or gatherings		
Mobile agricultural advisory services		
Agricultural research institutions		

Government bulletins		
Online Search (Google, agricultural websites)		
NGOs involved in agriculture		
Agricultural suppliers (seed/fertilizer vendors)		
Other: (Please state)_____		

5. Examples:

i. Can you share any specific examples of inaccurate information you have encountered about climate-smart agriculture?

 --

ii. Which source(s) did you come across this information

.....

6 How has the inaccurate or misleading information you received about climate-smart agriculture influenced your farming practices? Tick as appropriate.

- i. I am less likely to try climate-smart practices because I don't fully trust the information.
- ii. I have used practices that didn't work well because of wrong information .
- iii. I have lost money as a result of incorrect information I adopted on climate smart agriculture
- iv. I am unsure which climate-smart practices to follow because of conflicting information.
- v. I have delayed trying climate-smart practices because the information is confusing.
- vi. I have avoided spending money on climate-smart tools or resources because of misleading information.
- vii. I have gone back to traditional farming methods instead of trying climate-smart options.
- viii. I have started looking for information from other sources to clear up confusion about climate-smart agriculture.
- ix. I ask local experts or community groups for advice to understand climate-smart practices better.
- x. Other (please specify): _____

6b. Can you describe any other changes you made based on information that later turned out to be wrong or misleading?

7. Verification Methods:

i. How do you verify the accuracy of the information you receive about climate-smart agriculture?

Verification Methods	Tick
Consult agricultural extension officers	
Ask from fellow farmers	
Depend on my Personal experience	
Conduct small trials	
Check online sources (Google, agricultural websites)	
Verify from government bulletins or advisories	
Seek advice from agricultural institutions	
Verify through radio/TV/newspaper sources	
Ask family members with farming experience	
Consult agricultural cooperatives or community groups	
Check with NGOs involved the practice	
Seek religious or community leader guidance	
Verify from extension officers	
Other: _____	

ii. Are there any other steps you take to fact-check (Check if information is correct or not) this information? Yes No

please specify if yes _____

ii. How effective do you find these resources or tools?.....

10. Challenges Faced:

i. What challenges do you face when trying to verify the accuracy of climate-smart agriculture information?

Limited access to reliable information sources	
High cost of consulting agricultural experts	
Poor mobile network coverage	
Conflicting information from different sources	
Language barriers or technical jargon	
Lack of internet access	
Difficulty in finding trustworthy sources	

Time constraints due to farming activities	
Insufficient support from extension officers	
Misinformation from other farmers	
Lack of resources for accurate verification	
Distance from agricultural institutions or cooperative	
Lack of regular training or workshops on new practices	
Difficulty in accessing updated government bulletins	
Other: _____	

Conclusion

8. Final Thoughts:

i. Is there anything else you would like to add about your experiences with climate-smart agriculture information?

ÀTÒJỌ ÌBÉÈRÈ FÚN ÀWỌN AGBẸ LÓRÍ ALÁYÉ TI KO PE NÍNÚ ÒNÀ OGBIN TÓ BÓJÚ MÚ AYÉ (CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE)

Ẹ ẹ ẹ gán an fún gbiba tí ẹ gbà láti kópá nínú ifòròwáni lenu wo yíí. Ìwádíí yíí jẹ ìṣẹ àyèwò lórí **ṣíṣe ìṣẹ agbẹ ní ònà tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu** àti àwọn ìṣòro tí àwọn agbẹ n dojú kò nípa **aláyé tí kò pé (Information disorder)** àti bí èyí ẹ ní ipa lórí bí wọn ẹ gbìyànjú láti tẹlẹ. Ìdí pàtàkì ìṣẹ àyèwò yíí ni láti lóye irírí yín, àwọn àfíyèsí yín àti bí ẹ ẹ máa ẹ àyànmò nípa ònà ogbin tó ba oju ojo mú.

Ìbáṣepò yín pèlú wa yòò fún wa ní ìmò tí ó lè ràn wa lowo lórí bí a ẹ lè mú kí ìṣẹ agbẹ túbò dáa àti bí a ẹ lè fi èkò yíí gbé àwọn agbẹ laruge. Gbogbo ohun tí ẹ bá sọ yòò jẹ ìkòkò patapata, a ó sì lò ó fún àwùjọ ìṣẹ iwádíí nìkan.

Aláyé Nípa Ẹnikẹni Tó N Fèsì

Ojo Ori: 18-25 26-35 years 36-45 years 46-55 years 56-65 years 66 years and above

Ako/Abo: Ako Abo

Ìpele Èkò (Educational Level): Kò ní èkò Èkò Èkò gíga alákoḃẹrẹ Èkò gíga Masta/Phd

Iwọn Ilẹ Ogbin: **Ohun tí o n ẹ lórí ilẹ yíí** **Ìrírí oḃún nínú ìṣẹ agbẹ** **Orúkọ adúgbò agbẹ rẹ (Farm Settlement**

Àwọn Ònà Ogbin tó bójú mú ayé wo ni o ti gbò/ní ìmò nípa rẹ?

No.	Ìṣẹ Ònà Ogbin tó bójú mú ayé	Fowosi (✓)
1	Irugbin tí kò ko le ku lasiko oda	
2	Yíyí irugbin padà lẹkùnréré	
3	Gbígbin irugbin oríṣííríṣíí papò	
4	Gbígbin lẹgbẹẹ odò nígbà tí òjò korò	
5	Gbígbin fún itójú ilẹ (Cover cropping)	
6	Fífi ilẹ sílẹ láí fi ọwọ kàn án fún àsìkò die	
7	Ìmúdára ilẹ pèlú, eerú igi, àtawon ohun atowoda	
8	Gbígbin lórí òkè tàbí ilẹ tí ó n yára	
9	Omi igbalode ti o ropo ojo	
10	Kíkó omi òjò jo (Rainwater harvesting)	
11	Asotele oju ojo	
12	Sisin eran igbalode	
13	Gbígbin igi pèlú agbo (Agroforestry)	

14	Kíkó ile ẹran ní ọna ti oba oju ojo mu	
15	Piparo ile tie ran fin jeko	
16	Ìtójú àkúnya tàbí idòtí àti síṣe biogas	
17	Àmúlò agbára oorun tàbí afẹ́fẹ́	
18	Èrọ agbẹ tó dín epo lilo ku	

i. Kí ni ìpele ìmò rẹ nípa ọ̀nà iṣẹ́ agbẹ́ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu (CSA)?

- Mo ní ìmò jinlẹ
- Mo ní ìmò díẹ
- Mi ò mò rárá

Sé o lè ṣàlàyé rẹ ní ṣókí?

.....

.....

.....

2. Sé o ní ìmò kànkàn nípa aláyé to ko pe (ítàn tàbí ifihàn àìtọ) nípa ọ̀nà iṣẹ́ agbẹ́ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu?

- Bèèni
- Rárá

ii. Sé o lè fún wa ní àpẹẹrẹ tàbí àlàyé nípa ohun tí ìwọ rántí nípa aláyé ti ko pe lori iṣẹ́ agbẹ́ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu?

Àpẹẹrẹ:

.....

.....

.....

3. Àwọn orísun ìmò nípa ọ̀nà iṣẹ́ agbẹ́ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu?:

i. Níbo ni o ti máa ń gba ìmò nípa ọ̀nà iṣẹ́ agbẹ́ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu, báwo sì ni ìdánílójú rẹ sí wọn

Orísun Imoran	Bèèni	Gbẹ̀kẹ̀lé Gidi-Gidi	Díẹ ni Mo Gbẹ̀kẹ̀lé	Mi ò Gbẹ̀kẹ̀lé rara
Àwọn olùkọ agbẹ				
Rádiò				

Tilifisọ̀nù				
Ìwé iròyìn				
Àwọn agbẹ egbe mi				
Àwọn pẹpẹ ayelujara (Whatsapp, Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, Twitter àti bẹẹ bẹẹ lọ)				
Egbé àjọ agbẹ				
Molebi mi to n sise agbe				
Egbé ijọ Olorun				
Olumòràn ogbin lórí fónú				
Ilé-ẹ̀kọ̀ ìwádíí ogbin				
Ìwé iròyìn ijọba				
Ìsàwárí lórí Ayélujára				
Àwọn ajọ aláàánú tó n sise lori ogbin				
Àwọn oníṣòwò irugbin				
Omíràn: (Jòwó ṣàlàyé)				

4. Nje o lè sọ àwọn orísun awon aláyé ti kò pe lori isẹ agbẹ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu

Orísun Imoran	Béèni	Béèko
Àwọn olùkọ̀ agbẹ		
Rádiò		
Tilifisọ̀nù		
Ìwé iròyìn		
Àwọn agbẹ egbe mi		
Àwọn pẹpẹ ayelujara (Whatsapp, Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, Twitter àti bẹẹ bẹẹ lọ)		
Egbé àjọ agbẹ		
Molebi mi to n sise agbe		
Egbé ijọ Olorun		
Olumòràn ogbin lórí fónú		
Ilé-ẹ̀kọ̀ ìwádíí ogbin		
Ìwé iròyìn ijọba		
Ìsàwárí lórí Ayélujára		
Àwọn ajọ aláàánú tó n sise lori ogbin		
Àwọn oníṣòwò irugbin		
Omíràn: (Jòwó ṣàlàyé) _____		

5. Apere:

i. Sẹ o lè pín pelu wa àpẹrẹ kankan pato ti àlàyé àitọ́ tí o ti pàdé nípa isẹ agbẹ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu?

ii. Níbo ni o ti rí àlàyé yí tàbí àwọn orísun wo lo ti gba

6 Báwo ni àlàyé àìtò nípa isẹ agbẹ tó bá ayípadà ojú-ojo mu ẹ nípa ipa lóri bí o ẹ n ẹ isẹ agbẹ rẹ? Jòwọ, fi àmì sí ohun tó bá yẹ.

- i. Mi ò nífẹẹ láti gbìyànjú àwọn ilàna isẹ agbẹ tó bá ayípadà ojú-ojo mu torí pé mi ò ní igbàgbò pátápátá nínú àlàyé nàa.
- ii. Mo ti lo àwọn ilàna tí kò ẹisẹ dáadáa torí àlàyé àìtò tí mo gbọ.
- iii. Mo ti padánù owó torí àlàyé àìtò tí mo tẹlẹ nípa isẹ agbẹ tó bá ayípadà ojú-ojo mu.
- iv. Mi o mò dájú alaye ti mole tẹlẹ torí pé àlàyé naa tako ara wọn.
- v. Mo ti fa seyin ninu igbìyànjú isẹ agbẹ tó bá ayípadà ojú-ojo mu torí pé àlàyé nàa kún fún idàrúdàpò.
- vi. Mo ti yàgò nina owo lóri àwọn irinsẹ isẹ agbẹ tó bá ayípadà ojú-ojo mu torí àlàyé àìtò.
- vii. Mo ti padà sẹyìn sí ọna isẹ agbẹ ibilẹ dípò kí n gbìyànjú àwọn àşàyan isẹ agbẹ tó bá ayípadà ojú-ojo mu.
- viii. Mo ti bèrè sí ni wá àlàyé látínú àwọn orísun mí láti lè yanjú idàrúdàpò nípa isẹ agbẹ tó bá ayípadà ojú-ojo mu.
- ix. Mo n bèrè imoran lati ọwọ àwọn akosemose agbègbè tàbí egbẹ agbe láti ní imòràn dájú nípa isẹ agbẹ tó bá ayípadà ojú-ojo mu.
- x. Ohunmíràn (jòwọ şàlàyé): _____

6b. ẹ o lè şàlàyé àwọn ayípadà mí tí o ẹ lóri isẹ agbẹ rẹ torí àlàyé tí ó yàtò sí òtítò

7. Àwọn ònà Ìjẹrisí:

i. Báwo ni o ẹ n jẹrisi itónisónà tabi imoran lóri isẹ agbẹ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu?

Àwọn ònà Ìjẹrisí	Fowosi (✓)
Bèèrè lodò awọn olùkó agbẹ	
Bèèrè látòdò àwọn agbẹ míràn	
lo irírí ti ara mi	
Şe idánwò kékeré	
Şàyèwò àwọn orísun ikànni lóri ayélujára (Google, àwọn ikànsí agbẹ)	
Ìjẹrisi látínú iwé ikilò ijoba	
Bèèrè imòràn látòdò àwọn ilé-èkó agbẹ	
Ìjẹrisi láti ori rádíò/telifison/iwe iroyin	
Bèèrè látòdò àwọn idílé mi tí ó ní irírí agbẹ	
Ìmúlò àwọn egbẹ isòkan agbẹ	
Bèèrè imòràn látòdò olórí ẹsin	
Ìjẹrisi látòdò àwọn oşisẹ itòsónà	

Òrò mírán: _____	
------------------	--

ii. Sẹ àwọn ìgbésè mírán wà tí o n gba láti jèrìsì ìtònisónà yìí (Sàyèwò bí ìmòrán nàà jé òtító tàbí kó tó)? Bèèni Rára

Jòwó sàlàyé tí oba se bèèni _____ "

ii. Báwo ni ìrìnṣé yìí ṣe wúlò tó?....."

10 Ìṣòro Tí o n dojú kọ:

i. Kí ni àwọn ìṣòro tí o n dojú kọ nígbà tí o bá n gbìyaju láti jèrìsì ìmòrán lórí ìṣé agbẹ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu?

Ìṣòro Tí A Dojú kọ	Fowosi (✓)
Ànfaàní sí orísun ìmòrán tó dájú kó tó	
Iye owó tó ga láti kó ìmòrán látòdò àwọn àkòwé agbẹ	
Ìjakulẹ̀ láti orí nẹ̀tẀọ̀kì ìbáńisòrò alágbèéká	
Ìmòrán tí ó tàkò ara rẹ̀ láti orísirísí orísun	
Ìdena láti ibi èdè tí a fí n gbọ̀ ìmòrán	
Àìní àyè sí erò ayélujára	
Ìṣòro ní lílo orísun ìmòrán tó dájú	
Àìsí àyè nítorí àwọn ìṣé agbẹ	
Àìní ìtònisónà tó péye látòdò àwọn oṣìṣé ìtòsónà	
Ìmòrán tí kò tó láti ọ̀dọ̀ àwọn agbẹ̀ mírán	
Àìní àwọn ohun èlò tó péye fún ìjẹ̀rìsì tó tó	
Ìjìnnà sí àwọn ilé-èkó agbẹ̀ tàbí àwọn ẹ̀gbé ìṣòkan agbẹ̀	
Àìní ìmòrán tó péye tàbí àkókó ẹ̀kó nípa àwọn ilàna tuntun	
Ìṣòro ní lílo àwọn iwé ìkílò ìjọba	
Òrò mírán: _____	

Ipari

8. Òrò Ikẹhin:

i. Sẹ ohun mírán wà tí o fẹ̀ kó àkóónú nípa ìrírí rẹ̀ pẹ̀lú ìmòrán lórí ìṣé agbẹ̀ tí ó bá ayipada oju-ojo mu?

.....

.....